

**COMMUNICATON AND PARENTAL ENGAGEMENT DURING TRANSITION TO
PRIMARY SCHOOL: A PARTICIPATORY CASE STUDY IN SCOTLAND**

CAROL JANET STROM

Thesis submitted in partial fulfilment of the requirements
of the University of the West of Scotland
for the award of Professional Doctorate

June 2025

Declaration

Banner Number: B00261326

I declare that, except where explicit reference is made to the contribution of others, that this thesis is the result of my own work and has not been submitted for any other degree at the University of the West of Scotland or any other institution.

Name: *Carol J. Strom*

Date: June 2025

Abstract

Transition from Early Learning and Childcare (ELC) to primary school benefits from involving parents/carers in the transition process that their child is going through, because children's positive emotional response to school could be affected by the families' preparedness for their child starting school (Bérubé *et al.*, 2018). The Covid-19 pandemic and restrictions imposed on Scottish educational settings (Scottish Government, 2020) during this time, influenced the communication tools used to actively involve parents/carers during the transition process, as almost all communication reverted to digital, when school and ELC 'lockdowns' were introduced. As Scottish educational settings returned to normality during the school year 2022-2023, it was an appropriate time to review the communication tools used by ELC and primary schools to communicate with parents/carers during transition programmes. This study aimed to ascertain the communication tools that parents/carers preferred were used, to promote their active parental engagement during their child's transition from ELC to primary school. The study, being a Scottish exploratory case study, where the 'case' was a standalone ELC setting and the main primary school its children were transitioning to. It adopted a participatory research approach via a steering group of parents, Transition Coordinator, a senior leader representative from both the ELC and the primary school and the researcher, with the group collectively making decisions. These decisions included which research data collection methods should be employed and deciding from the data collected, which communication tools and parental engagement opportunities should be taken forward for the forthcoming academic year transition programme. Qualitative data collection methods included semi-structured interviews, with parents of pre-school children transitioning from the ELC to the main primary school in August 2023, and focus groups with ELC staff and future Primary One teachers. Additional data in the form of reflective notes completed by participants and the researcher were also collected. Results suggested that communication tools for parental engagement opportunities included a parental preference for face-to-face practical opportunities – exploring the primary school and meeting core school staff. The study acknowledged that parental engagement with the primary school was valuable, but identified barriers to their involvement, particularly for working parents, including the timing and advance notice of these planned transition events. Using the

generated data, the steering group made collective decisions about the communication and parental engagement opportunities during the transition from ELC to the main primary school for the forthcoming academic year. For the primary school these included: opportunities for parents to see round and meet core staff prior to school enrolment in January; introducing a monthly transition newsletter from January; and information requested by parents including about school uniform to be provided earlier as opposed to waiting for the primary school parental transition talk in June. Through adoption of a participatory research approach via the steering group, the two parent members of the group acknowledged that their opinions were valued and they had an equal voice in the collegiate decisions made by the group.

Keywords: communication, parental engagement, transition, ELC, primary school, participatory, case study

Acknowledgements

I would like to thank the following people without whom I would not have been able to complete my Doctoral research. The management and participants from both Rainbow ELC and Blue Primary School who participated, without whom I would not have been able to undertake this case study. I would also like to express my deepest appreciation to my lead supervisor Dr. Carole Bignell whose knowledge, dedicated support and guidance has given me the confidence to see the research through from initial concept to its conclusion. Her positivity was crucial during times of uncertainty via her email responses and online catch ups. I would also like to thank my second supervisor Dr. Beth Cross who used her insight in the subject to challenge my thoughts and opinions.

I also extend my sincere thanks to colleagues both past and present who have supported me throughout the course of my Professional Doctorate journey. Their encouragement and support over the past three years have kept me motivated to complete my thesis.

My biggest thanks go to my family and friends, who have been supportive throughout my academic journey. They have been particularly understanding over the past three years when I have been unable to spend time catching up with them, as I have dedicated time to completing this thesis. I would also like to thank my father for always believing in me and giving words of encouragement throughout my academic journey so far. Lastly, I would like to mention my husband Lee and thank him for his patience, support and understanding for the time I have needed to dedicate to complete my thesis. You have been an amazing support.

Professional Research Output

March 2015

Planned and presented a PowerPoint presentation to local authority Early Years colleagues who were interested in transition from nursery to primary school. The presentation concentrated on my research, including how nursery staff and primary school staff can work together to support children during the transition from nursery to primary school.

February 2018

Planned and presented as a guest lecturer, a PowerPoint presentation, to students undertaking the Bachelor of Arts Childhood Studies degree at the University of the West of Scotland. The presentation focussed on current transition from nursery to primary school research, including my own.

October 2018

Informal PowerPoint presentation to parents at a local private ELC setting about starting primary school. The presentation focussed on, how an additional year at nursery may be beneficial to children who were legally entitled to an additional funded year at nursery – known as a deferred child. It was informed by current research, including my own.

November 2019

Ten Minute PowerPoint presentation of my Master of Education degree research study at 'The Educational Colloquium' at University of Glasgow. The event was attended by academics and students from University of Glasgow, University of Strathclyde and University of the West of Scotland.

September 2023 – May 2024

Worked as a member of the local authority Early Years transition working party, to complete the final draft of the local authority best practice guidance, for transitions within ELC settings and from ELC settings to primary school. This guidance was distributed in June 2024 to all ELC settings and partnership nurseries within the local authority.

Glossary of Key Terms

The following glossary contains some of the key terms used within this thesis.

Care Inspectorate – a regulatory body that oversees ELC settings in Scotland.

Catchment Primary School – this is a school area within the local authority that is defined by the child's permanent home address.

Deferred Child – this is a child who was aged to start primary school but is having an additional funded year at an ELC setting and will start school the following August term.

Depute Head Teacher (DHT) – a teacher who is part of the senior leadership team in a primary school and deputises for the Head Teacher when required.

Digital Communication – mode of communication that relies on electricity or batteries.

Early Learning and Childcare (ELC) – settings that offer education and care to children up until they start primary school. It is not compulsory for children to attend, but all children from aged three until they start primary school are entitled to a yearly 1140 hours funded by the Scottish Government.

Early Years Practitioner (EYP) – all staff who have an Early Years professional qualification (HNC in Childcare and Education, or above) and work with children within an ELC setting. They are registered with the regulatory body the Scottish Social Services Council (SSSC).

Education Scotland – the body responsible for supporting quality and improvements in learning and teaching within all aspects of Scottish education.

Head of Early Learning and Childcare Centre – manager of the ELC setting, who has responsibility for all aspects of the centre. This includes the care, welfare and education of the children and leadership and management of staff.

Local Authority – an organisation that is officially responsible for public services and facilities within a particular area. Within Scotland there are 32 local authorities.

Nursery – an alternative term for an ELC.

Parental Engagement – a parent’s engagement in their child’s learning at home, school and wider community.

Parental Involvement – getting involved in the work and life of an educational setting.

Pre-school Child – a child who has not yet started primary school but will be starting primary school in August.

Primary School – in Scotland children start primary school between the ages of four and a half and five and a half years of age. They spend seven years at primary school before moving onto secondary school. Primary school marks the start of formal schooling.

Primary One – the first year of formal schooling for children in the Scotland. Children are eligible to start school if they are five between 1st March and last day of February. August is the only intake of children.

Traditional Communication – face to face communication, telephone communication and printed communications e.g., letters, booklets.

Transition Coordinator – a member of ELC staff responsible for leading and overseeing the transition from an ELC to the different primary schools that the children will be going to. It could also be a member of staff from the primary school who liaises with ELC settings to set dates for transition events for children who will be starting their primary school. This includes co-ordinating primary school transition events for both children and families.

Abbreviations

Depute Head Teacher	DHT
Early Learning and Childcare	ELC
Early Years Practitioner	EYP
Focus Group/Groups	FG/FGs
His Majesty's Inspectorate of Education	HMIe
Senior Leadership Team	SLT
Steering Group	SG/SGs
Steering Group Parent 1	SP1
Steering Group Parent 2	SP2
Steering Group Parent 3	SP3

Table of Contents	Page
Title	i
Declaration	ii
Abstract	iii
Acknowledgements	v
Professional Research Output	vi
Glossary of Key Terms	vii
Abbreviations	ix
Table of Contents	x
Tables	xvii
Appendices	xviii
Chapter One: Introduction to the Research	1
1.1. Why Undertake This Research?	1
1.2. Professional and Personal Perspectives	2
1.2.1. Professionally	2
1.2.2. Personally	3
1.3. The Scottish Context	6
1.4. Research Questions	7
1.4.1. Aims	8
1.5. Outline of Thesis	9
1.6. Chapter Summary	10
Chapter Two: The Context	11
2.1. Introduction	11
2.2. Policy Context	11

2.3.	Educational Context	14
2.3.1.	Location	14
2.3.2.	ELC	15
2.3.3.	Primary School	16
2.3.4.	Transition	16
2.4.	Chapter Summary	18
Chapter Three: Review of Literature		19
3.1.	Introduction	19
3.2.	Conceptualising Transition	19
3.3.	Conceptualising Parental Involvement and Parental Engagement	24
3.4.	A Systematic Consideration of Informing Literature	27
3.5.	Communication	29
3.5.1.	Home/School Communication	29
3.5.2.	Digital Communication with Parents/Carers	31
3.5.3.	Section Summary	36
3.6.	Parental Involvement and Engagement	37
3.6.1.	School Policy Development for Parental Engagement	37
3.6.2.	Parental Involvement and Engagement during Transition to Primary School	39
3.6.3.	Barriers to Parental Involvement and Engagement	45
3.6.4.	Section Summary	47
3.7.	Chapter Summary	48
Chapter Four: Methodology		50
4.1.	Introduction	50

4.1.2. Axiology, Ontology and Epistemology	50
4.1.3. Case Study	53
4.1.4. The Positionality of the Researcher – Insider, Outsider or Inbetweener	54
4.1.5. Participatory Research Approach	56
4.1.6. Navigating Issues of Power in Participatory Research	58
4.2. Participants	60
4.3. Qualitative Data Collection	64
4.3.1. Steering Group	65
4.3.2. Focus Group Interviews	69
4.3.3. Individual Semi-Structured Parent Interviews	71
4.3.4. Accompanying Notes/Reflective Notes	72
4.4. Analysing the Data	74
4.4.1. Transcription and Analysis	74
4.5. Trustworthiness in Qualitative Research	78
4.6. Ethical Considerations	80
4.7. Conclusion	81
Chapter Five: Findings	83
5.1. Introduction	83
5.1.2. Contextualisation	83
5.2. Findings Related to Research Aim One	84
5.2.1. Digital Communication	87
5.2.1.1. The Nursery App and School App	87
5.2.1.2. Emails	89

5.2.1.3. Blue Primary School Website	90
5.2.2. Traditional Communication Methods	91
5.2.2.1. Letters	92
5.2.2.2. Face-to-face	92
5.2.3. Additional 'informal' Method of Communication	94
5.2.4. Communication with Parents at Local Authority Level	94
5.2.5. Summary of Key Findings for Aim One	95
5.3. Findings Related to Research Aim Two	96
5.3.1. Getting to Know Blue Primary School	96
5.3.2. Establishing a Professional Relationship with School	
Staff	100
5.3.3. Summary of Key Findings for Research Aim Two	103
5.4. Findings for Research Aim Three	104
5.4.1. Timing of the Transition Talk	104
5.4.2. Advance Notification of Events	105
5.4.3. Different Care Arrangements	106
5.4.4. Possible Solutions to Barriers to Parental Engagement with	
Transition Opportunities	107
5.4.5. Summary of Key Findings for Aim Three	107
5.5. Policy Awareness	108
5.5.1. Summary of Policy Awareness	109
5.6. Findings Related to Research Aim Four	109
5.6.1. Parent Reflections on the Participatory Research Approach	110
5.6.2. Professional Reflection on the Participatory Research	
Approach – Head of ELC, Transition Coordinator and DHT	112

5.6.3. Summary of Key Findings for Research Aim Four	115
5.7. Conclusion	116
Chapter Six: Discussion and Implications of Findings	117
6.1. Introduction	117
6.2. Discussion and Implications Related to Research Aim One	117
6.3. Discussion and Implications Related to Research Aim Two	124
6.4. Discussion and Implications Related to Research Aim Three	127
6.5. Discussion and Implications Related to Research Aim Four	129
6.6. Discussion and Implications Related to Policy Awareness	131
6.7. Conclusion	132
Chapter Seven: Researcher Reflections on a Participatory Approach	134
7.1. Introduction	134
7.2. Positionality and Power	134
7.3. An understanding of What Participatory Research Approach Involves within Education Through the Adoption of Galletta and Torre (2019) Key Elements of Participatory Action Research	136
7.4. Galletta and Torre (2019) as a Tool for Reflection	138
7.5. Overcoming Practical Barriers to Participation	143
7.6. Conclusion	143
Chapter Eight: Recommendations and Conclusion	145
8.1. Introduction	145
8.2. Recommendations Related to Research Aim One	145
8.2.1. Recommendations for Rainbow ELC/ Blue Primary School	145

8.2.2.	<u>Recommendations for both the EY and Primary</u>	
	<u>Sectors in Scotland</u>	147
8.2.3.	<u>Recommendations for Local Authority</u>	148
8.3.	<u>Recommendations Related to Research Aim Two</u>	148
8.3.1.	<u>Recommendation for Rainbow ELC/</u>	
	<u>Blue Primary School</u>	148
8.3.2.	<u>Recommendations for both the EY and Primary</u>	
	<u>Sectors in Scotland</u>	149
8.4.	<u>Recommendations Related to Research Aim Three</u>	150
8.4.1.	<u>Recommendations for Rainbow ELC/Blue Primary School</u>	
	<u>and both the EY and Primary Sectors in Scotland</u>	150
8.4.2.	<u>Recommendations for Local Authority</u>	151
8.5.	<u>Recommendations Related to Research Aim Four</u>	151
8.5.1.	<u>Recommendations for Rainbow ELC/</u>	
	<u>Blue Primary School</u>	151
8.5.2.	<u>Recommendations for Parents</u>	152
8.5.3.	<u>Recommendations for both the EY and Primary Sectors</u>	
	<u>in Scotland</u>	152
8.6.	<u>Recommendations Related to Policy Awareness</u>	152
8.6.1.	<u>Recommendation for Rainbow ELC/</u>	
	<u>Blue Primary School</u>	152
8.6.2.	<u>Recommendations for both the EY and Primary Sectors</u>	
	<u>in Scotland</u>	153
8.6.3.	<u>Recommendation for Policy Makers</u>	153

8.6.4. Recommendation for Local Authority	153
8.7. Response to Research Questions	153
8.8. The Uniqueness of this Professional Doctorate Research Study	155
8.9. Update Since Conclusion of Research	156
8.10. Limitations of the Study	157
8.11. Recommendations for Future Study	157
8.12. Final Reflections	158
References	161

Tables	Page
<u>Table One - Participant Involvement and Data Collection</u>	<u>64</u>
<u>Table Two - Parent Participants</u>	<u>83</u>

Appendices	Page
<u>Appendix 1 – Summary of Publications Relevant to Research Study</u>	173
<u>Appendix 2 - Process for Searching and Selection of Literature Articles</u>	178
<u>Appendix 3 – ELC Letter</u>	188
<u>Appendix 4 – Primary School Letter</u>	190
<u>Appendix 5 – Participant Information Sheet – Steering Group (Parents)</u>	192
<u>Appendix 6 - Consent Form (Steering Group)</u>	195
<u>Appendix 7 - Participant Information Sheet – Steering Group</u> <u>(ELC/Primary Staff)</u>	197
<u>Appendix 8 - Participant Information Sheet – Individual Interviews</u> <u>(Parents/Carers)</u>	200
<u>Appendix 9 - Consent Form (Interview)</u>	203
<u>Appendix 10 - Participant Information Sheet – Focus Group</u> <u>(ELC/Primary School Staff)</u>	204
<u>Appendix 11 - Consent Form (Focus Group)</u>	207
<u>Appendix 12 - Reflective Notes Completed</u>	208
<u>Appendix 13 - Steering Group Members</u>	209
<u>Appendix 14 - Final Questions (Individual Interviews)</u>	210
<u>Appendix 15 - Final Questions (Focus Group)</u>	212
<u>Appendix 16 - Data Posters</u>	214
<u>Appendix 17 - Parent Interviews</u>	220
<u>Appendix 18 - Reflective Note Template Steering Group Meeting One/</u> <u>Reflective Note Template ELC/Teacher/Parents</u>	221
<u>Appendix 19 - Reflective Note Template Steering Group Meeting Two</u>	222

<u>Appendix 20 - Initial Codes</u>	<u>223</u>
<u>Appendix 21 - Themes</u>	<u>226</u>
<u>Appendix 22 - Steering Group Meeting Three Task (Collated Results)</u>	<u>228</u>
<u>Appendix 23 - What to Take Forward</u>	<u>239</u>
<u>Appendix 24 - Data Timeline</u>	<u>240</u>
<u>Appendix 25 - Steering Group Data Collection</u>	<u>258</u>

Chapter One: Introduction to the Research

1.1. Why Undertake This Research?

Research is about increasing knowledge, including the creation of new knowledge when a knowledge gap has been identified. For this research study, a gap in knowledge was identified, from a Scottish perspective, related to the communication tools that parents would prefer were used during the Early Learning and Childcare (ELC) to primary school transition programme that their child was part of. Additionally, both parental engagement and parental involvement transition opportunities that parents, also from a Scottish perspective would prefer to be involved in. Moreover, this knowledge gap was supported through the adoption of a participatory research approach which directly involved parents, an area identified within *Chapter Three: Review of Literature*, as missing from current research. The knowledge gained from this study would inform not only my own practice, but also professionals working within the Early Years (EY) and Primary sectors of Scotland. As someone who works in the EY sector, this study would increase my credibility, within the field of transition and parental engagement within the local authority where I am currently employed, as I disseminate my research to colleagues and other interested parties. Furthermore, the recommendations discussed in Chapter Eight, outline research informed ways to promote and engage parent voice, including the promotion of a participatory research approach. This research will also provide a link between professional policy/guidance in Scotland and practice (Menter *et. al.*, 2011).

Transition from an ELC setting to primary school can, for children and parents, be a period of mixed emotions. It is therefore imperative that professionals from both the ELC and primary school strive to support the child, parent and family through this period of change and adjustment - as the child becomes a school pupil and the parent becomes the parent of a school pupil (Griebeling and Gilbert, 2020). The communication tools used by all parties during this period are vital to ensure clarity for the parent, as many parents navigate this period of transition for the first time (Jose *et. al.*, 2022). Covid-19 and its associated lockdowns, where almost all communication shifted to digital, severely impacted transition programmes from ELC to primary school

in Scotland. However, as normality fully returned to transition programmes offered by ELCs and primary schools in Scotland in August 2022, it was a good time to reflect on the shift towards digital communication and the involvement of parents in the transition process. This research therefore focused on the communication tools used between January 2023 and June 2023, to support parental engagement from ELC to primary school. The research study also focussed specifically on supporting parents/carers through the period of transition from ELC to primary school because their involvement can assist children during this crucial period of time to cope better with the adjustment to school (OECD, 2017). I had considered involving children in the research, but decided for this small-scale professional doctoral research that this was not warranted for a number of reasons. The first was that, being a nursery teacher working in the nursery involved in this exploratory case study, I was fully aware of the support that Rainbow ELC staff already gave children collectively and individually through this specific transition period to Blue Primary School. Moreover, transition to primary school guidance and support recommended by both the local authority and 'Realising the Ambition' (Education Scotland, 2020) were both currently being implemented, through the leadership provided by the Transition Coordinator to support children during this period of transition. Finally, there was recent Scottish research of involving children in transition but limited research of involving parents in transition research from a Scottish perspective. The remainder of Chapter One therefore discusses the professional and personal perspectives related to undertaking the research, before discussing the Scottish context, the research questions and associated aims.

1.2. Professional and Personal Perspectives

As this research study is for a Professional Doctorate qualification, it was important to reflect both professionally and personally the value of undertaking this research.

1.2.1. Professionally

The Scottish Government introduced the *Scottish Schools (Parental Involvement) Act 2006*, with a view to actively promoting ELC and schools working with parents/carers to support their child's education. This legislation requires all ELCs and schools to

work actively with parents. Education Scotland (2022) states this can be achieved through ‘effective parental involvement, parental engagement, family learning and learning at home’ (Education Scotland, 2022, p. 18). Additionally, as part of self-evaluation all schools or ELCs in Scotland should be using ‘*How good is our school?*’ (Education Scotland, 2015) or ‘*How good is our early learning and childcare?*’ (Education Scotland, 2016) to support self-evaluation. Each document consists of a variety of quality indicators that senior leaders and members of staff can use to evaluate their ELC/school practice, including 2.6 ‘transition’, where effective communication and partnerships are advocated to support successful transitions (Education Scotland, 2016). Although within this quality indicator no indication is given explicitly or implicitly about a preferred/desirable mode of communication. All ELCs in Scotland may also share evidence of their partnership with parents and other educational settings, resulting from inspections undertaken by Care Inspectorate. Furthermore, as a society that relies evermore on digital communication, it is therefore imperative within education that digital communication is suitable for engaging parents in school life, including the period of transition from ELC to primary school.

For this research, the focus is transition (an integral part of nursery life) within which ELC settings work with the primary schools that children from their setting will be going to, supporting both the child and their family during this period of change (Education Scotland, 2020). Additionally, as I am a practising teacher in Scotland, there are professional standards I am required to follow and embed within my practice. These include the requirement as part of the standard Professional Skills and Abilities, to ‘work effectively with colleagues, parents/carers ... to enrich learning and teaching and support the wellbeing of all, across the learning community’ (GTCS, 2021, p. 9). This research provided the opportunity to develop and reflect upon these skills for myself as a professional, and to better understand how effective partnership might enhance the nursery child’s transition experience.

1.2.2. Personally

My personal interest in undertaking this research stems from an interest in transition which has lasted more than forty years. As a child, I started Primary One in a Scottish

primary school at four years of age and initially struggled to cope. I was expected to instinctively know what to do, but looking back there had been no transition opportunities for my peers and I prior to starting primary school. Moreover, my parents had not been given any advice on how to support me starting school, or how to adapt to being a parent of a school child. Since entering the Early Years teaching profession, my goal has been to ensure that both parents and children are supported during their child's transition from nursery to primary school.

My academic research into transition, started with my Bachelor of Education Honours Degree research study, where I chose to research 'starting school at four'. The study focussed on whether children who were four years old when they started primary school, coped as well with the tasks they were faced with, as children who had started school aged five. The findings of this small-scale action research study suggested that some boys who were four years of age when starting school, found it harder to concentrate and follow instructions when undertaking a variety of small group tasks in a Primary One class.

More than ten years later my academic journey continued, when I undertook as part of the postgraduate Early Years Teacher Specialism qualification, a quantitative research study into concerns parents may have for their child starting primary school. The findings suggested that, for many parents, their main concerns were practical rather than being about their child being academically ready for Primary One. These concerns were shared with senior leaders of the primary schools that the children were moving onto. It was important the concerns were shared, as these issues could affect parents' ability to support their child, because a parent's anxiety could be transferred to the child, thereby affecting the child's ability to cope with starting primary school (Bérubé *et. al.*, 2018).

Three years later as part of a Leadership for Learning postgraduate qualification, I led a transition working group that supported all transitioning children and their parents. The transition working group consisted of staff representatives from the primary

schools the children would be moving on to and nursery staff. The group developed a variety of resources to support transition to primary school for the primary schools, children and parents. Feedback from participants was positive.

My research interest in transition continued for a Master of Education Degree, where I sought to answer the research question 'what support can help children with social and emotional difficulties make an effective transition from nursery to Primary One?' This qualitative action research study responded to professional dialogue with primary colleagues, which highlighted that some pupils were finding it emotionally and socially challenging to cope with the transition from nursery to Primary One. The findings suggested that enhanced transition programmes were required for these identified children. Recommendations included that transition programmes should actively involve parents and staff in both the EY and Primary sectors working collaboratively. Transition programmes should also be well-planned and cater for individual child's needs, including providing practical school life experiences.

With my passion for transition continuing, and wanting to ensure that parents are actively involved during this crucial period of time, I decided to research a different aspect of transition for the Professional Doctorate. Therefore, this research study has explored the communication tools employed to engage and involve parents during the transition of their child from ELC to Primary One. The specific focus partly arose after receiving a thank you card in June 2021 from a parent of a child in the nursery where I worked at that time as a nursery class teacher. The thank you card related to transition based digital communications via Microsoft SWAY prepared by me and sent out electronically by the primary school. Covid-19 mitigations were still in place for parents during the academic year 2020-2021, meaning that parents were unable to engage in any face-to-face transition opportunities (Scottish Government, 2020). Feedback from a quantitative questionnaire indicated that 80% of parents in this nursery felt that the digital transition-based Microsoft SWAYs had been beneficial, indicating that the parent who sent the thank you card was not alone.

To conclude, I undertook this research within the Professional Doctorate because I genuinely wanted to make a difference. I wanted to promote parental engagement, which for this research sits within the context of transition from nursery to primary school. It is expected that the research recommendations discussed in Chapter Eight, will be pertinent not only to issues of transition but also to the use of a participatory research approach, discussed in section 4.1.5. to support developments in practice.

1.3. The Scottish Context

This research, which took place within a Scottish context, sought to identify opportunities that would actively involve and engage parents throughout their child's transition process from nursery to primary school and identify communication tools that might best allow this to happen. This type of transition commonly known as 'vertical transition' (Education Scotland, 2020) refers to the movement between education levels, including from nursery to primary school. In Scotland, children transition from nursery to Primary One, being eligible to start school in August if they are five between 1st March and end of February.

It is vital that parents are involved in the transition process, because it is suggested that children's positive emotional responses to starting school, are affected by their families' response to being prepared for their child starting school (Bérubé *et al.*, 2018). Furthermore, it is recognised that children do better in school when their parents are involved, as the children are happy when they see their parents taking part (Haut See and Gorard, 2015.) Thus, this type of transition needs to be thoughtfully planned, not ad hoc, as this too could have long term effects on the children if not well managed (Bateson, 2013).

Unfortunately, the process of actively involving parents in ELC to primary school transitions, which traditionally commenced after the child has been registered in the January of the year that they are due to start primary school, was made more challenging in the Spring of 2020. In Scotland, when the Covid-19 pandemic and associated lockdowns were imposed, starting with the first lockdown from 23rd March

2020 to 24th June 2020, all schools/ELC settings closed to all but vulnerable children or children of key workers (Scottish Government, 2020). These mitigations from the Scottish Government, put in place to reduce the spread of Covid-19, had a significant impact on educational transition programmes. Almost overnight, face-to-face opportunities including transition visits for both pupils and parents had to be replaced, with almost all moving to digital forms of communication. The Scottish academic year of 2022-2023 was the first full school year since the March 2020 restrictions, whereby face-to-face indoor parental engagement and involvement could take place. Professional dialogue with primary colleagues made it clear that face-to-face involvement and engagement with parents during nursery to primary transition would be particularly welcomed again. Covid-19 mitigations had resulted in them experiencing a very different (a less positive and engaged) relationship with parents and families of children. Moreover, as a society that relies evermore on digital communication, it is imperative within education that this form of communication is suitable for engaging parents in everyday school life, including within the context of transition. Finally, as already discussed in section 1.2.1, parents/carers are expected through the *Scottish Schools (Parental Involvement) Act 2006*, to be actively involved in their child's educational journey. Through the adoption of a participatory research approach, discussed in detail in section 4.1.5., this research outlines a practical way to actively involve parents in their child's educational journey.

1.4. Research Questions

With educational settings more able to again actively involve parents following the Covid-19 pandemic, I felt this was an appropriate time to reflect, review and discuss the communication methods used for parental engagement during ELC to primary school transition. I wanted to research whether digital communication tools introduced during or since 'lockdown' were meeting the needs of parents and children. Moreover, I was interested to understand how these digital communication tools might be further developed in partnership with parents who would ultimately be using them. Therefore, my research sought to answer the two research questions and associated aims below:

The research questions:

1. What communication tools are pertinent to successfully supporting parental engagement during transition programmes from Early Learning and Childcare to primary school?
2. What are the benefits and challenges of parent/professional partnership work within a participatory approach to research?

1.4.1. Aims

The four aims of the research were:

1. To investigate whether the communication methods employed by both the ELC and the main feeder primary school for parental engagement during the transition process are meeting parents needs and, if not, what alternatives could be used.
2. To identify parental engagement opportunities that parents would like to be involved in during their child's transition to primary school.
3. To identify any barriers to parental engagement during their child's transition from the ELC to the main primary school and how these might be overcome.
4. To investigate what we can learn about parent and professional partnerships from the participatory approach of the study.

In relation to the above aims, *Chapter Three: Review of Literature*, highlighted that since 2018, specifically within a Scottish context there has been limited published academic research into transition from ELC to primary school. This included a lack of research about the communication tools used to engage parents in their child's education and how parents might be involved in the development of these to support transition. This suggested the merit of undertaking this research specifically within the context of Scottish education. Moreover, Dunlop (2017) stated:

The growing number of publications focusing on early childhood transitions attests to the fact that this has become a recognised field of research and practice enquiry.

(Dunlop, 2017, p. 257)

Thereby, supporting transition as the basis of my own research study. This view was further endorsed more recently by Dunlop, Peters and Kagan (2024) who suggested that research within this area had grown, and that transition was currently a focal point for studies that supported the understanding and implementation of transition practices and policies.

1.5. Outline of Thesis

This thesis consists of eight chapters, with Chapter One outlining the importance of the research both professionally and personally and the reason for focussing specifically on communication with parents during the period of early years to primary transition. It also discusses the Scottish context, the research questions and associated aims that underpin the study. Chapter Two explains the background to the research from a Scottish perspective, including the current professional landscape in terms of policies and guidance linked to transition, communication and parental engagement. Chapter Three reviews the informing literature related to early years transition, beginning with an explanation of the process used in identifying the literature that was subsequently reviewed. There are two overarching sections in this chapter, each exploring different themes – communication and parental engagement. The chapter concludes with a critical consideration of how the review of literature, has informed the research that was subsequently undertaken. Chapter Four discusses the methodology - researching through a case study design. The research methods are outlined, including the research design, data collection tools employed and how data analysis was undertaken. Chapter Five presents the research findings, and Chapter Six critically discusses and analyses these findings, in relation to the research questions and aims, identifying implications for both the ELC setting and primary school involved in the case study and for the wider EY and Primary sectors in Scotland. Chapter Seven provides a personal reflection on adopting a participatory research approach within the study. The final chapter, Chapter Eight, begins by outlining suggested recommendations for the ELC setting and primary school involved in the case study, both the EY and Primary sectors in Scotland, the local authority where the 'case' was situated and policy makers. The chapter concludes with reflections on the research questions, the uniqueness of this Professional Doctorate research, the

limitations of the research study, identification of future research opportunities and final reflections on the research study.

1.6. Chapter Summary

This chapter has outlined the relevance of this research from both a professional and personal context. It has highlighted why communication with parents has been selected as the primary focus and how this will be achieved through the research questions and associated aims.

Chapter Two: The Context

2.1. Introduction

This chapter will explore the policy context from a Scottish perspective, before summarising how these policies and guidance link to transition, communication, parental engagement and how these inform my research. The chapter will then explain the Scottish research context and conclude with a description of the educational context for this case study research.

2.2. Policy Context

Scottish educational policy frames this study and inevitably informs its intentions and purposes. This begins with the legal requirement that all local authorities in Scotland implement the *Scottish Schools (Parental Involvement) Act 2006*. The act requires local authorities to develop and seek to further improve parental involvement in schools through learning at home, home-school partnerships and parental representation (Scottish Executive, 2006). Since the introduction of this act, both policy and guidance have been published by the Scottish Government and Education Scotland. The overarching intention of these publications are to support local authorities and schools in implementing legislative requirements. *Appendix 1 - Summary of Publications Relevant to Research Study*, summarises chronologically, key documents published by both the Scottish Government and Education Scotland that are relevant to the study. It also outlines specifically how the information contained within these eight publications may support or enhance communication with parents/carers or parental engagement and identifies how these documents are relevant to my study.

As outlined in Appendix 1, interestingly there was only one policy publication directly relevant to this study '*Achieving Excellence and Equity – 2024 National Improvement Framework (NIF) and Improvement Plan*' (Scottish Government, 2023). This document since being introduced in 2016, and updated yearly, identifies six drivers

aimed at improving the achievements of children and young people in education. One driver relevant to my research study was 'parent/carer engagement and family learning' – known until the 2024 version of the NIF as 'parent/carer involvement and engagement'. This driver emphasises a requirement on education settings to actively engage with parents/carers and the wider family to help raise children's attainment.

The seven guidance publications within Appendix 1 were developed to support individual education settings with communication and parental engagement. These publications included the '*National Improvement Framework: Parent Communication Plan A parent communication plan for the National Improvement Framework*' (Scottish Government, 2016). This document outlines six principles that educational settings should consider as good practice when communicating with parents – simplicity and clarity; transparency; relevance; partnership; flexibility and adaptation; timeliness. These principles are intended to inform settings about the best ways to communicate with their parents/carers. This includes for example the need for staff to understand that adopting a single approach when communicating with all parents/carers may not meet all parents/carers needs, with the requirement for a more flexible approach. The document additionally addresses the timeliness of communication with parents/carers about events involving them to facilitate changes to work commitments and childcare arrangements. Although communication with parents has been discussed within almost all the guidance documents within Appendix 1, interestingly the use of digital technology appears to have come to the fore as a modern method of communication (Education Scotland, 2019b), compared with other types of communication including leaflets and conversations (Scottish Government, 2016).

Another guidance publication '*Strategic Framework for: Parental Involvement, Parental Engagement, Family Learning and Learning at Home*' (Education Scotland, 2022) outlines how these four areas of the framework should be addressed by education professionals in Scotland. Included within the framework is a section on transition. This section outlines the role that parents play in supporting their child during key periods of transition, noting that professionals should 'work with parents to promote positive transition processes and embed effective parental involvement and

engagement structures' (Education Scotland, 2022, p. 25). Moreover, the framework makes reference to the 'Parental Involvement/Engagement Census' undertaken by Education Scotland in 2019, which identified a number of barriers to engaging parents. These included work commitments and [parents] not being aware of engagement opportunities. However, the onus is *now* on *education settings* to understand and address these barriers to parents becoming involved and engaged in their child's education.

It is interesting to note that within the guidance documents in Appendix 1 the terminology of working with parents appears to have changed, as Education Scotland (2019b) states that parents should now be *empowered* to become involved in the life and work of the setting and be actively involved in their child's educational journey. This arose as His Majesty's Inspectorate of Education (HMIe) during inspections identified inconsistency in the willingness of educational settings to use parents' views to influence school improvements. It is therefore imperative that educational settings are ensuring that parents have a voice in school/ELC decisions, with the feedback from parents impacting on school development.

Within Appendix 1, only one policy document was statutory with all the others guidance. This suggests that many of the ideas put forward by the Scottish Government are intended as guidance. Additionally, all the guidance documents discussed within Appendix 1 do not contain any specific examples or their effectiveness when developing specific approaches to communication around transition and parental engagement opportunities. Consequently schools/ELC settings have the flexibility to develop their own context specific school/ELC policies and protocols, based on the guidance provided by the Scottish Government or Education Scotland. Although this flexibility creates a challenge as each setting 'reinvents the wheel', potentially dedicating finite time developing their own processes for transition. This, in turn, puts pressure on ELC settings, who may have children transitioning to different primary schools, to keep abreast of the different ways the primary schools are communicating information about their transition programme to parents/carers. However, if examples had been included, these could have been used

by individual settings to spark professional dialogue and support the development of bespoke policies and guidance for staff and partners, around transition and parental engagement opportunities and the communication methods used to support their implementation. It was also important to note that all documents within Appendix 1 are applicable to all staff working in educational settings in Scotland, not just Senior Leadership Teams, therefore all staff should be aware of them. Therefore, the findings from my research study may support settings in Scotland by providing a spark for professional dialogue around transition and parental engagement and the different communication methods that could support this within their own unique context. It was envisaged that the research findings within Chapter Five and recommendations within Chapter Eight, would not only enhance parental engagement during the transition of their child from Rainbow ELC to Blue Primary School but also the wider EY and Primary sectors throughout Scotland.

2.3. Educational Context

This research was undertaken through an exploratory case study. It was therefore imperative that the particular educational context – the choice of settings, that I selected for the study was explained as providing background information on the research context.

2.3.1. Location

For this research, the research methodology was a case study, the ‘case’ being a Scottish Early Learning and Childcare (ELC) setting and the primary school where the majority of the children from this ELC would go to school. Although the settings are separate, they are adjacent to each other, separated only by a public footpath. Both educational settings are located in a town of more than 13,000 people within a large local authority council area in Scotland. The town is semi-rural and has been given the pseudonym Westland.

2.3.2. ELC

The ELC setting, given the pseudonym Rainbow ELC, is the only stand-alone local authority ELC within Westland. It has provision for both mainstream children and children with additional needs. There are two other local authority ELC settings in Westland, but both are nursery classes attached to primary schools, alongside three private ELC nurseries. Rainbow ELC, which is the focus of this research, offers 52-week access from 8am-6pm, only closing for bank or local holidays, giving parents of children attending childcare flexibility, to use their annual Scottish Government funded 1140 hours ELC allowance for children aged three until starting Primary One (Scottish Government, 2017). The most common attendance patterns during the research were either five mornings or afternoons or two and a half days. Out with these core hours, there were options for parents to purchase additional hours or claim further free hours if they are receiving certain Government benefits.

Within Rainbow ELC, it was the 3-5 mainstream playroom cohort of children due to move to the main feeder primary school (case study primary school) in August 2023, alongside their parents and key staff from the nursery that were the focus of the case study. At the time of the research, Rainbow ELC accommodated up to ninety-six children aged three to five years at any one time. The number of pre-school children within this cohort was sixty-nine, with forty-four moving onto the main feeder primary school. Twelve Early Year Practitioners (EYP) worked within the 3-5 mainstream playroom, including one EYP, who was the Transition Coordinator. She had previously worked as an EYP in the nursery class of the primary school involved in the study, and had a well-established relationship with its Senior Leadership Team. These forty-four children, their parents and key staff supporting transition represented the 'case' in this research. The remaining twenty-five pre-school children were going to different primary schools or being a deferred child and having an additional funded year at the ELC, and therefore did not form part of the 'case' for this research. Consideration had been given to involving all the parents of children starting primary school in August 2023. However, the number of children starting these other primary schools was small (no more than three per school), making it difficult for suggestions given by small groups of parents to amend the current communication tools used during transition

programmes with the other primary schools, as larger numbers of children were going to these primary schools from other nurseries in Westland.

Rainbow ELC leadership team consisted of a Head of Centre, two Deputies – one overseeing the mainstream provision and the other the ASN provision, two full time equivalent Team Leaders and one Parent and Child Support Worker. Due to local authority re-organisation within the EY sector, no ELC within the local authority had a permanent nursery teacher. However, they could request support from one of the thirteen Peripatetic Nursery Teachers, of which I was one. Throughout the data collection phase of the research, discussed in detail within sections 4.3.1 – 4.3.4. I was working two days a week within Rainbow ELC. My role during this period of time was a Peripatetic Nursery Teacher working alongside staff and children within the 3-5 mainstream playroom.

2.3.3. Primary School

The primary school involved in this case study, referred using the pseudonym as Blue Primary School, is adjacent to Rainbow ELC and was Westland's largest primary school with approximately four hundred pupils. The primary school had a nursery class until June 2021 when it was permanently closed, as it required the nursery class playroom for a classroom, due to the increasing role and the stand-alone Rainbow ELC was, by then, fully operational. Blue Primary School leadership team consisted of a Head Teacher and two Deputy Head Teachers (DHT), with one having the remit for early years and infants (up to Primary 3), one Principal Teacher and fifteen Class Teachers. Within Blue Primary School it was key staff involved in the transition programme that were the focus of the case study.

2.3.4. Transition

The local authority where the two settings within this case study are based, requires parents of children who will be five years of age by the end of February after starting school the previous August, to register their child for primary school, unless they have

opted for an additional funded year at ELC. Parents are required to enrol their child online during a specified week in January. Where the parents and child permanently reside dictates the primary school that the child will automatically go to – this is known as the catchment primary school. Contact by the catchment primary school to the parents, is made after the enrolment week has ended. Although parents can indicate while enrolling their child for primary school, that they wish to apply to an alternative primary school – known as a placing request. The outcome of a placing request is normally known by the end of April. If a placing request application is submitted, then protocol dictates that the parent and child cannot have contact or communication with either the catchment or placing request primary school until the outcome of the placing request is known.

With Rainbow ELC opening in November 2020, the academic year 2021-2022 was the first full academic year, that a transition programme was implemented between Blue Primary School and Rainbow ELC. During that year, more than thirty pre-school children were involved in different transition opportunities from January to June 2022. Although due to ongoing Covid-19 mitigations (Scottish Government, 2020) contact with Blue Primary School for the children was outside, and, for parents, all transition opportunities were either outside or via email. For the academic year 2022-2023, the six-month transition programme for children starting Blue Primary School in August 2023 commenced in January 2023. The programme included opportunities for the first time since Covid-19, for both children and their parents to engage fully in face-to-face transition opportunities. For parents, this opportunity involved meeting staff from Blue Primary School, during the transition talk given by the Head Teacher (HT). The transition programme between Blue Primary School and Rainbow ELC was developed collegially by the ELC Transition Coordinator and the DHT, who leads the transition to Primary One and was a continuation of the programme implemented in 2021-2022. The forthcoming six-month transition programme timetable was sent out digitally to the parents for children taking part in the transition to Blue Primary School, via the newly developed Nursery App in November 2022.

2.4. Chapter Summary

This chapter has summarised Scottish policy and guidance related to transition, communication and parental engagement. It has allowed me to understand the policy landscape, in order to make sense of where my research might contribute to a greater understand, in relation to policy and guidance implementation within the EY and Primary sector in Scotland. The chapter also discussed in detail the educational context including the two settings that were used for this case study research.

Chapter Three: Review of Literature

3.1. Introduction

This chapter initially conceptualises transition and outlines the importance of a positive transition for children transitioning from ELC to primary school. It then conceptualises both parental involvement and parental engagement and discusses the differences between them. Thereafter, an explanation is provided outlining the systematic process used to search and select research literature, including databases and key search terms selected for a review of literature. From there, the informing literature is divided into sections in light of the literature search, focussing on two key themes. The first key theme communication incorporates home/school communication and digital communication with parents/carers. The second key theme parental involvement and engagement, incorporates school policy development for parental engagement, parental involvement and engagement during transition to primary school and barriers to parental involvement and engagement. The chapter concludes with a discussion of the relevance of the reviewed literature to my research study, and how some identified 'knowledge gaps' were to be addressed within my research.

3.2. Conceptualising Transition

As part of this research study, it is important to consider different conceptions of transition, including definitions of both vertical and horizontal transitions. Interestingly, Vogler, Crivello and Woodhead's (2008) review of transition research in early years identified that there was no single definition for the term 'transition'. However, these three researchers proposed a generic definition - 'transitions are key events/or processes occurring at specific periods or turning points during the life course' (Vogler, Crivello and Woodhead, 2008, p. 2). These key events/processes possibly might include change of role, relationship and practices if linked directly with a change of education setting. Rogoff (2003) adds that at times of transition 'individuals change their role in their community's structure' (p. 150), which for children starting primary school would involve them changing from a nursery child to that of a school child.

Coupled with the parental role also changing from that of a nursery parent to the parent of a school child (Dockett and Perry, 2022).

However, transition might further be conceptualised as vertical or horizontal, with vertical transition involving:

Key changes from one state or status to another often associated with 'upward' shifts (e.g., from kindergarten to primary school; from primary to secondary school, etc.)

(Vogler, Crivello and Woodhead, 2008, p. 2)

With this definition fitting in with the transition that children go through when they transition from ELC to primary school, as children are moving from a familiar ELC setting to a new learning environment – primary school (Kagan and Neuman, 1998). Moreover, Dockett and Perry (2022) added that this type of transition usually only happens when children move onto the next phase of their education. From a Scottish perspective children in Scotland go through several vertical transitions as they go through the Scottish education system with the first being the movement from ELC to primary school. Thereafter a child will usually move to secondary school after seven years at primary school and finally leave secondary school at the age of sixteen (Dunlop, 2024). Supporting Vogler, Crivello and Woodhead's (2008) definition is included in '*Realising the Ambition: Being Me*' (Education Scotland, 2020), which states that vertical transition is a 'major change for children and their families, such as starting ELC or primary school' (Education Scotland, 2020, p. 90).

Conversely, horizontal transitions 'occur on an everyday basis' (Vogler, Crivello and Woodhead, 2008, p. 2). Examples of this type of transition occur during the day and include routines undertaken by children from different types of caregivers or education settings to another. They might include the daily trip from home to nursery and back home (Kagan and Neuman, 1998). This type of transition is explained by Clark (2000)

as a form of 'border crossings', whereby a child's identity can change when moving between different domains. This may include changes in role, behaviour and the type of activities children are involved in. Moreover, Scottish guidance within '*Realising the Ambition: Being Me*' (Education Scotland, 2020) endorses this view stating that horizontal transitions are 'multiple changes that occur throughout the day, such as from home to setting and moving from periods of play to mealtimes etc.' (Education Scotland, 2020, p. 90).

Vogler, Crivello and Woodhead, (2008) note that until the late 1990's transition within educational institutions conceptualised transition as 'one point' events (p. 2) including for example, the first day of primary school. More recently transition research including that undertaken by Petriwskyj, Thorpe and Tayler (2005) focussed on three western regions – USA, Europe and Australia/New Zealand from 1990-2004, suggests that starting school is more of a process that incorporates experiences for children and stakeholder partnerships sustained over time.

As part of conceptualising transition, this period of time links to Bronfenbrenner's (1994) Ecological Theory where the child is at the centre surrounded by the microsystem, mesosystem, exosystem and macrosystem. The first system, the microsystem contains people around the child including parents/carers and teachers/keyworkers. In terms of transition, parents/carers could directly affect their child's ability to cope with transition to school, as parental feelings and anxieties about the period of vertical transition from the early years setting to the school could transfer to the child. The second system, the mesosystem involves the school's interactions with the child and parents/carers to promote a supportive learning environment. Linking to transition, the interactions with and involvement of parents/carers with the primary school, including their interactions with key staff and attending school events, may facilitate a smoother vertical transition. The third system, the exosystem includes policy and practices developed both at local and school/ELC level. In terms of transition from the early years setting to school, the decisions made at this level would directly affect the transition programme available to the child and parents/carers opportunities offered within that programme. Finally, the fourth system, the

macrosystem includes the ways in which children's school-related transition experiences are positioned and valued by the culture that surrounds each parent will influence the way they choose to engage with their child's transition experiences in school.

Conceptualising transition from a Scottish perspective acknowledges horizontal transitions as ones that can occur multiple times a day. Examples include transitioning between different activities or between home and nursery and back home. While vertical transition as discussed previously in this section is one way, with (in the case of this research) children moving from the early years setting in to primary school. For children and families, this type of transition involves a change, which for some can be challenging, as it involves children adjusting both socially and culturally to new rules and routines (Burns, 2018). This period of transition is viewed as a critical time, not only for the children, but for parents/carers and staff involved because:

If parents expect transitions to be positive and they feel confident and enthusiastic about what lies ahead, then children are much more likely to feel relaxed and happy too.

(Scottish Transitions as a Tool for Change Project Group, (STTCPPG, 2019, p. 5).

It is also generally recognised that if transition has not been a positive experience for children, then this may impact on their ability to cope, both emotionally and academically, with school and any future transitions (Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD, 2017). Moreover, when parents are engaged in the transition process their children do better (OECD, 2020).

There should also be opportunities as part of the transition process for early childhood educators and primary educators to link and work together, which Dockett and Perry (2020) entitled 'professional linkage'. Additionally, opportunities should be provided for parents and teachers from the primary school to work collaboratively, thereby giving parents the opportunity to develop relationships and trust in the adults who will be

responsible for their child within the school environment (Dunlop, 2017). With the development of trust being particularly important during the period of transition for parents (Tobin *et al.*, 2022). It is recognised that this transition period can be a time of major change for parents too, as they adapt from being a nursery parent to a school parent and the different expectations that brings (Bérubé *et al.*, 2018).

As discussed previously within Appendix 1, support for transitions in Scotland can be located in guidance within 'Realising the Ambition: Being Me' (Education Scotland, 2020). This includes using the five 'C's (Burns, 2019) to underpin transition planning within EY: child-centred; communication; collaboration; consistency; and culture. The guidance also states that everyone should be involved in supporting the child during this period of time. Additionally, the six principles: 'aspirations; expectations; opportunities; entitlements; participation; contribution' (STTCPPG, 2019, p. 4) from the 'Transitions as Tools for Change' Project may also be used to support the development of transition policy and practice within individual settings in Scotland.

Crucially ELC to primary school transition in Scotland should not be viewed as a one-off event but a process that children and their families move through (STTCPPG, 2019). Moreover, this transition process should start prior to the child starting school and continue after the child has started school (Dockett and Perry, 2014). Interestingly some researchers including Huser, Dockett and Perry (2016) now liken the process of transition to a 'bridge' between the two settings. From a Scottish perspective this bridge is formalised within Curriculum for Excellence (CfE) (Learning and Teaching Scotland, 2009), a 3-18 curriculum, where the Early Level starts in the ELC and continues until the end of Primary One for most children.

To summarise this section, there are two distinct definitions of transition – horizontal transition and vertical transition. Moreover, the vertical transition from ELC to primary school is a period of time that children go through, but for this to be viewed positively and successfully long term, parents need to be equipped to support them. Partnership and collaborative working between ELC staff, primary school staff and parents can

enable this to happen. Finally, it is evident that parents may need help to adjust to their new role, requiring support from both ELC and Primary staff.

3.3. Conceptualising Parental Involvement and Parental Engagement

As part of this research study, it is important to conceptualise parental involvement and parental engagement and the distinction between them. From a Scottish education perspective, there are no universally recognised definitions of parental involvement (Education Scotland, 2019a). However, one definition currently used in Scottish education for parental involvement focusses on ‘the ways in which parents can get involved in the life and work of the ELC or school setting’ (Education Scotland, 2020, p. 59). Examples of this includes parents contributing to ELC or school improvement plans or being involved in other important decisions and continuing to encourage two-way communication between home and ELC or school (Education Scotland, 2019a). Parental engagement on the other hand often focuses on ‘parents’ and families’ interaction with their child’s learning’ (Education Scotland, 2020, p. 59). With this learning taking place at home, in the education setting, or within the community (Education Scotland, 2020). Examples of this includes practitioners/teachers engaging in discussions with parents about how they can help their child’s learning and how they can provide a supportive learning environment at home (Education Scotland, 2019a). However, it is also important to look at the conceptualisation of parental involvement and parental engagement from an academic perspective. One definition for parental involvement comes from Goodall (2025) who suggests that it is regularly conceived of as ‘a school led and orchestrated process of bringing parents into the fold’ (Goodall, 2025, p. 1). In earlier work, Goodall and Montgomery (2014) propose contrasting definitions of parent engagement and parent involvement as follows:

Parent engagement relates to parents’ engagement directly with the learning of their children, while parent involvement describes the relationship between parents and school staff, related to that learning (Goodall and Montgomery).

(Goodall, 2025, p. 4)

The authors add that parental engagement should be developed *with* parents through the voice and presence of parents. More importantly for effective engagement with parents it is suggested that 'a non-judgemental, supportive relationship must exist between parents and school' (Goodall and Montgomery, 2014, p. 402). Parental engagement is also long term, and recent research has highlighted that building productive relationships with parents takes time (Goodall, 2022). According to Borgonovi and Montt (2012) parental engagement is mostly likely to succeed with parents whose social and cultural capital aligns with the school. In such a context, parents may not see value in engaging with the school, about the child's learning or may feel unable to engage - perhaps for example due to low literacy levels or anxiety about engaging with teaching professionals. It is also important to note that Goodall and Montgomery (2014) added that while barriers are present for some parents' involvement with schools, for example timing of events, this may not actually affect parental engagement with children's learning as this can take place anywhere, not necessary at school.

A model of progression from parental involvement to parental engagement was developed by Goodall and Montgomery (2014) - a parental involvement to parental engagement continuum, whereby the parental involvement focussed on parents' involvement with schools to parental engagement where parents are involved in children's learning. The three points on the continuum were: parental involvement with the school; parental involvement with schooling; and parental engagement with children's learning. The first point characteristics include schools being in control of the relationship and flow of information given to parents, with the power controlled by the school. Additionally, although activities involve parents they are controlled by the school and mainly took place at school. The second point is characterised as an 'interchange of information between parents and school staff' (Goodall and Montgomery, 2014, p. 404), taking place in school or at home. This point also involved an interchange of knowledge between the parents and schools which helps the development of trust and beginning of relationships between home and school, alongside active involvement and shared support of a child's learning. However, schools still direct through guiding discussions and interactions with the parents although two-way communication is promoted. Power at this stage is more even

between home and school. The relationship also shifts as parents are partners and contributing to their child's academic future. The third point on the continuum is characterised as giving greater parental control, as both the actions and engagement of the parents to the information provided by the school about their child's learning remains with them (Goodall and Montgomery, 2014, p. 405). Consequently, engagement by the parent in their child's learning is ultimately decided by the parent to help to raise their child's achievement. Power at this stage is now mainly held by the parent.

To summarise, there are definitive differences between parental involvement and engagement. Parental involvement entails the involvement of parents in their child's education but is controlled/coordinated by the educational setting. Involvement is also not frequently related directly to the child's learning – it may involve attendance at a parent council meeting, for example. Parental engagement on the other hand, involves parents being engaged in their child's learning and having a voice in making decisions about their child's education. Engaged parents will assume their right to decide whether to take part or forgo the opportunities provided by the education setting. With parental engagement, two-way communication about the child's education between home and school is also assumed. This often includes educational settings using information provided by the parents about their child, alongside the promotion of a more equitable power relations between the parent and the school.

Finally, it is important as part of both parental involvement and parental engagement to consider challenges of involving and engaging parents. One challenge according to Jeynes (2018) may come from teacher resistance. Some teachers view themselves as professionals, not requiring input from parents in order to educate their child. Moreover, many people in society have increasingly perceived teachers as the education specialists, resulting in parents slowly withdrawing their parent responsibilities when it comes to their child's schooling (Jeynes, 2018). Therefore, in order to combat these views, it is imperative that teachers encourage parent participation, whilst parents also need to have a desire to take on their parent responsibilities and be involved in their child's schooling. Additionally, parents' own

perceptions and experience of education and school (Goodall and Montgomery, 2014), may also affect how they become involved and engaged with the education setting and their own child's educational journey. As previously stated above, educational settings may offer parental engagement opportunities but it is up to the parents to decide whether to uptake these opportunities (Goodall and Montgomery, 2014). Moreover, specific research related to barriers to parental involvement and engagement are discussed within section 3.6.3.

3.4. A Systematic Consideration of Informing Literature

A systematic review of literature on a specific subject, allows analysis of the findings from these studies to be synthesised and key themes to be identified. Petticrew and Roberts (2006) explains this type of review as:

1. Identifying the review focus, searching for and mapping the available evidence
2. Specifying the review questions
3. Identifying studies to include in the review
4. Extracting data and study quality appraisal
5. Synthesising findings and analysis across studies
6. Reporting the results of the review

(Petticrew and Roberts, 2006, p. 9 -10)

This study's review of informing literature followed Petticrew and Roberts (2006) six stages. Stage one, explained in sections 1.2 and 1.3., identified a specific focus, with stage two – section 1.4 specifying the research questions. Stage three focussed on identifying studies to be included/excluded from the review with literature published from 2018-2025 considered, as this reflected the timescale of my Professional Doctorate research. The review of research was undertaken using the University of the West of Scotland (UWS) online library search to access the following databases: Education Source, SpringerLink, Taylor and Francis, Scopus, Web of Science and UWS Research portal. ProQuest was also searched separately. All research articles sourced were peer-reviewed, in the English language and were in British, European, American or Australasian journals, as their education systems are similar to the

Scottish education system. With articles also initially selected for review by title and abstract summary. In searching for articles within the databases, key words/phrases were used including: 'digital communication with parents'; 'school communication with parents'; 'parent engagement during transition'; 'home/school communication'; and 'transition to school', with these terms and variations of these terms addressing aims one and two (section 1.4.1.) of my study. Aim three of my research was addressed through key phrases for the literature search including 'barriers to parental engagement'. Research from key researchers within the field of EY transition, that I was already familiar with alongside recommendations from my supervisors were also included. To aid research transparency, *Appendix 2 - Process for Searching and Selection of Literature Articles*, summarises the systematic review of the literature and includes a rationale for including/excluding sourced literature, as recommended by Petticrew and Roberts' (2006) stage three. Thereby explaining why research articles, which met the basic search term criteria via title and abstract summary, were ultimately included or excluded in the review of informing literature.

After completing the selection of relevant articles, following stage four of Petticrew and Roberts (2006) systematic review of literature involved extracting from these studies data, findings and implications/recommendations that were pertinent to my research study. Using the identified literature for review, two overarching key themes were identified – communication and parental involvement and engagement. The first key theme, communication is discussed within sub-sections home/school communication and digital communication with parents/carers. The second key theme parental involvement and engagement, is split into sub-sections school policy development for parental engagement and parental involvement and engagement during transition to primary school. Stage five is discussed within the section summary of each key theme, where the relevance of the research studies to my own research study are explained. Finally stage six is addressed within the overall chapter conclusion, whereby a summary of the relevance of the review of literature articles and how some of the gap of knowledge will be addressed by my study.

3.5. Communication

As my research focused on communication tools used to support parental engagement during the period of transition, it was necessary to find out what research within this area had already undertaken. This section discusses general home/school communication with parents/carers, where literature selected focussed on how educational settings communicated with parents and how successful they were. Thereafter it discusses research that focussed on digital communication with parents/carers as this was an area of particular interest within my research.

3.5.1. Home/School Communication

Home/school communication is a vital component of school life, not just during transition. One such research was school communication and the perspectives of parents by Bates, Finlay and O'Connor Bones (2021) during the first Covid-19 lockdown in March 2020 in Northern Ireland. An online, mainly quantitative survey was sent to parents of primary school children in Northern Ireland, with 2509 responses received. The survey concentrated on communication, school guidance and resources shared between school and home during the first Covid-19 lockdown. It also focussed on parents' experiences and any challenges faced during this period of time, in order to support planning for any unplanned school closures in the future. The research highlighted that parents' felt that communication was mainly one-way, namely from primary school to home and the frequency of any communication by schools varied. The researchers suggested that to prepare for any future unplanned school closures there needs to be: two-way communication; give consideration to a digital divide (access to suitable devices, internet access, parents' ICT skills); and understand that a one size fits all approach does not apply when schools are communicating with parents.

Different Irish research was undertaken by Oke, Butler and O'Neill (2021) into the perspectives of practitioners and parents and their contribution to quality early education and care (ECEC), through the use of technology in home to school communication and family involvement practices in ECEC. The researchers adopted a qualitative methodology and data were collected through semi-structured individual

interviews with practitioners (n=18) and different families (n=15). Findings revealed that some families felt they had to initiate contact with the ECEC, when this should have been the ECEC's responsibility. For family involvement this included finding out what families wanted or why they did not participate, as a way of understanding how the ECEC could better support families. When specifically discussing communication, the families felt that it was better to have one-to-one discussions about their child rather than short discussions during drop off. Some families also noted that the only interaction between home and school was when there was a problem. Recommendations suggested by the researchers' included: more two-way communication between home and ECEC to support parents who are unable to drop off/collect their child or attend events; and the need for two-way communication to consider the views and thoughts of parents.

To gain a deeper insight into the communication practices used specifically by teachers, Leenders *et al.*, (2019) undertook qualitative research into two-way home/school communication and the subjects that teachers spoke to parents of children with special needs about at parent-teacher conferences and other opportunities. Three types of schools in southern Netherlands participated, involving 55 teachers – at-risk schools serving low-socio-economic children (n=21), mainstream primary schools (n=20) and special education schools (n=14). Through data collected from individual semi-structured interviews with the teachers, the researchers' established that creating trusting relationships was important. This included acknowledging the importance of developing informal contact with parents, with the teacher actively seeking that contact. Interestingly, teachers working in the special education schools, were aware of limited time out with formal meetings to chat with parents, so used email, phone and written notes to communicate with parents about their child. Conversely, staff in the 'at-risk' schools tended to welcome parents informally into the classroom, arranging low-threshold activities to support a connection with parents. The researchers also noted that two-way communication between the teacher and the parents across all schools during the first parent-teacher meeting involved parents giving information about how their child was doing, and teachers taking this information into account. This was acknowledged as an example of supporting the development of a trusting relationship. The researchers stated that

the building of trust needed to be developed between the parent and teacher, before parents were able to engage in purposeful dialogue with the teacher about their child.

3.5.2. Digital Communication with Parents/Carers

As my research study included exploring digital communication particularly from the parents' perspective and the impact this has had on parental engagement, it was necessary to review what research within this area had already found and recommended, and how these studies might inform my research. One such American study, a descriptive case-study by Berklan and Hughes (2020), adopted a mixed method approach involving a survey and individual interviews. The research focussed on: parents' perspectives on communication between home and school; the parents' preferred ways to communicate with the school and whether these methods were considered by the school; and policy and practice supporting working relationships with parents. A 'Parent Communication Survey' using predetermined questions, was distributed to both Hispanic and Caucasian parents (n= 480 response rate 46%) who were residents of a school district in Arizona. This was followed up by individual qualitative interviews with nine parents. The researchers discovered that over 10% of the parents surveyed generally had problems using electronic communication, with an additional 1.4% having no direct internet access. When questioned about the types of electronic communication they would like used by teachers, the responses were: 'email (73.3%); text (39.4%); social media (7.2%); electronic portal (40.9%); and none (5.5%)' (Berklan and Hughes, 2020, p. 9) highlighting that the majority of parents preferred email, while a small number preferred no electronic communication. The findings also highlighted that while two-way communication between school and home was evident, the teachers were more active in maintaining this two-way communication. The findings from the nine parent interviews suggested that parents regularly used their smartphone as a sort of portable computer to navigate the school online portal, although these parents stated that the size of the smartphone screen made it difficult to use the school online portal. Furthermore, three non-English speaking parents added that language was a barrier. Interestingly the researchers' findings acknowledged that parental communication preferences had not previously been considered by the schools. Moreover, the parents were not aware of any

consistent approach or policy to ensure effective communication and collaboration with them. The researchers concluded that, with the parents' lives becoming more mobile, schools needed to review parents access to the school website, electronic portal and other web information. Schools also needed to consider whether information being read on a smartphone, was in fact readable. Recommendations included that schools considering the effectiveness of their home-school communication should ask parents and other partners how good the home-school communication is and provided suggestions for improvement should be considered. In terms of policy development, the researchers acknowledged that while the schools involved may not want to develop their own local policy for home-school communication this should be encouraged and should include dialogue with parents.

In contrast Epstein *et al.*, (2019) discussed the importance of using different ways to communicate with parents, including always providing written communication as an option. Epstein *et al.*, (2019) acknowledged that consideration should also be given to both traditional and emerging social media for home to school communication and vice versa. Thereby, they partially argue against the fully digital approach to communication that appears to be a recommendation of Berklan and Hughes' (2020) research. Interestingly the point made by Berklan and Hughes' (2020) about parental access to smartphones resonates with research by Winter *et al.*, (2025) study in the United Kingdom (UK) about the rights of very young child (0-36 months) and their access to digital technology in the home. As part of this research the survey of parents (n=1444) from across the four nations of the UK identified that 98.3% of parents had access to a smartphone at home.

Addressing a gap in knowledge about teachers and parents view of digital communication and parent-teacher partnership, a mixed method methodology was undertaken by Kuusimäki, Uusitalo-Malmivaara and Tirri (2019). A mainly quantitative digital communication scale questionnaire was emailed to two different areas of Finland – one rural with teachers (n=24 response 45%) and parents (n=120 response 14%) and one urban municipality with teachers (n=94 response 16%) and parents (n=1003 response 9%). Although using a questionnaire to collect data were

appropriate, the researchers acknowledged that the low response rate of parents and teachers from all school stages was a limitation. Notwithstanding this, the findings are interesting and revealed: rural schools had more parent-teacher partnerships than urban schools; effective two-way communication supported partnership between home and school; digital communication also supported co-operation between home and school. Additionally, some parents (n=400) and teachers (n=80) completed the survey's qualitative questions about the content that parents and teachers wanted communicated digitally. Subsequent content analysis highlighted that these parents wanted: more information about the schools and class events; sharing of information about what they could do to support their child at home; and sharing of information about pedagogy being used. The researchers concluded that digital communication was good for school related matters and supported the school and home partnership, especially if it was two-way. Reiterating a recommendation of Bates, Finlay and O'Connor Bones (2021) that communication between home and school should be two-way.

Digital technologies and parental involvement from a United Kingdom perspective, was studied by Head (2020). Her English qualitative research study involved fifteen mothers, all recruited via Facebook, who had children aged 4-6 years of age in reception or year one and attended different primary schools. The findings from individual interviews revealed that a variety of communication tools were used by the various primary schools. These included emails, texts, apps and social media – Facebook and Twitter, although the main communication tool used by the different schools was email. Interestingly, there was no consensus from participants as to the preferred communication tool schools should use, as the mothers' managed the information being sent out by the schools differently. Examples provided included memorising the dates, putting the information onto the fridge or transferring the information to a diary/electronic calendar. Additionally, many of the mothers felt that too much communication from the primary school could be overwhelming, as some of the primary schools used multiple communication tools to share the same information. A few of the mothers also spoke about being responsible for passing on information to their partner who may not be receiving the information directly from the schools. Some of the parents involved in Head's study had also developed an informal online network,

including a Facebook page set up for their child's class, as a way of mediating the volume of communication being sent out by the school. The Facebook page and other informal digital platforms set up by parents helped keep other parents up to date with what was happening, including working parents who were not dropping off/collecting their child. The findings from Head's study suggest that participants felt the primary schools did not appropriately communicate how to use the digital software that they were sharing information through. The findings also questioned whether these communication tools suited the needs of the individual families involved, including the lack of both parents being directly communicated by the school, reiterating the findings of Berkman and Hughes' (2020) that parents were not consulted about the best ways for the school to communicate with them.

Linking also to Berkman and Hughes' (2020) conclusion that schools need to consider parental access to websites, Gilleece and Eivers (2018) investigated one hundred random Irish primary school websites. The quantitative study involved scrutinising basic website information: school contact details; practical information (open and closing times and school closures); and school activities including school initiatives. It also considered: types of parental involvement (parental involvement, communication with parents and parental involvement in their child's learning); school policies; and website readability and functionality (website links and download speed). The findings from the 90% of schools that had some web presence was enlightening. For basic information: 92% had school contact and enrolment details; 47% had an up-to-date teaching staff list but only 37% included an up-to-date list of support staff. Within practical information: 72% listed opening and closing hours; 68% noted school closure dates; and 77% highlighted school initiatives. Regarding parental involvement: 46% named board of management members and 38% named parent association members; 23% gave information about parental involvement in their child's literacy development and 20% numeracy development. Within communication with parents: 72% had a current academic year report from the principal or class teacher; 11% linked to Twitter; and 7% to Facebook. Specific school policies found on the school websites scrutinised included: 'anti-bullying (59%); behaviour (57%); child protection (51%); homework (34%); complaints (22%)' (Gilleece and Eivers, 2018, p. 421). Interestingly, functionality of the websites was very good with 97% having no technical problems

and 78% having all links from their website working. The researchers concluded that there was little information for prospective parents, limited use of the website to communicate directly with parents and the school community and limited information about formal parental involvement. However, the researchers acknowledged that as most parents enrolled their child at the nearest primary school extensive information for the primary school was not needed. A recommendation made by the researchers was that parents should be involved in the design of the website in order to ascertain information that is relevant to them.

Piller, Bruzon and Torsh (2021) added to research into school websites from an Australian perspective. The researchers focussed on whether parents who spoke English or did not speak English had equal opportunities to access high-quality enrolment information, thereby allowing them to support their child's education. Thirty linguistically diverse primary schools' websites within the state of New South Wales were assessed by the researchers, who scrutinised three web pages from each school: homepage; information about school; and enrolment information page. Results of this scrutiny were enlightening and included: English being the exclusive language used in each page; twenty-six schools had a hyperlink to Google translate but information about this was provided only in English; twenty-eight schools had a hyperlink to the state's Department of Education enrolment pages, although the links to the different languages on the government page were only provided in English; and only one school's website stated that help was available to parents who did not read English. The implications given by the researchers were interesting and included: monolingual websites curtail parent engagement; greater awareness and understanding of linguistic diversity needed at all levels from local government to school level. As a result, recommendations provided included: the school's home page should include welcome in languages that represented the home languages spoken by children and families; how to book an interpreter; information that links to Google translate hyperlink being given in home language as opposed to English; and the enrolment information provided by local government for each language being listed together on one page. The recommendations were particularly important to the participating schools, as a communication policy and strategy was the responsibility of schools as opposed to being provided by one at government level.

3.5.3. Section Summary

In summarising this section on communication with parents/carers, it is evident that consideration needs to be given to the communication tools and methods used to engage parents/carers. This includes communication tools being used to develop trust between parents/carers and teachers both formally and informally, including face-to-face opportunities. Consideration also needs to be given to communication barriers, including access by parents/carers to relevant technology to enable communication between school and home, alongside schools' awareness of any digital divide. Additionally, two-way communication between home and school is a vital component when communicating with parents/carers. Furthermore, school websites need to be suitable to engage and inform new and current parents/carers about the school. It is also important that schools ascertain the communication tools that parents/carers would like to be used, and to enquire whether ones currently used are suitable for all parents/carers and contain information that parents/carers are actually looking for. All the points discussed are relevant to the communication tools/methods used during parental engagement including the context of transition from ELC to primary school and therefore pertinent to my first research question.

Although this section made no reference directly to ELC settings, many of the research findings and recommendations made about communication methods/tools used by schools to communicate with parents/carers, including digitally, are pertinent to nursery settings too. Nursery staff need to communicate with parents/carers about their child's learning and actively involve them in the life of the setting and their child's education journey including during the transition period. Therefore, my research study through aim one, would be able to find out within the context of transition, the communication tools that parents/carers want to be used. Finally, I would also ascertain whether there were any identified digital communication barriers for parents/carers, thereby addressing aim three of the research study.

3.6. Parental Involvement and Engagement

As the overarching subject of parental involvement and engagement is so wide, this section of the review of literature has been divided into sub-sections that are relevant to my research. These are, school policy development for parental engagement, parental involvement and engagement during transition to primary school and barriers to parental involvement and engagement.

3.6.1. School Policy Development for Parental Engagement

Parental involvement and engagement from the Scottish Government perspective, discussed in section 1.3., is a legislative element of Scottish education. As part of my research, it was important to identify academic research that researches policy. One example was Smith's (2022) case study using a policy enactment framework developed by Ball, Maguire and Braun (2012). The focus of Smith's study was to understand parental engagement activities, with a view to informing the development of a national 'broad and general' engagement policy. The research 'case' involved an English speaking, medium sized state primary school in New Zealand where thirteen members of staff took part in individual semi-structured interviews and relevant artefacts from the primary school were also reviewed. These research methods supported Smith's understanding of what policy expects of school's engagement with parents and the community, and how school staff, teachers and parents understood their obligations in relation to the policy. Interestingly where Ball, Maguire and Braun's (2012) findings positioned parents as 'outsiders', Smith's case study identified parents as 'insiders' (the same as teachers and leaders), because parents were making sense of the parental engagement policy and how it involved them. Additionally, Smith (2022) cited that when developing policy Ball, Maguire and Braun (2012) had three stages – interpretation, translation and implementation. The interpretation stage involves an initial reading of the policy by the school leader or other designated member of staff and establishing a framework for school practice within the school's context (Smith, 2022). This process makes the policy individual to that school. The translation stage 'is the process of developing institutionally-based policy texts before putting them into practice' (Smith, 2022, p. 105). This may involve discussions, observations and meetings with members of staff who will eventually be putting the policy into practice

– the implementation stage. Ball, Maguire and Braun (2012) according to Smith (2022) also stated that there were eight different teacher roles involved in policy work - ‘narrators; entrepreneur; outsiders; transactors; enthusiasts; translators; critics; receivers’ (Smith, 2022, p. 110), which were all influenced by their teacher expertise, type of policy and the staff member’s role within the school. Taking these various roles into account, Smith (2022) suggested the requirement for a clear and coherent parental engagement policy, including the school deciding what it could achieve after taking into account other school and external demands. She stated that a broad definition of parental engagement gave a school the flexibility to relate their policy to their own context. Nevertheless, having a broad national policy can make it hard for schools to identify exactly what parental engagement is, how it is understood and how to encourage it. Smith (2022) recommended the adoption of a participatory approach to policy development at local level, so that policy is understood by all, including parents who are key participants. Although a study from New Zealand, this study has relevance to the Scottish context. The Scottish Government has explained their definition of parental engagement (Education Scotland, 2019a), however how it is understood/enacted by individual settings in Scotland has not been specified.

In addition, Hornby and Blackwell (2018) carried out a small-scale British study, which focussed on school policies and parental involvement (PI) in schools. It was a follow up to research carried out in 2011 which focussed on PI and an apparent gap between the rhetoric and reality. This updated study involved the participation of eleven schools ranging in size from under two hundred pupils to more than seven hundred pupils, with Blackwell undertaking individual semi-structured interviews with the Head Teacher or delegated member of staff. Interestingly, the findings revealed that almost all PI policies were embedded within other policies and not presented separately. Activities to encourage PI from the participating schools included: newsletters/information sheets/letters home; websites; parent/teacher meetings and open days/evenings. Furthermore, more than half the schools’ policy or practices had changed within a five-year period. For many, this change stemmed from: the significant influence of the Head Teacher on PI within their school; responding to the needs of the community or OFSTED parent survey; Governors’ influence; good practice from

books/journal/websites; and sharing of practice from different schools and talking to colleagues.

3.6.2. Parental Involvement and Engagement during Transition to Primary School

As the focus of my research was transition from ELC to primary school and the involvement of parents/carers, it was important to review current research within this area. An American study into parental involvement and engagement in the transition process was undertaken by Griebing and Gilbert (2020). Their research focussed on a four to six week 'Me and My School Kindergarten Transition Program', and how children and their families were supported to adapt to formal schooling, with all programme interventions both school and family specific. This included talks by school staff to parents and the development of 'Family Kindergarten Transition Kits', where rewards were used to actively encourage participation. The researchers involved children from low socio-economic and/or who had lower academic abilities (n=750) from twenty-one schools and used a variety of qualitative data collection methods, including child observations, field notes from key staff group discussions (n=33) and parent surveys (n=192 response rate 60%). Noteworthy findings included: once the transition programme finished, school staff reported that the children who took part were more familiar with the new school environment; pupils with special educational needs had been identified; and from day one teachers were ready to support. From the families' perspective, all those (including parents) who had taken part had an enhanced relationship with the teachers and other staff and their children experienced less anxiety starting school. The researchers concluded that parents, families and children who had taken part had benefitted from the support provided during the transition to formal schooling, particularly the opportunity to develop better relationships with the school staff. These points support those made by OECD (2017) that children who had a positive transition experience coped better emotionally and socially. This latter point by Griebing and Gilbert (2020) also resonated with Bérubé *et al.*'s (2018) Canadian quantitative study. Bérubé *et al.*, (2018) hypothesised that the number of transition practices children had taken part in positively affected their ability to cope with starting kindergarten. Through a quantitative questionnaire

completed by four hundred and twelve parents of kindergarten children from one hundred and seven schools, Bérubé *et al.*'s (2018) findings highlighted that those taking part in more frequent transition opportunities were found to be better prepared/able to settle into school. Interestingly the researchers identified that whilst supporting their child during this period of change parents also needed to prepare themselves for their changed role. Bérubé *et al.*, (2018) concluded that parents needed to be involved from the start of the transition process and that the first contact the new school made with parents was vital.

A further American study, a case study by Merideth *et al.*, (2022), investigated the perception of parents participating in a kindergarten program called 'Families First' (FF). Their study explored which aspects of the programme were helpful to both students and parents and aspects that could be changed to better meet participants' needs. The FF programme was open to all students who were due to start kindergarten, although priority was given to those who had not attended pre-school or Head Start, had additional needs, were bilingual, from certain ethnic backgrounds or came from low-income families. FF consisted of fifteen half day three-hour sessions for children and optional twice weekly one hour parent sessions. Examples of parent sessions included: presentations; discussion of transition related topics; question and answer sessions; and informal opportunities to get to know other parents. The programme's goals were to increase children's readiness for school, reduce kindergarten absenteeism and increase parental involvement in schools. Data were collected from semi-structured interviews with thirty-nine parents across five school sites during the final week of the programmes. Using qualitative analysis, findings related to parent perceptions of the programmes included: FF had a positive impact on parents; parents had opportunities to familiarise themselves with the school environment; parents developed a better understanding of the school routines and customs. Additionally, teacher-parent relationships developed during the programme, alongside an increased parent knowledge of support and resources available. Detailed analysis demonstrated that: 78% of parents valued the opportunity to make one-to-one connection with school staff, helping to alleviate their anxiety of supporting their child's transition; 90% felt it helped connect with other families; and 100% felt the programme had a positive impact on their child. Recommendations included stronger

daily communication and improved communication before and during the programme. The results from Merideth *et al.*, (2022) were similar to research undertaken more recently by Fan *et al.*, (2023) into Countdown to Kindergarten (CTK), a different summer kindergarten programme in America. Their mixed methods study looked at parents/caregivers' perspectives of kindergarten readiness focussing on the impact of being involved in the CTK programme. The CTK particularly supports children and families from disadvantaged backgrounds. The mixed methods study collected data initially from a survey of randomly selected parents (n=380), of which 194 (51.6%) children and families had participated in the CTK programme. Results from this survey highlighted that parents who took part in CTK were more positive about the transition to kindergarten. Data were thereafter collected via individual semi-structured interviews with ten parents who had taken part specifically in the CTK. Specific findings from these ten parents included: feeling their child was more prepared for kindergarten; kindergarten expectations were explained to the parents; opportunities during the visits to ask questions and build relationships with staff; parents/caregivers felt relaxed with the teacher and were able to see how the child interacted with their teacher; and parental involvement in their child's schooling was explained. Interestingly, children who attended the preschool programme were also more positive about transition to kindergarten than children of families who had not participated.

Linking directly with section 3.5.2. digital communication, Walsh, Romo and Jeon (2018) undertook American research into how videos supported parental engagement during the transition to kindergarten and any associated barriers to using the videos. In total four videos, with associated information sheets, were sent out weekly in English or Spanish. Videos were used because they reduced language and literacy barriers due to being visual with audio commentary. The content of the videos included: general information about preparing for kindergarten; hands-on learning activities; different perspectives about the transition to kindergarten; and registration information. Participants came from six classrooms, with one hundred and ten parents watching the videos and ninety-one completing the researchers' survey. Results from the ninety-one participants included: 51.6% felt the video lengths were appropriate (5-8 minutes); approximately 50% felt the videos audio was clear to hear and visual definition was sufficient too; 45.5% felt the content was helpful. Additionally, fifty-six

participants (English n=39; Spanish n=17) completed additional open-ended questions about the features of the videos that were most helpful. Interestingly the researchers stated that while most of the information in the videos was found in kindergarten information given by the local district, the use of videos may have given this information in a more accessible format. Taking on board feedback from the parents', the researchers recommended that in the future the videos should include children, use fewer subtitles and use a context that would be relevant to the parents watching them (a real classroom).

More recently, a comparative case study was undertaken by Woodhouse, Passey and Anderson (2024) into how digital technologies were used to develop and maintain home-school connections during transition to nursery school or school. Four schools in Northern Ireland (NI) with nursery provision and four primary schools in New Zealand (NZ) took part. Data were collected from individual semi-structured interviews with either the principal/lead for transition to school and analysis of key policies relevant to their research. Developing their own parental engagement framework from a combination of earlier studies in the field, the researchers proposed four levels: 'Level 1 Establish communication and build initial connections with parents; Level 2 Develop opportunities for parents to engage with the school community; Support parents' involvement in their children's home learning; Level 3 Maintain support to meet parents' evolving needs; Level 4 Review existing practices and explore new opportunities' (Woodhouse, Passey and Anderson, 2024, p. 5). The results of level 1 included a NZ principal highlighting the importance of parents being free to contact the principal to ask questions, while a second NZ school used their website to explain to parents how to use the applications (app) used by the school. In NI one school used an app to keep parents abreast of key days and events. Results from level 2 found that all schools in NZ used at least three ways to communicate with parents in order to fit in with the lifestyles of their parents. Also, both NZ and NI schools communicated with parents in a variety of ways including email, school app and website. Level 3 findings acknowledged digital technologies as particularly important during Covid-19 to maintain communication between home and school. Finally, level 4 revealed that schools checked the effectiveness of the digital technologies they used and whether any others would be more effective. Noteworthy was that some schools in the study

found that regardless of the communication method used, some parents did not read the emails or newsletters. The researchers concluded: digital technology positively supported parental engagement through regular communication; existing and emerging communication methods were important to build collaboration with parents; and to continue using a multimodal communication. This point differs to that of Head (2020), whose participants felt that using different communication tools to give the same message was overwhelming. Woodhouse, Passey and Anderson's (2024) research also recognised that schools need to be aware of parents' circumstances and aspirations that might influence their access to both technology and their willingness/availability to be involved in school life. Furthermore, the researchers noted that both parent and teacher voice were important to ensure that suitable communication methods were used, in contrast to Berkman and Hughes (2020) who focussed primarily on parent voice. Finally, from a policy perspective, Woodhouse, Passey and Anderson (2024) recommended that schools are provided with guidance about understanding parents' aspirations and circumstances and how providing digital technologies may invite parental participation and engagement.

Another recent research was an Irish quantitative study by Tobin *et al.*, (2023) who explored the impact of cultural and social capital through parents' beliefs and participation during the transition of their child from preschool to primary school in academic readiness activities. The study also investigated whether relationships with the school staff were affected if the parents already had an older child who had previously been through the transition to school. The research involved an online structured questionnaire with parents (n=477) where 90% of respondents were female. Results particularly relevant to my research included that relationships were significant for first time parents, particularly those from a working class or migrant background. A reason provided by the researchers was that transition helped these parents become familiar with school's culture. Interestingly there was little impact on the relationships with school staff if parents had already been through the transition process with another child. A reason given was that these parents were already aware of the parents' role and expectations from the school. Recommendations included providing family transition activities before a child starts school and strengthening links between preschool and primary school via the continuity and familiarity of school

expectations. The researchers also suggested that policies and practices at both government and school level should be inclusive, taking into account diverse families, so that these families could be positioned as equal partners. In order to reduce barriers, recommendations included providing childcare for parent evenings and considering parent's working hours when planning events.

Specifically, research related to a mother's involvement in transition to primary school was undertaken in Australia by Rogers (2018). She researched how mothers engaged with their child's learning, as their child made the transition to primary school, as well as the perspectives of educators about mother and child engagement. The study involved four complex and diverse communities with thirteen educators (class teachers, principals and allied staff) and twenty-one mothers from social and/or economically disadvantaged backgrounds. All participants were individually interviewed prior to their children starting school, with seven mothers interviewed again after their children had started primary school. Data were also collected from direct observations, documents and informal conversations. Using constructivist grounded theory, the findings revealed that mothers and educators had different perspectives. The mothers used different ways to engage in their child's learning that were dependent on the context, experiences, expectations and aspirations for their children. Conversely, the educators viewed the parents' knowledge and skills in supporting their child's learning as deficient, requiring specific instructions from the educators. The research concluded that the mothers were looking for regular dialogue about their child, allowing them to share information about their family circumstances with educators. However, the mothers did not want information sessions about school practices or programmes. Interestingly, the information sessions and workshops planned by some of the settings had been decided by the school and included information the school staff felt the parents needed to know about the school, for example expectations and routines. In reality, this was not what the mothers actually wanted.

Further research into the experiences of mothers during the transition of their children to primary school was undertaken in Ireland by Tobin *et al.*, (2022) through a case

study. The study focussed on the connections between family and school during the transition to primary school. Data in the form of individual semi-structured interviews were collected from five mothers of children who had started at three different primary school. Additional data were collected via Tobin's reflective journal. Following an interpretative phenomenological approach to analysis, different themes were identified, including the supportive nature of the transition activities offered. Transition activities discussed by the parents included parents finding it helpful to attend a meeting with teachers to clarify what to expect during the first year at primary school. However, one mother stated she would have liked a formal family visit to the primary school to help her better support her child at home, while other mothers discussed both formal transition and informal activities for their children. An example of an informal activity included one school opening their yard to families over the summer, thereby giving both children and families the opportunity to become familiar with the outdoor school environment. From interviewing the mothers, it became evident that transition opportunities across the three primary schools were inconsistent, although opportunities were available for the mothers and children to familiarise themselves with their new school and routine prior to their child starting school. The researchers also acknowledged the trust the mothers subsequently had in their child's new teacher, and the positive connection between family and school during the transition to primary school. The research concluded that the quality of the experiences offered were important, not just the number of contacts between the primary school and the families, and that there should be a consistent policy and practice across schools during the transition to school. Interestingly, the most important transition activity offered from the mothers' perspective was the opportunity to familiarise themselves with the new school environment during the period of transition.

3.6.3. Barriers to Parental Involvement and Engagement

As part of parental involvement and engagement, it was important to consider any specific barriers that may affect parental engagement, including any that were to be pertinent to my own research study. Lohmann, Hathcote and Hogan's (2018) literature review into the partnership between families and young children with disabilities identified a number of barriers, including a parent's work schedule. Their research

found that some school staff assumed non-attendance by parents at events/meetings indicated that parents were not interested in their child, when in fact work commitments had affected parents' ability to attend. Additionally, Hornby and Blackwell's (2018) research (section 3.6.1.) identified barriers to parental involvement (PI) that fell into four categories. The first was 'parent and family factors affecting PI', which included parents' own negative experiences of school or parents' own issues - parents being separated, having poor literacy levels, speaking English as an Additional Language or mainly almost all attendees at events being mothers. A second category 'practical barriers', included practical barriers to involvement - time constraints and school opening hours. The third category 'parent-teacher factors' affecting PI' included diverse family structures, including separated parents. The final category was 'societal factors' which included economic, historical and demographic factors. Hornby and Blackwell (2018) noted that PI was a vital part of facilitating effective education, adding that schools must collaborate with parents and partners, as schools are now a central part of the community. School leaders also needed to liaise with others, including other school leaders in order to share and learn what others have undertaken to promote PI. Importantly Hornby and Blackwell stated that PI required a whole school approach involving all stakeholders. Interestingly when comparing research they had undertaken ten years ago into PI, they acknowledged that although progress had been made regarding PI, barriers still remained.

Linking directly with Hornby and Blackwell's (2018) 'parent and family factors affecting PI' was research undertaken by Desmarchelier *et al.*, (2022) using two different theoretical lenses – feminist theory and communication theory. Their Australian study used an online survey to investigate the experience of separated parents in parental engagement, including any barriers. The research involved 140 participants who were separated parents, from diverse backgrounds, and had a child/ren of school age. The researchers' findings highlighted the barrier that separated parents felt when excluded from receiving information from their child's school. This included not knowing when school events and meeting open to them were to occur. Suggested solutions for schools included: considering parent living arrangements; having a school protocol and using online communication instead of hard copies, as often only one copy is

distributed. Interestingly, this latter point contrasts with Epstein *et al.*, (2019) view that communication should always be *made available* in written form.

Another possible barrier to parental engagement, was the involvement of fathers in parenting programmes. This barrier was researched through a review of international literature by Lechowicz *et al.*, (2019). The researchers' review focussed on father engagement in parent programs, identifying broad policy and practice recommendations for Australian practitioners. Recommendations identified from the review of literature for practitioners included: remembering as part of the parenting team to engage with fathers; realising that one-size does not fit all; programs offered do not meet the needs of all fathers; realising that fathers are experts and inviting fathers directly to parental engagement sessions. While recommendations identified at organisational and service level included: increasing father engagement practices; father inclusive policies; sessions held out of working hours and increased professional training about father engagement. Although these recommendations are pertinent to Australia, they were considered within the research design of my study, discussed in detail within section 4.3.1. This included a researcher led discussion with the SG, regarding appropriate times to engage with the wider ELC parent participants which included fathers.

3.6.4. Section Summary

To summarise this section, parental engagement/involvement policies are important and can be driven forward by different people or changing situations. Crucially these policies should involve key personnel, including parents from the outset. Furthermore, the participation of all parents needs to be considered when planning parental engagement opportunities and mitigating barriers to their involvement, if parents wish to participate. This may include considering the time of day when transition events take place and finding out from parents exactly what they want to know. Additionally, having the opportunity to get to know and meet the school staff and visit the new school environment were also important. Finally, consideration should be given to communicating digitally with the parents.

3.7. Chapter Summary

In summarising the overall review of literature, a number of key themes were identified related to communication with parents. The use of digital communication, appears to be the predominant method of communication between school/teacher and home. However, for some, the amount of information being sent by schools can be overwhelming. Using solely digital communication methods can be a barrier for some, and so consideration needs to be given to mitigate this in order that all parents can be successfully communicated with. Interestingly, the importance of two-way communication between school/teacher and home came through, but it was evident that this was not happening consistently. Finally, parents are often not consulted about the communication methods they prefer or information they are interested in being given by the schools/teachers.

With reference to parental involvement and engagement there were a number of key themes. These included the broad nature of policies related to parental engagement/involvement often being embedded within other policies and not involving parents when writing them. Another theme was parental involvement/engagement in transition to primary school, and the importance of parents being able to support their child through this change, as well as managing their own changing role, that comes with their child starting formal education. Therefore, finding out what parents actually want to know about their child starting school would assist this, alongside opportunities for parents to establish a relationship with key school staff may also help. Finally, consideration for barriers to parental engagement include addressing the needs of all parents, including parent work patterns.

Referring directly to my research the findings regarding two-way communication mainly from school to home, access to suitable devices to receive any digital communication and frequency of communication are all interesting aspects to be explored as part of my case study research. Furthermore, the principles of how to work with parents/carers including developing two-way conversation and a trusting relationship through face-to-face opportunities both formal and informal were also interesting aspects to be explored within my study. In addition, whether digital

communication would be a positive aspect of parental engagement during the transition from ELC to primary school. Additionally, whether employing multiple ways to communicate between home and school would be beneficial and if specific policy guidance is needed at a setting level. Lastly whether there were any barriers to the parents/carers engaging during the transition programme and how these could be overcome are also interesting aspects explored within my research study.

In conclusion, it is evident that academic research into communication methods that parents would prefer to be used has taken place internationally, but there appears to be a particular knowledge gap from a Scottish perspective. This is also true for transition opportunities for parental engagement and involvement. The research I have undertaken has addressed both these points through the context of transition from ELC to primary school. Moreover, none of the research discussed within this review of literature, actively involved the parents/carers in planning parental involvement or engagement opportunities. However, my research actively involved parents/carers during transition from ELC to primary school from a Scottish perspective and is discussed in detail within *Chapter Four: Methodology*.

Chapter Four: Methodology

4.1. Introduction

This chapter discusses the axiology, ontology, epistemology and methodology adopted within this research. Justification for employing a case study design, the positionality of the researcher, the adoption of a participatory research approach and navigating issues of power in participatory research are also explained. Thereafter the participants involved in the research, the qualitative research methods used to address the research questions, research tools, data collection and the process employed to analyse the data are explained. The chapter concludes by discussing trustworthiness in qualitative research and ethical considerations.

4.1.2. Axiology, Ontology and Epistemology

Paradigms are different ways of looking at the world (Cohen, Manion and Morrison, 2018), incorporating axiology, ontology, epistemology and methodology. Axiology incorporates a researcher's intent, position and value which ultimately drives and influences the research (Ling and Ling, 2017). A researcher's axiology may motivate and influence both the type and purpose of research they undertake and the research design (Ling and Ling, 2017). The second element ontology concerns the nature of reality (Cohen, Manion and Morrison, 2018). Braun and Clarke (2013) state that ontology involves human understanding of the world through the researcher's view of reality. If a researcher believes reality is consistent and does not change, then reality is positivist (Ling and Ling, 2017). However, if a researcher believes reality can change over time, it is neo-positivist (Ling and Ling, 2017). Both positivist and neo-positivist may lead the researcher towards objective knowledge research (Ling and Ling, 2017). Another ontological stance is interpretivist which 'focuses on how the social world is interpreted by those involved in it' (Robson and McCartan, 2016, p. 24), including everyday interactions with others (Cohen, Manion and Morrison, 2018). An interpretive ontology, may lead the researcher to undertake research that seeks to shed insights into people's subjective experience (Ling and Ling, 2017).

Epistemology is the nature of knowledge or understanding where the knowledge within research has come from (Ling and Ling, 2017). There are different theories of knowledge including positivist, whereby knowledge comes from knowable truth, or interpretivist where knowledge is socially constructed (Ling and Ling, 2017). Socially constructed knowledge relies ‘... as much as possible on the participant view of the situation being studied’ (Creswell and Creswell, 2020, p. 27) and how they make sense of their experience (Robson and McCartan, 2016). This specific theory of knowledge focuses on the different lived experiences of participants and is subjective. It requires the researcher to examine the situation through different lenses, in order to define the situation by focussing on environment, contexts and interactions (Cohen, Manion and Morrison, 2018). Knowledge is not fixed but is waiting to be constructed by the researcher and requires an understanding and interpretation of the knowledge from dialogue between the participants and the researcher (Ling and Ling, 2017).

Epistemological assumptions in turn inform methodological decisions – the methodology for the research. Methodology involves the researcher designing a systematic inquiry using research methods that are appropriate to address the research question (Ling and Ling, 2017) and are consistent with the axiological, ontological and epistemological assumptions underpinning the research. It is the framework within which research is conducted (Braun and Clarke, 2013) and different types of methodology can be employed depending on the research. This includes quantitative that is predominately used within a positivist paradigm to qualitative that is likely to be used within an interpretivist paradigm (Ling and Ling, 2017). Furthermore, if research is to be a ‘subjective, evidenced understanding and interpretation of a topic of research, the research falls in the interpretivist category’ (Ling and Ling, 2017, p. 12).

This research study adopted an interpretivist paradigm, as I wanted my axiological commitment to make space within the research design for the promotion of parents’ voice, discussed within section 4.2. The research was designed so that parents/carers could be actively involved in reviewing communication and parental engagement within the current transition programme from Rainbow ELC to Blue Primary School. It

was parents' interpretation and perceptions of the communication tools used, and parental engagement opportunities available during the transition programme, that were at the heart of the research. Ultimately, I wanted the parents/carers to have a voice in decisions that would affect them, hence the development of the steering group, discussed in section 4.3.1. My ontological assumption was interpretivist, as it was my intention through interpretation of the data to ascertain what the participants felt about the current communication tools used and parental engagement opportunities offered and any consequent changes. Crucially it was the participants' subjective knowledge, influenced by their experience of the current transition programme, that was pertinent to the research, thereby allowing me to address the research questions and associated aims.

The epistemology within this research was social constructivism. It was the participants' views and lived experience of the transition programme that were pertinent to the development of knowledge, about communication and parental engagement during the transition programme from Rainbow ELC to Blue Primary School. The information collected from the focus groups (FGs) and individual interviews were interpreted by me, the researcher, alongside the members of the Steering Group (SG). This collective analysis allowed us to uncover what the participants thoughts were from the data collected, thereafter constructing together future communication methods and parent engagement opportunities for the transition programme between both settings. In terms of research methods and data collection tools, adopting an interpretivist approach is associated with interviews, whereby multiple perspectives are valued (Robson and McCartan, 2016). The research methods employed within this research, discussed within sections 4.3.1. to 4.3.4., were FGs, interviews, reflective notes from both the researcher and participants and accompanying notes completed by the researcher. Additionally, the research gave me, the researcher, the opportunity to interact personally with all the participants who came from different social positions (Cresswell and Cresswell, 2020). It was the knowledge that the participants had, alongside the parent representatives on the SG, that were at the heart of this research, and ultimately supported answering the research questions and associated aims.

4.1.3. Case Study

Referring back to section 4.1.2., and this research study being an interpretative paradigm, there were a variety of methodologies appropriate to this paradigm. One such methodology, is case study research, which can be used to investigate in-depth a contemporary phenomenon within a real context (Yin, 2018). Case study is context specific and relevant to current practice (Hayes, 2019). Additionally, case study research should adopt, as required, a multifaceted approach to collecting evidence (Hayes, 2019) by using more than one method of data collection (Yin, 2018; Cohen, Manion and Morrison, 2018). This type of research, can also be firmly placed within the epistemological approach of constructivism, as it focuses on the researcher interpreting, translating, and articulating the case both systematically and analytically (Hayes, 2019) to make sense of participants' experience within the identified case. According to Yin (2018) there are three different types of case study that can be employed. The first type is an exploratory case study, which allows the researcher to explore 'the key issues affecting those in a case study setting' (Denscombe, 2014, p. 57) alongside adopting 'what' research questions' (Yin, 2018). The second type is an explanatory case study, which looks to explain a particular phenomenon focussing on 'how' and 'why' research questions, by explaining why certain conditions occur or do not occur (Yin, 2018). The final type is a descriptive case study which concentrates on describing in detail a phenomenon (Yin, 2018). There are also two main types of case design, a single case study (Yin 2018) and multi-case, whereby at least two case studies are involved (Yin, 2018). According to Denscombe (2014) it is also vital to have self-defined boundaries for the case.

There are advantages to employing a case study methodology, including the opportunity to: investigate in-depth; focus on relationships and social processes within social settings, taking a holistic view; and work with a situation that is natural and not artificial (Denscombe, 2014). However, limitations to adopting a case study research design may include making generalisation of findings hard as the 'case' is bound by the context of the research study (Denscombe, 2014).

For this research study a single exploratory case study approach was adopted. The self-defined boundaries of the case included exploring the 'key issue' of communication and the tools used to communicate with parents/carers about the transition between Rainbow ELC and Blue Primary School in the town of Westland between January 2023 and June 2023. It involved participants discussed in section 4.2, who were parents/carers of children attending Rainbow ELC who would be starting Blue Primary School in August 2023 and key staff from both educational settings. Furthermore, both research questions were 'what' questions – a type of question Yin (2018) states is suitable for an exploratory case study. The study also adopted the positive aspects outlined by Denscombe (2014) including: the situation being a real-life context; and an opportunity to investigate in-depth the communication tools and parental engagement opportunities from both parents/carers and professionals taking part in the research. The limitation of generalising the finding, discussed by Denscombe (2014) was also relevant to my research. However, it had not been my intention to generalise the findings discussed in Chapter Five, as these were relevant within the confinement of the context and time of this research study. Although the research cannot be generalised it does provide the opportunity to develop 'context dependent knowledge' (Flyvbjerg, 2006, p. 223), which could be relevant to both the EY and Primary sectors in Scotland, as discussed within *Chapter Eight: Recommendations*. It could also be used as a 'method of learning' (Flyvbjerg, 2006, p. 222), for professionals who wish to enhance their own setting's parental engagement through adopting a participatory approach, discussed in section 4.1.5.

4.1.4. The Positionality of the Researcher - Insider, Outsider or Inbetweener

All researchers need to consider critically and reflexivity their position and role within the research they are undertaking (Braun and Clarke, 2013). A researcher could be viewed as an outsider when they are not affected by the outcome of the research and are detached from any outcomes (Denscombe, 2014). Such a position may endorse the researcher as being impartial. Alternatively, a researcher could be viewed as an insider, due to professional links and an 'insider perspective' (Milligan 2016). This could influence the research, both positively or negatively, as the researcher uses their insider expert knowledge to understand/interpret the collected data (Milligan, 2016).

As an insider, the researcher is often not impartial or detached from the research context (Denscombe, 2014). Another position, from the participants' perspective, is an inbetweener (Milligan, 2016), whereby the researcher is a 'knowledgeable outsider' (Milligan, 2016), who has knowledge or previous experience of the situation being researched but is not necessarily invested in the outcomes of the research.

With respect to my position and role within this study, I could have had a variety of roles. Initially I felt an outsider (Denscombe, 2014), as I was not directly impacted by the research implications and recommendations, as discussed respectively in Chapters Five and Eight. Alternatively, I could have been viewed as an insider (Denscombe, 2014) by the participants, as I had at a professional level an 'insider perspective' (Milligan, 2016) - both relevant knowledge of the specific settings and a general understanding of the culture (Milligan, 2016) - transition from ELC to primary school. Also having direct access to the ELC staff and parent participants, due to working in Rainbow ELC during the data collection phase of the study discussed in section 2.3.2, furthered this viewpoint of being an insider researcher. This may have on reflection led to the participants including the parents, perceiving me as an insider, who worked within the ELC setting. Even although at the heart of my research, I was giving participants the opportunity to discuss their own personal views on communication and parental engagement provided during the transition programme. However, on reflection the participants may have provided responses they thought might influence insider practices, or be seen as favourable by me. The ELC staff and the future Primary One teachers may have also decided to only share information during their FGs that they felt I wanted to hear or information they felt safe to share.

My personal view of my positionality during the research was that I was an inbetweener. I had knowledge of the transition programme being undertaken between the settings involved in the case study, alongside in-depth knowledge of the transition from ELC to primary school within the local authority context. Although not directly impacted by the overall research, the knowledge gap discussed previously in section 1.1. was addressed, and my professional development, discussed in section 8.12.

enhanced. Being an inbetweener had inevitable implications for participant recruitment, analysis and interpretation as discussed in section 4.1.5.

4.1.5. Participatory Research Approach

Alongside the adoption of a case study methodology, this research embraced a participatory research approach. This type of approach involves ‘doing research *with* people and communities rather than doing research *to* or *for* people and communities’ (Cohen, Manion and Morrison, 2018, p. 56). Such an approach seeks to be democratic, aims to be reflective and makes use of knowledge from members within the community (Cohen, Manion and Morrison, 2018). A participatory research approach, can also give direct benefit to the community through their involvement in the project (Hall, 2005), perhaps by giving a voice to the participants (Schubotz, 2020). This type of research embraces the efforts of a community to investigate human problems using cultural and locale expertise to confront these problems (Galletta and Torre, 2019). Furthermore, a participatory research approach can involve the participation and influence of non-academic researchers (Warwick-Booth, Bagnall and Coan, 2021) working collaboratively alongside the researcher. Additionally, Macaulay (2017) states that participatory research is ‘an umbrella term for a school of approaches that share a core philosophy of inclusivity’ (Macaulay, 2017, p. 256). Within education research, a participatory approach centres on the experience and wisdom of participants from different hierarchies of power. This includes students, parents and educators who become ‘architects of the research, rather than objects of study’ (Galletta and Torre, 2019, p. 1) challenging the traditional top-down transmission of knowledge, alongside an ethical commitment to ‘redistribute power and legitimacy’ (Galletta and Torre, 2019, p. 1).

For this research adopting a participatory research approach meant that instead of the researcher (me) initiating the research, setting out the agenda, deciding how the data were to be collected and analysed, a SG were actively involved in making a number of these decisions alongside me. Although the research was initiated by me, it did indirectly assist Rainbow ELC in addressing a recommendation from a Care Inspectorate inspection in 2022, to strengthen communication with parents/carers.

The participation and collaboration of the participants of the SG, was central to the data collection methods selected. The research aimed to involve parents/carers and staff from Rainbow ELC and Blue Primary School as 'equal partners in the research' (Denscombe, 2014, p. 125), while 'democratizing the research process' (Denscombe, 2014, p. 126), as it sought to create contexts through which control shifted from the researcher (me) to the participants of this case study research. An in-depth reflection on this research approach is discussed in Chapter Seven. Adopting the participatory research approach involved participants of the SG, deciding collectively with the researcher, the qualitative research methods and tools employed, thereafter using the collated data to inform any changes to future transition programme for parents/carers of children transitioning from Rainbow ELC and Blue Primary School. For non-SG participants (interviewees), this involved the researcher seeking their views on communication and parental engagement within the context of transition and seeking ways in which their views could influence practice. The research set out to be participatory through general collaboration of community members (parents), organisational representatives (professionals) and the researcher, whereby the community members were deemed to be the experts (Warwick-Booth, Bagnall and Coan, 2021). Furthermore, the research aimed to embrace principles of inclusivity by engaging and involving the beneficiaries of the research (Macaulay, 2017).

Undertaking a participatory research approach, also involved considering power and the balance of power amongst the participants. As the researcher, I sought to acknowledge and value the parent participants and professionals, as they all had the insider and local contextual knowledge that was central to the research being undertaken (Cohen, Manion and Morrison, 2018). From the outset, I wanted all participants, whether members of the SG or not, to influence decisions that were to be made (Warwick-Booth, Bagnall and Coan, 2021). Parent participants, were the key participant group who *could* be viewed as both active and powerful rather than having a passive role (Cohen, Manion and Morrison, 2018), as their particular viewpoints could impact the transition programme currently implemented between the two settings. Members of the SG, both parents and professionals did have more control due to their specific involvement in different aspects of the research development, including selecting the data collection methods and tools. From the outset of the

research, I was fully committed as it was ultimately my research project with the members of the SG and the other participants all being invited to join and take part, thereby being committed to their part in the participatory approach adopted by this research. According to Warwick-Booth, Bagnall and Coan (2021), when adopting a participatory research approach, the power expectations of the participants and the researcher could be viewed differently. Therefore, the knowledge, views, contribution and opinions that the parents and the members of staff (who were participants) had were all ethically respected, as discussed in section 4.6. by me, the researcher. Moreover, adopting this stance 'emphasises the participation and influence of non-academic researchers in the process of creating knowledge' (Warwick-Booth, Bagnall and Coan, 2021, p. 4). It values personal knowledge (Eraut, 2004) by exploring what people know, do, learn and how they interpret and use what they learn (Eraut, 2014). Personal knowledge was valued in this research, as it sought to find out from the participants interviewed their experiences of communication tools and parental engagement during the current transition programme.

Finally, according to Jackson (2008) data analysis that is participatory is often the last stage to be opened up for participation. Undertaking this form of analysis can support participation by encouraging participants to listen to each other and work together, thus giving a richer interpretation of the data (Warwick-Booth, Bagnall and Coan (2021). For the SG members involved in my research, this involved collectively reflecting upon/interpreting (alongside the researcher) what the collected data might mean and what amendments to the transition programme could be made as a result. As such, attempts were made to ensure that the SG were actively involved in 'co-decision making' (Macaulay, 2017, p. 256) throughout the research process, as discussed in section 4.3.1.

4.1.6. Navigating Issues of Power in Participatory Research

When a researcher is embarking on research that embraces a participatory approach, the mitigation of power relations involves going against the traditional power dynamics in favour of an approach where the researcher uses dialogue and collaborative inquiry to work with 'non-expert researchers' (Warwick-Booth, Bagnall and Coan, 2021). This

can involve sharing power with participants, enabling them to make key decisions (Hickey *et. al.* 2018; Israel *et. al.* 2008), through challenging the traditional hierarchy of research (Schubotz, 2020). Within this research, I sought to empower the participants of the SG when it came to key decisions, including the final list of interview questions and data collection methods employed. I also sought to challenge the traditional hierarchal power, as decisions related to communication tools used and parental engagement opportunities to be offered during future transition programmes were made collectively by the SG - not solely by either the DHT or the Head of ELC. Seeking to engage in some sort of power sharing or (at least) a sense of active participation in decision making required all the participants, particularly the members of the SG, to acknowledge the consequences of decisions made for the two settings and the future parents of children involved in the transition between both settings (Thomas, 2010) – due to the research timescale, any amendments would be put in place the following academic year (2023-2024).

Professional power was something that I, as the researcher, specifically needed to consider, on two occasions while collecting the data. The first occasion was in the FG with the future Primary One teachers, because (unbeknown to me) when the DHT was recruiting the teachers on my behalf, I had actually taught one of them as a child, but I did not know this until we met face-to-face for the FG. On reflection, having an established relationship with this teacher may have in my opinion actually benefitted the discussion, as she appeared to be very open and the most forthcoming of the three participants. Although in hindsight it would have been advantageous to have enquired whether knowing me did actually affect her openness during the future Primary One teachers FG. The second occasion was while I was recruiting parent participants for the individual interviews, as this included a prospective parent, who I had recently professionally worked alongside. Unfortunately, she decided not to participate and, whilst it was hard for me to accept the rejection, I needed to accept her decision, not to take part. Reflecting on her decision not to participate, this could have been influenced by the hierarchy and power dynamics between us, as she was an EY practitioner and I was a peripatetic nursery teacher. Therefore, she might not have found it easy to distinguish my professional role as a teacher and a recent colleague, to that of a researcher when I was asking her to take part in the research.

4.2. Participants

Within this single case exploratory study, it was vital to consider who the participants of this research were going to be – the case being the 2022-2023 transition programme between Rainbow ELC and Blue Primary School and those involved in that transition. Selecting participants was an important part of this research, and one that ultimately required permission being granted from gatekeepers. Sometimes when undertaking research, permission to access participants can be required from different gatekeepers, who seek to mitigate any negative consequences/effects for either the participants or themselves (Cohen, Manion and Morrison, 2018). Permission for my research to take place in both a local authority school and an ELC setting was granted by a gatekeeper (Head of Education) via a standard ethics application form. Letters were also sent to and discussed with the Head of ELC (*Appendix 3 – ELC Letter*) and Head Teacher of the primary school (*Appendix 4 – School Letter*) seeking permission to contact staff and for the ELC parents/carers as well. Email permission was given by both for their respective settings to take part. The permission to both contact and collect data from participants was granted up to the end of June 2023 – the period that I had identified as the necessary time to collect data pertinent to this small-scale Professional Doctorate research study. As a peripatetic teacher, it was also the end of my time working in Rainbow ELC as I had been informed that I would be moving onto working in another nursery after the summer holidays. As such I ended direct contact with Rainbow ELC in June 2023.

For any research, consideration needs to be given to participant selection and how they represent the population being researched (Dawson, 2015). This is known as the sample. There are two main approaches to sampling that might be employed – probability, also known as random sampling, whereby participants are selected at random from the wider population, allowing generalisation of research results (Cohen, Manion and Morrison, 2018). The second is non-probability, also known as purposive sampling, where participants are targeted because they possess specific characteristics for a specific purpose within the research (Cohen, Manion and Morrison, 2018). Purposive sampling is frequently used in small-scale research, as it provides a greater depth of the data (Cohen, Manion and Morrison, 2018).

Purposive sampling was employed for this research, by inviting participants from the available population, namely parents and staff from within the boundaries of the case. These participants were knowledgeable about the communication tools used between home and the ELC/primary school, and the associated transition parental engagement opportunities available. The criteria for parent selection, was that their child attended Rainbow ELC and would be starting at Blue Primary School in August 2023. Therefore, the parent was directly involved in the transition programme during the academic year 2022-2023. For educational staff, the criteria required staff that were knowledgeable and actively involved in the current transition programme between the ELC and the primary school. In addition, leadership representation from both Rainbow ELC and Blue Primary School was sought as part of the SG, because senior leaders had: insight into the transition programme from the settings involved; indicated interest in taking part in the research; and the power to justify putting into practice (or not) decisions made by the SG group.

The purposive sampling for this research also involved two distinct groups. The first group included parents and educational representatives of both Rainbow ELC (Head of ELC and Transition Coordinator) and Blue Primary School (DHT) who were to become members of the SG, sometimes referred to as higher-level participants (Coghlan and Brydon-Miller, 2014). The second group involved other parents and staff from Rainbow ELC and the future Primary One teachers for August 2023 who met the above criteria. As these participants were not involved in the SG (but in the research interviews/FG), they might be referred to in research terms, as lower-level participants (Coghlan and Brydon-Miller, 2014).

As I was working at the time in Rainbow ELC, the Head of Rainbow ELC shared names of children who had registered to start Primary One at Blue Primary School in August 2023. All parents from this list of children, were invited to take part in the research. Additionally, the Head of Rainbow ELC indicated parents who may be available to join the SG, as meetings were taking place during the working day. I therefore focussed on approaching and speaking to these parents about becoming members of the SG and after approaching eight parents, four parents agreed. Each parent received the

participant information sheet (*Appendix 5 – Participant Information Sheet – Steering Group (Parents)*) and consent form (*Appendix 6 – Consent Form (Steering Group)*). All consent forms were completed and returned prior to the first SG meeting. Unfortunately, the number of parent participants reduced to two after the first SG meeting as one parent indicated after the first meeting that they were unable to participate further. A second parent whose child had been ill and had been unable to attend the first meeting, indicated through no response to further communication, withdrawal from the group. Ethically, I accepted their withdrawals and did not use my influence as a member of staff within Rainbow ELC at that time to encourage them to remain part of the SG. The remaining two parents continued to be actively involved. This was further supported by the Head of ELC who was happy for both mothers to bring younger children into the SG meetings, thereby enabling both parents to remain part of the group by removing a barrier to their active involvement, namely childcare. In terms of education staff membership of the SG, the Head of ELC nominated both the Transition Coordinator and herself, while the HT of Blue Primary School nominated the DHT, whose remit involved leading the transition from all ELC settings to Blue Primary School. As all three nominated staff were willing to participate in the research, they each received the participant information sheet (*Appendix 7 – Steering Group (ELC/Primary Staff)*) and completed and signed a consent form (*Appendix 6*) prior to the first SG meeting.

The second group involved all the remaining parents who met the purposive sampling criteria of having a child starting Blue Primary School in August 2023. These forty parents were initially invited to participate in FGs, via individually addressed envelopes containing a participant information sheet (*Appendix 8 – Individual Interviews (Parents/Carers)*), consent form (*Appendix 9 – Consent Form (Interview)*) and covering introductory letter. From the outset it had been extremely challenging to recruit parents to participate, particularly as this was a case study with a finite number of parent participants to invite to take part, coupled with a limited time to interview this group of parents due to SG meetings to be concluded by the end of June 2023. Reflecting back on the challenge of recruiting parents, I had initially thought that as I worked in the nursery at that point in time it would have been easier to recruit parents, as I could have been viewed as an insider, but this was not the case. Although some

parents agreed to take part in FGs, parents' work commitments on the date arranged for these and the challenge of getting enough parents together at the available times resulted in the FGs being changed to individual semi-structured interviews. In total nine parents out of the possible forty parents, (eight of whom were working parents) agreed to become involved and returned a signed consent form. Five parents took part in face-to-face interviews, with the remaining four opting for online interviews via MS Teams. Participants for the ELC staff FG, were individually approached by the researcher (me). Four members of staff, out of a possible eight agreed to take part and received a participant information sheet (*Appendix 10 – Focus Group (ELC/Primary School Staff)*) and consent form (*Appendix 11 – Consent Form (Focus Group)*). The DHT from Blue Primary School assisted me by handing out the participant information sheet (*Appendix 10*) and consent form (*Appendix 11*) to the teachers at the primary school who met the sampling criteria (future Primary One teachers) for the FG. All three agreed to participate, returning a signed consent form prior to the FG.

As there were different ways for the participants to be involved in the research, *Table One – Participant Involvement and Data Collection*, summarises: the different activities which participants were involved in; the focus of the data collection; and the data that was collected for each activity. From *Table One*, it is noteworthy that the FGs with ELC staff and the future Primary One teachers which occurred mid-May had both been easy to organise. However, due to changing from parent FGs to individual parent interviews, it took more than three weeks to undertake the interviews, due to parent commitments and my own work availability. Consequently, this had a knock-on effect of agreeing suitable dates with SG members for the second and third SG meeting.

Date	Activity	Participants	Focus of Data Collection	Data Collected
17/03/23	First Steering Group Meeting	Researcher; Head of ELC; Transition Coordinator; Steering Parents 1, 2, and 3; DHT from primary school (online, via MS Teams)	Discuss and decide ground rules; questions to be asked to the different participants – parents, ELC staff and future Primary One teachers; best way to undertake data collection with the parents – focus groups or individual interviews.	Researcher reflective notes and action points Participants reflections on meeting (<i>Appendix 12 – Reflective Notes Completed</i>) Meeting Notes Minutes of Meetings
09/06/23	Second Steering Group Meeting	Researcher; Head of ELC; Transition Coordinator; Steering Parents 1 and 2	Look and respond individually to data; discuss as a group, what the data were saying to them.	Researcher reflective notes and action points Participants reflections on meeting (<i>Appendix 12</i>) Meeting Notes Minutes of Meeting
26/06/23	Third Steering Group Meeting	Researcher; Head of Rainbow ELC; Transition Coordinator; Steering Parents 1 and 2. DHT from Blue Primary School	Look and respond individually to final data; in pairs decide from data what should be kept, discarded or introduced; discuss as a full group and make decisions about communication tools and parental engagement.	Researcher reflective notes Oral participant responses to reflection on steering group involvement Action points from the research Meeting Notes Minutes of Meeting
22/05/23-19/06/23	One to One interview with nine parents	Researcher and Parent	Individual interviews to find out parent responses to questions decided at first steering group meeting.	Semi-structured interview responses Researcher reflective notes Participant reflections on interview – reflective note (<i>Appendix 12</i>)
12/05/23	Focus Group with future Primary One teachers	Researcher and three Primary One teachers for session 2022-2023	Interview to find responses to questions decided at first steering group meeting.	Participants responses during focus group Researcher reflective notes Participants reflections on focus group – reflective notes (<i>Appendix 12</i>)
18/05/23	Focus Group with staff from ELC	Researcher, Team Leader, Parent and Child Support Worker, two Early Years Practitioners	Interview to find responses to questions decided at first steering group meeting.	Participants responses during focus group Researcher reflective notes Participants reflections on focus group – reflective notes (<i>Appendix 12</i>)

Table One – Participant Involvement and Data Collection

4.3. Qualitative Data Collection

As part of an exploratory case study, it is important to select appropriate data collection methods and tools that allow the researcher to make the link between the research being undertaken and the real-world context that the research occurs in (Yin, 2018). Additionally, it is crucial that the selected research methods and tools align with the research methodology and paradigm. As this case study research adopted an

interpretivist paradigm, it made use of qualitative research methods. These included semi-structured interviews and FGs, as both provide responses that are data rich in-depth description (Braun and Clarke, 2013). These qualitative data collection methods, permit open-ended responses, as more than one answer can be given, giving the researcher the opportunity to gain a deeper understanding of the topic from the participants' perspective (Braun and Clarke, 2013). Additionally, written accompanying notes/reflective notes can be used as a data collection method to provide reflective insight into the thoughts of both researchers and participants (Braun and Clarke, 2013).

Within this study a variety of data collection methods, discussed in *Table One – Participant Involvement and Data Collection* were employed, they were interviews, FGs and accompanying notes/reflective notes to gather data. These are discussed in detail within sections 4.3.2., 4.3.3. and 4.3.4. As discussed previously in section 4.1.5., the SG was involved in making decisions about which data collection methods would be employed with which participants. Thereafter, the data from the collected interviews and FGs were shared with the SG so that we could collectively discuss and explore possible changes to the current communication tools used to engage parents during the transition programme from Rainbow ELC to Blue Primary School. The next section explains what a steering group is and how it was used within the research study before discussing the data collection methods and tools employed within the research.

4.3.1. Steering Group

One way to involve parents in participatory research is the development of steering groups (SG). These groups involve members 'using their experiences, skills and knowledge of specific topics to help make strategic decisions' (Mind, 2025) using work completed by others. Within this research study, the SG was developed specifically to embrace the participatory aspect of the research, namely to promote active participation, including parents in making decisions about communication tools and parental engagement. The SG consisted of parents whose children were transitioning from Rainbow ELC to Blue Primary School, staff from Rainbow ELC and Blue Primary

School (who had experience of the current transition programme being undertaken between the ELC and Blue Primary School) and the researcher (*Appendix 13 – Steering Group Members*). Through membership of the SG, the participants had the opportunity to ‘gain knowledge, skills, capacity and power’ (Israel *et. al.* 2008, p. 11) through partnership working between the educational staff and parent members. It was hoped that both would be viewed as partners in the decision-making process. The SG also sought to embrace the principles of the *Scottish Schools (Parental Involvement) Act 2006*, whereby parents/carers have the opportunity to express their views and be involved in decisions that affect their child’s education. The group formation employed a ‘researcher-initiated model’ (Schubotz, 2020), as the researcher approached the participants to become members of the group to help investigate, and ultimately answer, the research questions and aims. Parent members of the SG group had higher-level participation (Coghlan and Brydon-Miller, 2014) as I sought to empower them to decide, in conjunction with the researcher and other members of the SG, key questions to be asked by the researcher during the ELC and Primary One staff FGs and to parent participants. The extent to which these parents were positioned as equal partners, and the extent to which they viewed themselves as equal partners will be considered within *Chapter Five: Findings and Chapter Six: Discussion and Implications*.

When undertaking research in such a context, it is suggested that ground rules for group work are established in order that all members feel safe, included and heard, while allowing members to refer back to the ground rules if required (Braun and Clarke, 2013). Therefore, ground rules for the SG were agreed at the start of the first meeting to support attempts at equal participation. The agreed rules were: please maintain confidentiality of what we are discussing; please do not to share discussion points out with the group and; please respect the opinions of other members of the group. On reflection, these rules could have been more explicit in facilitating extended responses from all participants.

At the first SG meeting, collective decisions were made by all members, drawing on their insider knowledge of the settings (Eisner, 2002). These decisions included

undertaking parent FGs (rather than 1:1 interviews) as these might support the parent participants better, as the parent members of the SG felt that the parents may feel that FGs were more a conversation/chat, as opposed to individual interviews which might be more nerve-racking for some parents. However, it was agreed that if FGs were not possible, then individual interviews would be an alternative method of data collection with the parents. Unfortunately, the latter choice ended up being the data collection method employed for parent participants, as discussed in section 4.3.3. Another collective decision was how the data from the FGs should be collected. The SG recommended that the FGs should be recorded using audio only, as they felt that participants, especially the parents might have felt uneasy being videoed. Audio recording options available for this research were Microsoft Teams with the video off, or recording using a digital recorder. To make transcription easier and quicker for 'in-person' interviews, I decided to use MS Teams with the camera off. This method was also used during the four interviews with parents online. At the same meeting, SG members decided the final schedule of key questions the researcher would ask the parents, ELC staff and future Primary One teachers, from a possible list of questions prepared in advance by the researcher. To embrace the participatory research approach, it was imperative that the researcher involved all members of the SG in deciding the final list of questions for parents (*Appendix 14 – Final Questions (Individual Interviews)*) and FGs (*Appendix 15 – Final Questions (Focus Group)*). On reflection, the decisions made collectively as a group, particularly related to the data collection methods and tools, was hard for me. Traditionally in previous research I had made decisions about the best way I felt to collect the data, which for the parents would have been to conduct individual interviews. They would have from the outset been easier to organise and was a research method used by me when working with parent participants for previous research studies, including my Master Degree. However, I knew I wanted to adopt a participatory research approach within this study and utilise the SG members insider knowledge of the context and possible participants.

During the second SG meeting, we undertook a task where all members individually spent time looking at the data posters (*Appendix 16 – Data Posters*), that contained responses to the questions asked during both the FGs and individual interviews

placing sticky note comments about what the collected data were saying to them on each poster. These comments concentrated on the members' own interpretation of the data, including anything they felt was interesting/noteworthy. This task was completed individually before SG members discussed their thoughts collectively as a group. However, as the second SG meeting took place before all the data had been collected, part of the third (final) SG meeting involved spending time looking at data collected from Parents 7, 8 and 9. Also at the third meeting, participants worked in pairs, discussing all the shared data and deciding, in response to the data reviewed, 'which communication tools and parental engagement activities should we stop doing, keep doing, develop or introduce?'. The group then came together and discussed their responses before collectively deciding what should be stopped, continued or introduced as new ideas to become part of future transition programmes. In this way, employing a SG enabled this study to be more democratic (Schubotz, 2020), as decisions were made collectively, while providing a richer interpretation of the data than would have been possible if undertaken solely by me, the researcher.

It is also important to note that all data collected by the researcher and consequently shared with the steering group was anonymised prior to being shared with the members at the second and third SG meeting (see Appendix 16). All participants had been reminded during either their focus group (FG) or individual interview that the data was going to be shared anonymously with members of the SG and all these participants agreed that they were happy to continue with either the FG or interview on this basis. The members of the SG were not aware of which parents had been interviewed or what pseudonym had been given to each participant. Staff participants were aware that their anonymised data was to be shared with the SG and despite being known to the Head of ELC and DHT as participants in the study, were happy to proceed on this basis.

When reflecting on the SG it was important to consider the role that I had within the group. As I was professional working in Rainbow ELC there was a likelihood that I was viewed as an insider, as I had knowledge of the transition programme that was taking place or planned between Rainbow ELC and Blue Primary School, as this had

been shared with me by the Transition Coordinator. I also had general insider information about transition from my previous role as a nursery class teacher and knew the sort of transition events that should be planned to involve parents and how the parents were often communicated with by a school. However, I do feel that the parents may have found the power dynamics of being in a group with professionals challenging as the professionals (including me) had a good understanding of the transition programme operating between both settings, while the parents did not as both parents were taking part in the transition programme alongside their children for the first time and so had no prior experiential knowledge to draw on. Therefore, they may have felt uneasy with initially voicing their opinion and ideas. With hindsight, I feel I could have held a meeting prior to the first official SG meeting to give everyone a chance to chat informally and get to know each other on a more personal level, as this may have supported developing a relationship, particularly with the DHT and myself as we were both professionals who were not well known to the parents. This may have helped mitigate the potential for staff to be viewed as figures of authority by the SG parents. Additionally, this may have further supported the parents to have the confidence to speak openly in the group, thereby promoting the equal voice for all members of the SG that I was keen to enable. Power dynamics may also have come into play during the final meeting, as the parents decided to work only together. I had felt that this was because they were sitting beside each other but on reflection this could have been a result of the parents feeling more comfortable together and feeling (perhaps) more empowered to hold a view when not working with staff. On reflection, had I chosen to pair them with a staff member these parents *may* have felt more inhibited to voice their opinion.

4.3.2. Focus Group Interviews

Focus groups (FGs) is a data collection method suitable for undertaking qualitative data collection with groups, usually consisting of between six to nine people (Denscombe, 2014). These groups give insights into the collective view of the topic being discussed (Cohen, Manion and Morrison, 2018), with a large amount of data collected quickly. FGs can take different approaches including closed, semi-structured or open-ended interviews. They are also popular in social research, mimicking real-

life exchanges (Braun and Clarke, 2013) whilst often making people feel more comfortable, than in individual interviews. Braun and Clarke (2013) recommend that FG interviews take place somewhere quiet and comfortable, with seating left open for participants to select where they wish to sit. FGs also provide an opportunity to acquire data more efficiently, taking less time to undertake than individual interviews with the same number of participants (Leedy and Ormod, 2015), although it is acknowledged that FGs can be logistically difficult as it can be hard to agree times for everyone to come together (Braun and Clarke, 2013). Furthermore, FGs data may not be as data rich as individual interviews. Additionally, they may lead to the discussion becoming dominated by some participants at the detriment of others being unable/unwilling to voice their opinion on the topic being discussed (Newby, 2014). This can be mitigated, by establishing basic ground rules prior to beginning FG interviews (Braun and Clarke, 2013).

For this study, following agreement with the SG, it was initially envisaged that there would be FGs adopting a semi-structured interview approach with parents, one FG with educational staff from the Blue Primary School and one FG with staff from Rainbow ELC. Unfortunately, due to the challenge of getting parents together, the parent FGs were replaced by individual interviews. However, FGs were still employed to collect data from both the ELC staff (consisting of four participants) and the future Primary One teachers for August 2023 (three participants). Both FGs took the approach of semi-structured interviews, using the key questions finalised at the first SG meeting (Appendix 15). The FG with the primary teachers took place in a multi-purpose room in Blue Primary School, with a large table with seats on one side for the participants and a seat in the middle of the opposite side for the researcher. The ELC staff FG took place in the small management meeting room with seats around small tables joined together. Prior to both meetings beginning, basic ground rules were established. These included that everyone would have the opportunity to speak and participants should not speak over each other. Introducing and agreeing ground rules hopefully mitigated against someone dominating the discussion.

4.3.3. Individual Semi-Structured Parent Interviews

Semi-structured interviews are popular within qualitative research (Denscombe, 2014) as they are flexible and interactive (Menter *et. al.*, 2011). They allow interviewees flexibility in how they respond to questions, including being able to give 'rich and highly illuminating material' (Robson and McCartan, 2016, p. 286). Interviews can follow an interview schedule of open-ended questions (Braun and Clarke, 2013). This gives the interviewer the opportunity to alter the wording, in order to support the participants understanding of what is being asked and to prompt/probe for further details/insights. Undertaking individual interviews, allows the researcher the opportunity to get the rich and detailed data, while also having the opportunity to develop a rapport with the interviewee (Braun and Clarke, 2013). However, it is acknowledged that undertaking several individual interviews is more time consuming, whilst taking longer to transcribe than FG interviews (Braun and Clarke, 2013; Menter *et. al.*, 2011). Furthermore, it can be challenging for the researcher to ensure that they do not influence the interviewee (Menter *et. al.*, 2011). Therefore, having an interview schedule of consistent questions can help reduce the influence on the interviewee.

Semi-structured interviews were suitable for this research, as the research sought to understand parent experiences of, and aspirations for, communication around transition. Each interview followed an interview schedule of open-ended questions (Appendix 14). Adopting this type of interview was reassuring, as I had the flexibility to change the wording should a parent require support to understand the question. On reflection, once the decisions about changing from parent FGs to individual parent interviews had been made, these were actually easier to arrange. Although the transcription of each interview took longer to transcribe than the FGs, transcription was easier, as I only had to concentrate on one voice at a time (Denscombe, 2014). Building a rapport with individual parents was also easier as I was able to make reference to their child throughout the interview, adding a personal aspect to each interview. In order to mitigate against influencing the interviewee, I focussed on the interview schedule questions and endeavoured to ensure interviewees had enough time to respond before either asking an additional question related to their response or slightly amending the questioning if I felt the interviewee was unsure of how to

respond. A summary of when the individual parent interviews took place can be found in *Appendix 17 – Parent Interviews*. In total nine parents were interviewed over a period of about three weeks, six parents prior to Blue Primary School Head Teacher’s transition talk for parents and three after the transition talk had taken place.

Furthermore, when involving participants in research, it is important to be aware of social desirability bias. Bergen and Labonte (2020) state this ‘bias denotes a mismatch between participants’ genuine construction of reality and the presentation of that reality to the researchers’ (Bergen and Labonte, 2020 p. 783). Within research this can be problematic, as the participants may overestimate the positives in their responses, thereby affecting the consensus of opinion (Bergen and Labonte, 2020). To mitigate this possibility, I sought to interview as many parent participants who met the purposive sampling criteria, in order to get a range of views related to the questions asked. Face-to-face interaction during the parent interview allowed me when necessary to clarify participant responses. The face-to-face parent interviews were held in private rooms, encouraging participants to speak honestly, as no one would be able to hear what they were saying. To minimise this further, I reiterated that their responses from the individual interviews would be anonymised prior to sharing.

4.3.4. Accompanying Notes/Reflective Notes

Researchers undertaking qualitative research can also use accompanying notes/reflective notes. These are permanent record of events, as interpreted by the researcher (Denscombe, 2014) and give the researcher the opportunity, as soon as possible after the event, to record personal reactions to participant(s), reflections on participants’ contributions and conduct and ideas for data analysis (Braun and Clarke, 2013). According to Campbell, McNamara and Gilroy (2004) written accompanying notes should include events, dates and times which, if completed by the researcher, can be used as an aide-memoire of the event. If participants are asked to complete a written comment/reflective note, these can give the researcher a reflective insight into the thoughts and feelings of those taking part in a research event (Robson and McCartan, 2016; Braun and Clarke, 2013). However, there are challenges and limitations when using reflective notes/accompanying notes, including the timescale

taken by participants or researcher to complete after the event has taken place (Denscombe, 2014). Cohen, Manion and Morrison (2018) recommend that, if notes have been initially hand written, they should be typed up, making them easier to store, retrieve and read later.

As an additional qualitative research method, accompanying notes/reflective notes were employed within this research. All participants taking part in FGs, individual interview or SG meeting were offered the opportunity to complete written reflective notes after their interview/FG or the first two SG meetings. The reflective notes completed by parent members of the SG, gave an insight into the extent to which they felt equal participants in the decisions being made, are discussed within section 5.6.1. To assist SG participants, guidance indicating what might be included in their note was given (*Appendix 18 – Reflective Note Template Steering Group Meeting One/Reflective Note Template ELC/Teacher/Parents*). Following advice from supervisors, the second SG meeting reflective note guidance included specific questions for the participants to consider when completing their response (*Appendix 19 – Reflective Note Template Steering Group Meeting Two*). As the researcher, I also completed accompanying notes/reflective notes after each SG, interview or FG, reflecting my thoughts and including anything of particular interest or possible areas to be looked at as part of the initial data analysis. The reflective notes completed by participants aided the interpretation of the data collected from the different participants, as they complemented the other data collection methods already discussed. To aid transparency, a summary of who completed the reflective notes, excluding the researcher's reflective notes, is found in *Appendix 12 – Reflective Notes Completed*. This highlighted that almost all ELC staff completed reflective notes, alongside two out of the three future Primary One teachers. This contrasted with the DHT who completed a short email note following her participation in the first SG. However, only two out of the nine parents who were individually interviewed completed and returned a reflective note. For the SG parents, one parent (SP2) who attended SG meetings one and two completed both reflective notes, with the other parent (SP1) who attended both these meetings completing a note for the first meeting. SP3 who only attended the first SG meeting completed a reflective note for that meeting. All reflective notes were readable with no requirement to contact any participants for clarification. The

researcher typed each reflective note onto the computer before transferring this data onto NVivo computer software for analysis.

4.4. Analysing the Data

This section discusses in detail the analysis that was undertaken, and how, in part, it embraced the participatory research approach adopted by this research. This includes analysis of data undertaken by members of the SG, but also analysis undertaken separately by me, the researcher.

4.4.1. Transcription and Analysis

Researchers should give careful consideration to how qualitative data is to be transcribed once it has been collected and analysed at the research design stage (Cohen, Manion and Morrison, 2018). This includes considering how data can be turned from audio data if it has been recorded into written text to support later analysis (Braun and Clarke, 2013). There are different ways that transcription can be undertaken digitally and electronically. This includes the use of computer software (such as NVivo) or via Microsoft (MS) Teams or Zoom's captions facility to assist with transcription of meetings that had previously been recorded.

For this research, the FGs and individual interviews transcriptions were taken directly from the recordings made by MS Teams software during the interviews and FGs, with the exception of one interview recorded via Zoom, which was played back at a later date and transcribed using MS Teams software. Thereafter, all transcripts were double checked by the researcher who listened to each interview and FG checking for accuracy and amending when needed, as some words had either not been transcribed correctly or had been missed out. To further support privacy, prior to each transcript being analysed, all participants were given a pseudonym, either an alternative name or Parent 1, Parent 2 etc.

In terms of analysing the data from an exploratory case study, it is important to develop an analytic strategy. This includes giving consideration to how the research data will be evidenced and presented (Yin, 2018) and how data analysis will address the research question(s) and aims. A thematic approach was also adopted by the researcher to systematically and rigorously analyse the data. The researcher's thematic analysis involved looking across all the data sets to identify emergent themes, employing Braun and Clarke (2022) six reflexive thematic analysis phases:

Phase 1 – Familiarising yourself with the data set

Phase 2 – Coding

Phase 3 – Generating initial themes

Phase 4 – Developing and reviewing themes

Phase 5 – Refining, defining and naming themes

Phase 6 – Writing up

Phase 1 involved me, as the researcher, immersing myself with the data through listening repeatedly to the interviews and FGs. Repeated listening gave me the opportunity to become familiar with all the data that had been collected and who had said what. Continuing to follow Braun and Clarke's (2022) guidance, phase 2 involved all transcripts being transferred electronically to Nvivo computer software. There are a number of benefits of using Nvivo computer software, including the tools within its software application that can help to code and categorise (Yin, 2018; Cohen, Manion and Morrison, 2018). NVivo also makes it easier to retrieve and find specific sources of data from files or codes (Cohen, Manion, Morrison, 2018). Using Nvivo computer software I undertook a systematic coding of the data, coding the data directly by assigning codes to phrases from the transcripts. At that point in the data analysis, there were ninety-nine initial codes (*Appendix 20 – Initial Codes*). Although I initially considered using a handwritten approach to code the data, I felt that this would make it harder to find data from individual participants related to a particular code, hence the decision to use electronic software, namely Nvivo computer software. Furthermore, as I analysed the data collected from the nine parents interviewed, it was evident that while analysing data from the final parent (Parent 9) that no new codes arose.

Phase 3 involved looking within the ninety-nine codes for any emerging themes related to the first research question, associated aims or interesting things within the data. At that point of analysis, this led to twelve overarching initial themes for aims one to three and four for aim four (*Appendix 21 – Themes*). For phase 4, the twelve themes were reviewed further, leaving eight overarching themes for aims one to three and two for aim four - other data and codes had been eliminated as they did not warrant further exploration. Phase 5 involved naming the final overarching themes for each aim and the final stage, phase 6, involved writing up the findings, which are discussed throughout Chapter Five.

It is important to note that as analysis of the data deepened, it was vital to continually refer back to both the first research question and associated aims to check that the coded data actually addressed these. Throughout the data analysis section, I was mindful of my own bias (Menter *et. al.*, 2011), as discussed in sections 4.3.2 and 4.5. This included my knowledge of the subject which informed my personal viewpoint and experience of what the local authority envisages should happen with respect to communication about transition. Throughout the reflexive thematic analysis phases 1 to 6, the collected data were shared with my supervisors, and from these regular discussions it became evident that some of the data could be viewed from more than one perspective depending on where the collected data came from.

The SG also informed interpretation of the data. Through embracing the participatory research approach, members of the SG were both beneficiaries and contributors to the research, as they potentially benefitted from any amendments to current communication tools and parental engagement in the transition programme. Within this research, it was important that the SG had the opportunity to respond and comment upon the collected data, from the parent interviews and the future Primary One teachers and ELC Staff FGs. These opportunities (discussed in section 4.3.1) arose during the second and third SG meetings where anonymised data were grouped together under each interview question and shared with the SG members via posters (*Appendix 16*). At these SG meetings, members looked at each poster individually, placing comments about the data they were reading on sticky notes. Their comments

helped me, as the researcher, to inform my initial engagement with the data and possible emerging themes that were coming forward as interesting to SG members, including barriers and practical engagement opportunities for parents. At the final SG meeting, we used the data collected to discuss and decide collectively on amendments that could be made to the current transition programme in relation to communication tools and parental engagement. Decisions made by the SG are discussed in detail within *Chapter Five: Findings* and included in *Appendix 22 - Steering Group Meeting Three Task (Collated Results)* and *Appendix 23 – What to Take Forward*.

As noted previously, the SG members were involved in the initial analysis of the data, and this could have led to ethical challenges. The data made available to the SG included data collected from Parent 9 (the parent who suggested a (mis)communication from the Nursery whilst also choosing not to access the Nursery App on which transition information was posted). With respect to ethical challenges, I could have been asked by colleagues to identify that particular parent so that Rainbow ELC could ensure that the parent knew about upcoming transition opportunities. If the Head of ELC or Transition Coordinator had asked for the parent's name, this could have placed me in an ethically compromising situation. As an inbetween, I was committed to the principle of participant anonymity, but as the Head of ELC was 'my boss' I might have felt under pressure to share the parent's name. As both researcher and employee, I could empathise with both perspectives. Fortunately, this scenario did not occur. If it had, I would have explained that research ethics required that I would not disclose who the parent was. I might have suggested that Rainbow ELC staff consider how all parents/carers are communicated with about the transition opportunities. This could include making the most of face-to-face discussions when children were dropped off/collected from nursery or having the information that has been placed on the Nursery App also displayed at the entrance to the playrooms. Such an approach could help to ensure that all parents/carers were made aware of key transition information, using communication tools that are accessible to all parents.

4.5. Trustworthiness in Qualitative Research

Trustworthiness in qualitative research is very important, with Lincoln and Guba (1985) identifying different criteria for researchers to use when considering how to conduct research, which ultimately informs decisions made by the researcher, helping to make it trustworthy. The first criteria is credibility, where researchers: acknowledge reflexivity within their research including personal biases and preconceptions; employ more than one data method; and allow enough time to build a rapport and trust with participants. Adhering to these criteria enable readers to have confidence in the research findings including the richness of the collected data (Ahmed, 2024). The second criteria is transferability which assumes that researchers: clearly describe their sample; provide good contextual information and a rich description. Adhering to these criteria enables readers to decide whether the findings are relevant and transferable to other contexts, including their own (Ahmed, 2024). The third criteria is dependability, where researchers: outline a clear audit trail supporting the traceability of the research; and methodological documentation of the research contains detail of procedures and consequent decisions. Adhering to these criteria enables readers to understand the reasons behind decisions made, as well as allowing readers to assess the dependability of the findings (Ahmed, 2024). The final criteria is confirmability, which assumes that researchers: engage in professional dialogue with experts and colleagues to discuss aspects of the research to reduce researcher bias; take part in the research review of the findings to confirm their accuracy; engage in reflexivity by keeping a reflective journal to record their personal thoughts and reflections. Adhering to these criteria enables readers to determine the extent to which the findings are shaped by the participants including minimising any researcher bias. Thereby increasing the objectivity and accuracy of findings through greater transparency (Ahmed, 2024).

The four criteria that Lincoln and Guba (1985) state for trustworthiness within qualitative research – credibility, transferability, dependability and confirmability were evident within my own research study. Credibility was evident as I was a familiar face for prospective participants, due to working part time in Rainbow ELC during the data collection phase of the research. This gave me the opportunity to build a rapport with

both parents and staff within Rainbow ELC. Although as discussed previously in Chapter One, I had a personal interest in transition, I tried hard to acknowledge my own personal bias and knowledge of transition and any influence that this had on the research study and the lens that it was being viewed through. Therefore, I was open to data, and its subsequent implications, even if it did not align with my personal views. However, transferability was only partially evident within this research because as the research was a case study, the findings discussed in Chapter Five were pertinent to the context, time and participants involved. Although settings similar to the ones involved with this research would be able to look at the research context and decide whether any of the findings may in some ways relate to their own context. Additionally, the majority of the recommendations discussed in Chapter Eight are relevant to the EY and Primary sectors within Scotland and could be used to spark professional dialogue within their own context. The third criteria dependability, was evident within this research, as there has been a transparent description of data collected and associated decisions made. This was supported by the description, explanations and justifications of the methodology and data collection methods employed (Hammarberg, Kirkman and de Lacey, 2016), discussed throughout this chapter. There has been traceability and transparency of the data collected, with a full list of data collected included in *Appendix 24 – Data Timeline*. The number of parent participants giving similar responses to the questions during their individual interview, would also support the dependability of the research. Furthermore, when reporting the findings in Chapter Five, direct quotes were used also supporting again the traceability and transparency of the research. However, aspects of dependability discussed by Lincoln and Guba (1985) were not evident within this research. This included the impossibility of participants checking the accuracy of the findings, as I no longer had contact with the participants and settings involved in the research, although the data were shared with both members of the SG and my research supervisors as described above. The final criteria, confirmability, has been evident behind the scenes, through regular discussions with supervisors who supported and challenged my interpretation of the collected data, in order to minimise/challenge any personal biases. Furthermore, I maintained a personal journal, allowing me to reflect on all aspects of the research process and any changes I would make if I were to repeat the research study again. Additionally, self-reflections of the participatory research approach are discussed in Chapter Seven.

4.6. Ethical Considerations

In any research, ethical principles need to be followed, with *'The British Education Research Association (BERA) Ethical Guidelines for Educational Research'* (BERA, 2024) having a set of research principles that are useful for researchers undertaking research within education. The BERA (2024) first principle highlights the importance of participant informed consent/right to withdraw, whereby the participant makes a voluntary decision to take part and has the right to withdraw, without giving a reason for withdrawing. The second principle, transparency, involves a researcher being open and honest about all aspects of the research. The third principle involves the use of incentives, whereby participation should not be encouraged through incentives e.g., monetary payment. The fourth principle involves giving consideration to potential harm arising from participation in research. This results in a duty of care towards participants, with the researcher recognising any associated risks to participants taking part in the research (including distress or discomfort) and planning for and sharing these with participants prior, during and after their participation. The fifth principle involves privacy, data storage and how researchers keep participants' data confidential and anonymous. The final principle relates to disclosure, and the requirement on the researcher to decide if confidentiality and anonymity should be maintained if something illegal comes to light during the research.

Within this research, all of the above principles from BERA (2024) were followed. Informed consent/right to withdraw was addressed within the participant information sheets (Appendices 5, 7, 8 and 10). These stated why participants were invited to participate, what their participation would involve and participant right to withdraw up to two weeks after participating without giving a reason. A consent form (Appendices 6, 9 and 11) was also signed by each participant, indicating their consent to take part. Moreover, to confirm each participant's consent, prior to each interview/FG/SG meeting, verbal consent was sought from all participants. Transparency was acknowledged through being open and honest with participants about the research and giving an opportunity prior to interview/FG for participants to ask questions about the research. In addition, it was explained prior to each interview/FG that all data would be anonymised before being shared with members of the SG. However, within the SG or FG themselves there was no opportunity to anonymise the information being

given by either the members of the SG or the participants of the FG as these all took place in-person and everyone knew what each other was saying. Furthermore, ethical approval to undertake this research was granted from both the UWS Ethics Committee and the Local Authority via a gatekeeper (Head of Education). Regarding principle three, no incentives were given to any participants to persuade them to take part – participants made a personal decision to take part/not take part. For principle four, that no participant would come to harm, it was decided in conjunction with the SG, that the name of the group was changed from action group to SG, as we were unlikely to action (take forward) all ideas from the collected data. Consideration was also given, that parent members of the SG group may have felt upset if all their ideas were not taken forward or considered. Moreover, when undertaking individual parent interviews, contact details of the DHT at Blue Primary School were provided, in the event any of the parents wanted to talk in more detail about issues discussed. To maintain the fifth principle, privacy, all participants were informed that there was no requirement to share anything that they felt invaded their privacy. Additionally, pseudonyms were given to all participants prior to the transcription phase of the data. All individual interviews were solely conducted by me, with all face-to-face interviews taking place within a private room. Furthermore, at all FG or SG meetings, participants were asked not to share information discussed with colleagues/other parents. All collected data were transcribed solely by me, anonymised prior to sharing and stored securely on the UWS One Drive. For the final principle, disclosure, all participants were informed that as a local authority employee, I was duty bound to share anything disclosed that I felt needed to be taken further with Head of ELC or Head Teacher.

4.7. Conclusion

This chapter has discussed the axiology, ontological and epistemology stance adopted within the research - to support the promotion of parental voice and involvement of parents/carers in their child's education journey through an interpretivist paradigm and social-constructivism stance. It has focussed on the methodology for the research, and justified the use of an exploratory case study, the positionality of the researcher, how a participatory research approach was adopted within this education-based research study, and power issues related to adopting this approach. The chapter has

also discussed the sampling of participants and why purposive sampling was adopted. Additionally, it has discussed why qualitative research methods were employed, through the use of FGs, semi-structured interviews and reflective notes, to gather participant responses, helping to address the first research question and associated aims. The chapter has explained the direct involvement of the SG within the adopted participatory research approach. It has also discussed how the transcription and analysis of the data were undertaken, alongside the trustworthiness of the research to stand up to scrutiny from other researchers. The chapter concluded by outlining the ethical considerations that were adhered within this research study.

Chapter Five: Findings

5.1. Introduction

This chapter outlines the findings from the data collection phase of the research discussed in detail in *Chapter Four: Methodology*. It will address the four aims of the research study, highlighting relevant and thought-provoking themes uncovered during analysis of the data.

5.1.2. Contextualisation

Prior to discussing the findings, it is important to provide contextual information about the parent participants who took part in this research. This background information sourced from the interviews/membership of the steering group (SG) assisted the findings of this research. A summary of this information can be found in *Table Two – Parent Participants*.

Parent Interviews			
Parent	Is their child male or female?	Is this their first child to attend primary school?	Was the parent interviewed before or after the transition talk?
Parent 1	Male	Yes	Before
Parent 2	Male	Yes	Before
Parent 3	Female	Yes	Before
Parent 4	Female	Yes	Before
Parent 5	Female	Yes	Before
Parent 6	Female	Yes	Before
Parent 7	Male	Yes	After
Parent 8	Female	Yes	After
Parent 9	Female	No	After
Steering Group			
SP1	Female	Yes	N/A
SP2	Male	Yes	N/A
SP3	Female	No	N/A

Table Two – Parent Participants

As part of contextualisation, it is helpful to briefly summarise the transition programme that children and their parents had the opportunity to participate in prior to their child starting Blue Primary School in August 2023. For the children, the transition programme started in January 2023 and continued through to June 2023, with various planned opportunities regularly provided by the Transition Coordinator to support familiarity of Blue Primary School. These included exploring the classroom, taking

part in school assemblies, visiting the school library for a story and meeting/spending time with their buddies (older children who would assist the nursery children when they start primary school). The DHT also spent time visiting the children at Rainbow ELC. In June 2023, the children attended two planned induction sessions on two consecutive days. The first took place at the same time as the transition talk for parents. During these induction sessions, the children spent time in their classroom with their new teacher and other children who would be in their Primary One class in August.

For parents, the transition programme involved them receiving emailed information about Blue Primary School and attending the first induction day. Before attending the transition talk on the first induction day, parents had the opportunity to escort their child to their classroom, briefly meeting their child's new teacher. At the transition talk, the Head Teacher shared information deemed important for parents to know. The first induction day concluded with parents accompanying their child to the dining hall to watch/assist their child experience the school lunch routine for the first time. The second induction day required the children to be dropped and collected after the induction session had finished.

5.2. Findings Related to Research Aim One

The first research aim investigated whether 'the communication methods employed by both the ELC and the main feeder primary school for parental engagement during the transition process are meeting parent needs and if not, what alternatives could be used'.

At first glance, all nine parents interviewed appeared satisfied with the different general communication methods currently employed by Rainbow ELC. The parents indicated that the nursery communicated using a Nursery App, with additional communication via a Sway, telephone calls or letters. However, when specifically discussing communication about transition, Parents 4, 5 and 9 stated they had issues receiving

information about transition opportunities their child would be/had been taking part in, with one parent stating:

I didn't even know that she had met her [buddy] until I had tried to get it out of [child's name]. It would have been nice to have known that she had met her buddy and [who] her buddy is.

[Parent 4]

This suggested that although Parent 4 received communication about transition, the information was not in sufficient detail or received in advance of the events to keep them abreast of what opportunities their child was being given.

Further to this, another parent commented about issues he had experienced being informed about transition events, as he appeared to be finding out about these afterwards:

Probably could get more awareness about that timetable and the times that Rainbow ELC have been taking them across, because trying to speak to your young one [by asking] 'What did you do today?' 'Oh, I did this, I did that'. They don't tell you much. It would be good to see [the timetable] for the next three months.

[Parent 9]

This parent's response suggested that the issue of receiving transition information after events had occurred was a concern for these three parents. However, when speaking to the Transition Coordinator at Rainbow ELC about whether a timetable was available, she indicated that all parents had been sent a six-month transition timetable via the Nursery App in December, giving dates for events/visits with Blue Primary School. The transition timetable was discussed by Parent 7 who stated, 'they gave us a rough timetable back in December, telling us each week what will be happening'. Furthermore, Norma (Team Leader (TL)) during the ELC Staff Focus Group (FG) discussion commented, 'All the dates, coming up, we'll put reminders on [the Nursery

App]', with this point agreed by the other ELC staff attending the FG. This suggested a possible issue with receiving information too far in advance of transition opportunities happening, placing importance on the information being received or actually receiving the timetable if parents do not have the Nursery App. It might also suggest that some parents may not be transferring the transition event information onto a calendar to remind them of upcoming transition opportunities, leading them to forget about upcoming events.

When referring directly to the communication with Blue Primary School so far, Parent 9 stated:

Since we've registered in January and February there's not been too much. It was more you'll hear from us nearer the time'.

[Parent 9]

The above suggests that he felt he had not received a lot of information about Blue Primary School. However, during a discussion with the DHT about information being sent out to parents, she stated that the initial confirmation email of their child's place at Blue Primary School, sent out in January/February, contained lots of information for parents to read. This emailed information was also discussed by Parent 7, who commented that he had received an email from the primary school containing a school handbook. This confirmed that email had been used to communicate directly with new parents.

It was interesting to note that different communication methods had been used by Rainbow ELC and Blue Primary School to engage parents during the transition programme. The communication methods currently adopted by Rainbow ELC for transition were split into digital communication - Nursery App and traditional communication methods – face-to-face. For Blue Primary School, digital communication was mainly via an introductory email in January/February, with open access to the school website or traditional communication, in the form of a letter, given

out in May via Rainbow ELC. The viewpoints of participants of these methods and the actual effectiveness of each method varied. To address aim one and whether the communication methods were all in fact suitable, the communication methods discussed during the individual interviews and FGs are split into two areas - digital communication and traditional communication.

5.2.1. Digital Communication

This section discusses the different digital communication tools currently used by both Rainbow ELC and Blue Primary School to communicate directly with parents - the Nursery App and School App, emails and Blue Primary School Website.

5.2.1.1. The Nursery App and School App

Through the individual parent interviews, it became apparent that the Nursery App, which can be downloaded to a mobile phone, was the main tool used by Rainbow ELC to communicate with parents - eight out of the nine parents interviewed spoke about having the Nursery App on their mobile phone. The Nursery App can be set up by parents to receive notifications direct to their mobile phone from Rainbow ELC. This includes general reminders, links to external information, emails and letters. Parent 5 discussed the Nursery App as being 'informative' as 'it tells you what's happening in nursery'. However, as Parent 9 had chosen not to download the Nursery App to his new mobile phone he stated that he relied on his wife to relay information but acknowledged that this did not always happen.

Interestingly, during the ELC Staff FG Norma (TL) spoke about reasons why Rainbow ELC had introduced the Nursery App:

[parents] weren't accessing emails, weren't providing email addresses, or weren't [looking at their emails] and the app is more instant.

[Norma]

This suggests reasons for Rainbow ELC changing their main communication with parents from emails to the Nursery App. Keeping parents informed about what is happening/will be happening was important, and the introduction of the Nursery App allowed this to happen. However, when asking parents if they had any issues with the communication with Rainbow ELC, both Parents 2 and 4 briefly discussed issues they had with the Nursery App, while Parent 5 spoke in detail about this:

I don't get them [messages] when they come or I'm not able to read them when they come, but I get notifications that they're there and I'll go back to them. If it was something that they were sending out that was an immediate announcement I probably wouldn't get it through the app or the email because I can't tap into it straight away [when working].

[Parent 5]

These viewpoints suggest possible issues with the Nursery App, in particular notifications being sent out and received on the parent's mobile phone in a timely manner. Although the nursery sends notifications to parents, it appeared from a few parents interviewed, that they were not being received or cannot be accessed instantly, possibly impacting on the parent's ability to keep abreast of what has been happening at Rainbow ELC. However, parents 2, 5 and 8 stated that they received a phone call if any communication from Rainbow ELC required an immediate response.

Although issues with the Nursery App were brought to my attention by individual parents, it appears that the ELC staff FG participants were not aware of issues with the Nursery App, as no issues were raised during the ELC Staff FG. Additionally, Parent 3 who appeared to have knowledge of this type of app, suggested it be used as a two-way communication tool allowing parents to communicate directly with Rainbow ELC. She suggested the Nursery App could be used 'as a way of messaging them [Rainbow ELC] directly ... to let them know of absences.' This point appeared to suggest that the app was capable of additional benefits for both the nursery and the parents, which at that time had not been explored.

Parents 7 and 8, interviewed after attending Blue Primary School parent transition talk, commented that they had downloaded the School App after being notified by the Head Teacher of its availability. Interestingly, Parent 9 who had attended the talk, did not mention the School App during his interview. The School App was similar to the Nursery App, but to receive notifications parents were required to register using the access code shared by the Head Teacher at the transition talk. This was different from the Nursery App, which had open access to anyone with the log in code. In addition, the school version gave parents the option to receive whole school and/or certain classes information. The School App according to the Head Teacher, was primarily used to communicate directly with parents. Anita, a future Primary One teacher, advised during the future Primary One teachers FG that the School App was used to send out announcements and give direct access to newsletters via a link. The two parent representatives (SP1 and SP2) attending the final SG meeting openly discussed the School App, which they had been informed about at the HT transition talk and had since downloaded. Both stated the benefits of having it, but shared that they did not wish to receive *all* notifications being sent out. The DHT, who attended this final SG meeting suggested that parents should only receive notifications for Primary One until their child started school in August, when notification for the full school could be set. The points raised about the School App has shown that familiarity through the use of the same app that parents are already familiar with was beneficial. However, with the School App having more options to manage notifications, the advice from the DHT about receiving only Primary One notification was helpful and one that SP1 and SP2 stated could have been shared by the Head Teacher at the transition talk.

5.2.1.2. Emails

Both the ELC staff FG participants and individual parents confirmed that emails had been the primary communication method used by Rainbow ELC to communicate with parents prior to the introduction of the Nursery App in August 2022. When questioned specifically about communication with *Blue Primary School*, Parents 4, 6, and 7 commented that, as prospective parents, they had all received a personalised welcoming email, which included an attached letter to both the parent and child about starting school.

Parent 6 indicated that she had also received a transition document as part of the welcome email which:

Answered questions about school meals, pick up and drop off. It had quite a lot of information that I probably wouldn't even have thought of.

[Parent 6]

However, Parent 9 (as discussed in section 5.2.) indicated that he had not received information since the introductory email which was sent out to parents in January/February. For this parent, there appeared to be a lack of information between this initial information received via email and the transition talk in June. Although when speaking to the DHT of Blue Primary School, in lieu of attending the second SG meeting, she confirmed that information was sent out within the welcome email in January/February. This included a Sway with lots of information about the primary school, the school handbook and video tour of the primary school. According to Parent 8, the Head Teacher during the transition talk, reminded everyone of the information that had been emailed as part of the January/February welcome email. However, the comments from the parents interviewed, suggest inconsistencies in recollection of the information the welcome email from Blue Primary School contained. This includes the quantity of information received or the amount of information contained within one email. Possibly leading parents to not opening all the attachments or not actually receiving the email in the first place, if the wrong email address had been submitted on the enrolment form.

5.2.1.3. Blue Primary School Website

Another source of transition information for some of the parents was Blue Primary School website, which Parents 1, 2, 5 and 6 stated they had accessed for a variety of reasons. Parent 1 used the website to decide whether she wanted her child to attend Blue Primary School, a non-catchment primary school, while Parent 2 wanted to see what the school looked like.

Whilst Parent 5 had a long list of information from the website she hoped to find:

What the uniform is ... information about how the first day is going to look. So, a bit of info as a prospective parent, just a wee section on the website to tell us what to expect and what to be preparing our young person to expect.

[Parent 5]

Unfortunately, Parent 5 stated that she was unable to find this information on the website. These points discussed by Parents 1, 2, and 5, indicate that parents had tried to access information on the website, in order to better understand the primary school, enabling them to support both their child and themselves during this period of change, and prior to the transition talk in early June. Interestingly Parent 7 although not having accessed the website, commented that:

You know with the parent hat on, you want to know everything that's going on. But given the line of work that I'm in, I am very conscious that there shouldn't be lots and lots of stuff on a publicly accessible website. General information like school schedules, the timetable, what the holidays are, newsletters that aren't containing much in the way of personal information are absolutely fine, but anything over and above that, I wouldn't necessarily like to see in a school publicly accessible and indexed website, because it's far too easy for that information to be picked up on by people who have no need to know the information.

[Parent 7]

The above comment offered a helpful insight into a school website and what it might (or might not) contain, indicating the importance of the transition talk and School App for parents, so that information could be shared in a safe manner.

5.2.2. Traditional Communication Methods

This section discusses the traditional communication methods currently used by both Rainbow ELC and Blue Primary School to communicate directly with parents - letters and face-to-face.

5.2.2.1. Letters

As discussed within sections 5.2.1.1. and 5.2.1.2. the Nursery App was now the main communication tool used by Rainbow ELC, with email used by Blue Primary School to communicate directly with the parents of Rainbow ELC. Other than this, on one occasion a letter about the forthcoming induction days in June was handed out on behalf of Blue Primary School via Rainbow ELC to parents. During the individual interviews when discussing any issues parents had with receiving communication from Blue Primary School, Parent 7 stated that he never received the induction letter and only found out about the induction days through a Facebook page (established by a parent at Rainbow ELC). He indicated that this was not an issue as he still received the information, and theorised that his child's pattern of attendance at nursery could have been the reason for not receiving the letter. The issue of a child's pattern of attendance and receiving letters from Rainbow ELC, was echoed by Parent 4 whose child attended five mornings. Parent 4 stated, 'When its paper obviously I can't get that until maybe I'm in the next morning'. Whilst these points suggested issues with receiving letters, a couple of other parents commented that letters were good to receive. This included Parent 9 who commented '[letters] usually go on the fridge'. As a collective, the parents' acknowledged letters were few and far between, as digital tools had taken over as the primary communication method to parents.

5.2.2.2. Face-to-Face

Parent 9, who did not have the Nursery App, relied on face-to-face discussions with nursery staff and verbal reminders during drop off/collection and found these beneficial. However, he stated that this information was not always given in advance of a transition event. This point was echoed by Parent 4 who commented:

When we pick her up or drop her off, they might say, oh she was over at the school today. I don't always know in advance that they're maybe going, but I usually find out that day or the next day in the morning depending, who has picked her up.

[Parent 4]

This appears to reinforce the importance of keeping parents informed about transition visits, even retrospectively, although advance notification was preferred. During the ELC staff FG, Lynsey (EYP) acknowledged the importance of face-to-face contact when speaking to parents about what was happening in the nursery.

The importance of face-to-face opportunities for parents provided by Blue Primary School, during the transition programme was discussed by Parents 7, 8, and 9, who were interviewed *after* attending the transition talk. Parent 9 stated that the transition talk, 'was good as it gave me a good opportunity to understand [the school] layout [and] a bit of background'.

Whilst Parent 8 reflected:

It was really good. Everyone was welcoming and so attentive with the children. I was speaking to a couple of them on the day, in fact, on the first day we were there.

[Parent 8]

Further to this, Parent 7 also acknowledged how he valued the opportunity to engage directly with the school staff:

The actual face-to-face yesterday has definitely been the most effective, it's nice to get stuff in advance and you'll be able to read it at your leisure, but it's not as engaging as when you actually get to see someone in reality. I mean, video call would probably be fine as well, it's about the human interaction.

[Parent 7]

These comments emphasised the importance of giving parents the opportunity to engage in face-to-face communication with Blue Primary School and meeting the staff who work there. This provided parents with an opportunity to speak to staff who would be responsible for supporting and looking after their child within school. However, Parents 5 and 6, who had yet to attend the transition talk, felt the timing of the

forthcoming transition talk could have been better for working parents, with the possibility of an evening time slot - either face-to-face or online - being offered. Detailed discussion on parental engagement opportunities will be discussed within section 5.3, and barriers to taking part within section 5.4.

5.2.3. Additional 'Informal' Method of Communication

Interestingly during the individual interviews, additional information about transition events between Rainbow ELC and Blue Primary School for Parents, 2, 6 and 7 came from an alternative source. The parents discussed that information came from a Facebook page, set up independently by a parent of a current nursery child, who was also taking part in the transition programme at Rainbow ELC. This suggests that, for these parents, there was difficulty receiving information directly from Rainbow ELC or Blue Primary School about the transition opportunities taking place-

5.2.4. Communication with Parents at Local Authority Level

As discussed in section 2.3.4., there are specific local authority protocols when enrolling a child for primary school, which are currently completed online and include the option to submit a placing request. There appears to be a lack of understanding of the school registration protocol, as Parent 1 commented about the placing request she submitted for her son to attend Blue Primary School as opposed to the catchment primary school:

We had no communication with [primary school] until three or four days before they were having an open day. We knew nothing and then, once he got his place, we've had lots of stuff from Blue.

[Parent 1]

The above suggests that the parent either had not been made aware when making a placing request that no communication with either the catchment or placing request primary school is permitted until the placing request had been approved or denied by the local authority. Alternatively, it might suggest that this parent had not read information supplied by the local authority about this protocol. Further to this, Parent

4 who was within the catchment for Blue Primary School commented:

I got the welcome email at the very start to say that she'd been accepted which I was quite happy with, it's not set in stone even though I'm in the catchment - there's that many kids.

[Parent 4]

The above appears to indicate that Parent 4 had not been made aware during the online enrolment process that their child would automatically get a place at their catchment primary school. However, within this local authority I was advised that all children who enrol for their local primary school should be given a place in that primary school if they enrol during the January enrolment week. These two points appear to suggest issues with communication at local authority level regarding the process for starting school and the placing request protocol, as well as when parental engagement with the primary school their child is going to commence. The local authority enrolment process and placing request protocol are information that parents may benefit from knowing, especially when it involves a first child starting primary school. It is important to note that prior to Covid-19, parents who wanted to put a placing request to an alternative primary school would have been informed during the in-person enrolment at their catchment primary school about this protocol. However, as the form is now completed online, parents either do not read all the supplementary information about placing requests before submitting the request or are not informed of the protocol at time of applying. This again brings to the fore the understanding of the protocol when no one is available in-person to explain the restraints on attending transition events for both child and themselves until the outcome of the application is known. During the in-person enrolments a member of the senior leadership team would have been able to ensure that the parents were fully aware that they would not have contact with their catchment or placing request primary school until the outcome of the placing request is known.

5.2.5. Summary of Key Findings for Aim One

Key findings for the first aim suggest just under half of the parents appear satisfied with the way both Rainbow ELC and Blue Primary School communicate with them,

including using a mixture of digital and traditional communication tools. However, there appear to be some technical issues, particularly with the Nursery App that Rainbow ELC staff are unaware of. Furthermore, one parent who does not currently have the app, relies on face-to-face discussions with nursery staff to keep abreast of transition information. Additionally, some information regarding transition does not appear to have been received by some of the parents prior to transition opportunities taking place, resulting in parents using alternative sources to find the necessary information. Finally, the face-to-face transition talk for the parents appears to have been beneficial, as acknowledged by Parents 7, 8 and 9 who were all interviewed after this event occurred.

5.3. Findings Related to Research Aim Two

The second research aim was ‘to identify parental engagement opportunities that parents would like to be involved in during their child’s transition to primary school’. Overall, all the parents interviewed appeared happy to be involved in the transition programme that their child was currently part of. When discussing possible parental engagement opportunities, a range of suggestions were given, and these will be discussed below.

5.3.1. Getting to Know Blue Primary School

Parents 1 to 6 who were interviewed prior to taking part in the parent transition talk in June, at Blue Primary School, had not had the opportunity in person to visit the primary school. The eagerness for some of the parents to see round the full primary school was evident, with Parent 1 stating:

It would be interesting to go round and see exactly where he's going so that you can put a picture to it.

[Parent 1]

This point was reiterated by Parents 3 and 5, with one parent stating:

I have only ever been in the building when I went to vote there. I haven't actually been in the building for any reason to do with [child's name].

[Parent 5]

This opportunity was something that half of these six parents wanted to experience. Having the opportunity to see round their child's new school was also discussed by Lynsey (EYP) during the ELC Staff FG:

I know talking to a few parents who are a bit apprehensive about [their child] going to different schools and it would be nice for them to be able to see the school.

[Lynsey]

The lack of opportunity for parents to visit the school prior to the parent transition talk was also raised during the future Primary One teachers FG, when Karen discussed the permanent loss of Blue Primary School Nursery Class in 2021 and the impact this had on familiarity with the school building for both new children and parents:

Parents were at the nursery and about the school. They could see the P1 playground, the classes. There was a lot more familiarity about the building itself.

[Karen]

All three future Primary One teachers acknowledged that, although the children transitioning to Blue Primary School were in and out the building, the parents were not getting that opportunity due to the primary school having lost the nursery class and direct contact with future parents. When discussing comments from the parents about not having had the opportunity to visit the primary school with the DHT, she stated that a link to a pre-recorded video of what the inside of the primary school building looked like had been included as part of the welcome email. Interestingly this was something that Parent 5 had suggested could have been sent to parents, appearing to indicate that Parent 5 had not received the video or could not recall seeing it as part of the

welcome information. Furthermore, none of the parents, when questioned about their knowledge of Blue Primary School, discussed the welcome information that had been emailed out in January/February, even though Parents 4, 6 and 7 had acknowledged receiving the welcome information from Blue Primary School (see section 5.2.1.3.). This may suggest that the parents who had received and read this information did not constitute this information as knowledge about the school.

When questioned about her knowledge of the primary school, Parent 5 commented 'I don't know enough to make myself so assured that I can reassure [child's name]'. This particular parent also identified that having suitable knowledge about the school would allow her to support both her child and herself during the transition process. Further to this, Parent 6 commented:

I feel like with her being my first. I don't know what to expect. I'm nervous for her so I want to know as much as possible to help her as much as possible.

[Parent 6]

The above indicates, from a parent perspective, the importance of a parent having their own concerns about their child starting primary school addressed in order that they can then reassure their child.

The timing of the parent transition talk at the start of June negatively impacted on Parent 5, who discussed her preference for having the information to be shared at the transition talk earlier, thereby allowing her to answer any questions her child had asked about the transition to primary school.

Information from the handouts the parents attending the transition talk would receive, was shared during the future Primary One teacher FG by Karen:

A lot of written stuff ... a booklet and information sheets about us. A PowerPoint and [HT] talks them through everything they should know for coming in August.

[Karen]

This highlights the amount of information in written form to be received by the parents. However, as Parents 1 to 6 had not yet attended the transition talk when interviewed, they talked about the information they wanted included during the transition talk. The parents also shared their interest in escorting their child to school during the induction sessions – giving them the opportunity to see their child's classroom, meet the teacher and observe their child taking part in the primary school lunch experience, with Parent 4 commenting:

It's the Tuesday morning, half nine to half eleven or twelve, but they get their lunch. We're getting told which teacher and should see their classroom. They'll go through the uniform. They're going through everything in the morning.

[Parent 4]

During the interviews with the six parents prior to the transition talk, they all intimated their determination to attend, even though it was a morning event. Interestingly, the points the parents wanted to be discussed as part of the transition talk were confirmed as having been addressed by Parents 7, 8, and 9 who were interviewed after attending the transition information talk. Parent 7 discussed in detail the PowerPoint given by the HT. He also stated that when the HT asked for any questions, no one asked any. This appeared to indicate that the PowerPoint presentation had provided the parents all the information they required.

Further to this, Parent 9 commented:

We got the big pack from them - it contained information. A video when we were in the meeting as well, so reasonably good. It gave me a good opportunity to understand the layout [and] a bit of background. We got to see the classroom, where they will be going,

where they will be hanging up their stuff, where they will be going, when they get into the school and stuff like that.

[Parent 9]

The above highlights the wealth of information shared during the transition talk. Parent 8 reinforced this point, stating that the information given by the HT was everything she needed to know, and that the welcome pack given out after the talk also contained the information the HT had discussed. It appeared that the amount of information given out contained information that some of the parents found valuable and insightful, but also having the written information meant that it could be consulted at a later date.

5.3.2. Establishing a Professional Relationship with School Staff

The importance of establishing relationships with school staff was discussed by Parent 1, who suggested a walk round the school would have given her the opportunity to 'click' with school staff and put faces to names that her son had talked about. Establishing a relationship with school staff was also discussed by Parent 7, who talked about the importance of the transition talk and induction day:

The staff were all exceptionally engaging. Very, very, very friendly. It's something you know as a parent really does set your mind at ease a little bit, when you can see these people and they're just really nice, really friendly, really welcoming. You kind of feel good that your child's going to be looked after.

[Parent 7]

The comment by Parent 7 suggested that this parent, at least, was grateful for seeing for themselves how the staff in the primary school were interacting with their child. The induction day/transition talk appeared to have a positive effect on the parent, as he felt more able to trust the staff after meeting them. Interestingly, Parent 1 commented that, for her, the relationship with the primary school staff had actually started prior to visiting the primary school, when she had received telephone communication and 'welcoming emails' that were not generic. This suggested that the relationship with school staff does not need to be face-to-face and that first impressions matter, regardless of the form these take.

As discussed previously in section 5.3.1., the future Primary One teachers explained the negative impact of losing the attached nursery class. They acknowledged that this had made it harder to establish a relationship between parents and the teachers. During their FG, they all discussed a positive impact of Covid-19 mitigations that had been introduced as part of the transition programme in May/June 2021. The transition programme during Covid-19 mitigations involved the Primary One teachers engaging directly with parents and children during outdoor transition opportunities. Karen noted:

The parents sat with them [children] as part of that activity. I think it was quite good just to be able to have that informal chat.

[Karen]

This reflection seems to value this alternative opportunity that the future Primary One teachers had undertaken, which allowed them time to begin to form a professional relationship with the parents and their child. Anita and Karen also spoke about current transition programme arrangements, where parents get to meet their child's teacher, when they drop them off and collect them during the transition days in June. However, they all acknowledged that the real relationship with the parents begins when the child officially starts in August, with Anita commenting:

[It] must be quite intimidating having your child go to start school, particularly when it's your first and not knowing what is really going on.

[Anita]

This led to the three future Primary One teachers' agreeing that more could be done with the *parents*, as they already did lots for the children, with different examples given of how this might be achieved. Anna reflected, 'They could have wee story afternoons, go to the burn, Bookbug...', with Karen adding:

Yeah, you could do a cup of tea in the natural play with management and us. Some mingling with the kids while others mingle [with] the adults and switch over. They could give each parent one opportunity. 'Here are the things that we're doing', and they could

sign up to help at one. Then you're getting to actually see each parent.

[Karen]

This suggested that the teachers were beginning to consider ways that their relationship with parents, even informally, could be developed prior to the children starting primary school in August. Some of these opportunities already involved the children, the only addition would be the parents attending. Parent 8, who was interviewed after the transition talk, pointed out that although she had attended the parent transition talk there could have been opportunities for more parent interaction with her child:

...The first day of the transition days, but maybe doing a wee activity with them or maybe a wee settling in day and mum and dad to come.

[Parent 8]

This specific point reiterates the one made by Karen, that the primary school could have more transition opportunities that involve parents. This may also reduce parent anxiety by allowing parents to observe their child's interaction with their new teacher.

Parent 8 also spoke positively about activities Blue Primary School had handed out following the induction talk. The welcome pack included home activities that parents could complete with their child - a going to school sticker book, a story book and a passport of information. The passport of information, which was to be returned to the primary school, gave parents the opportunity to communicate directly with their child's new teacher, including specific information about their child that they wanted to share.

Finally, the value of maintaining the relationship with the ELC Transition Coordinator during the transition days was highlighted by Parent 8 who commented:

My child had a wee meltdown on her second day there and they were really good. Eilidh from here [ELC] went to check if she was alright and came back to me to let me know. So, I didn't have a meltdown either.

[Parent 8]

This suggested that, at least for this parent, the presence of familiar adults during transition events was important, not just for her child but for her, as the parent had not had the opportunity to establish a professional relationship with staff in the primary school prior to the transition talk.

5.3.3. Summary of Key Findings for Research Aim Two

Key findings of research aim two, suggest that parents want to feel part of their child's transition journey. This includes having information available to support both the child and parent through this transition period. The parents appear to want practical involvement, especially seeing things for themselves, including the opportunity for an earlier visit to Blue Primary School prior to June. In addition, while detailed information was given at the transition talk, *some* of the parents would have welcomed this information earlier.

Establishing a face-to-face professional relationship with the school staff was identified as important to some of the parents, but this was not possible until the day of the transition talk. The feedback from the three parents interviewed after the event emphasised the importance of involving them in the transition programme, with the parent transition talk addressing points raised by the six parents interviewed prior to this event. This talk was really valued by the parents for alleviating anxieties some of them had regarding their child starting school. However, *some* parents would have preferred the talk to have been earlier in the school year, giving them the opportunity to use the information, to support their child during the full transition programme. The future Primary One teachers also identified transition events that could include parents as an area for development. Finally, specific suggestions made by the parents included involvement in the children's planned transition events and opportunities to

get to know the teachers and staff who would be working with their child. Decisions made by the SG to address some of these parent engagement opportunities can be found in *Appendix 23 – What to Take Forward*.

5.4. Findings for Research Aim Three

The third research aim sought ‘to identify any barriers to parental engagement during their child’s transition from ELC to the main primary school and how these might be overcome’. Three overarching themes were identified - timing of events; advance notification of events; different care arrangements. Parent 5 suggested possible solutions to some of the identified barriers and these are also discussed within this section.

5.4.1. Timing of the Transition Talk

The parent transition talk, that all parents whose children were transitioning to Blue Primary School were invited to, took place on a Tuesday morning at the start of June from 9.30am-11.30am. The timing appeared to be a potential barrier to participation, for Parents 5 and 6, as both parents reiterated this point at various points in their interviews, with one parent commenting:

I would say the timing just needs to be more considerate for full time working parents because I'm not obviously the only one that's going to miss all of these things coming up.

[Parent 6]

Further to this, Parent 5 commented:

I work school hours, and I can't just pop back [as] I'm quite far away. It's just fortunate that I've got some time back to take [to attend induction talk].

[Parent 5]

This potential barrier was also discussed by Parent 1, who pointed out that in order to attend the parent transition talk she needed to take annual leave. Both Parents 4 and 8 discussed that they would need to request time off from their employer to attend. Despite this, all nine parents felt it was imperative to personally attend the transition talk. The challenges related to the timing of transition opportunities was also discussed during the ELC staff FG. Norma (TL) discussed that parents whose children did not attend the ELC during any of the planned transition events were required to make separate arrangements for their child to attend. However, Katy (Parent and Child Support Worker) was sympathetic towards this possible barrier for working parents:

You can't obviously get all parents, some parents are working parents, and you will try and accommodate, but if you work 9-5 and you'll leave at 8:00 and don't get into six that is a challenge. If they can't get annual leave or take time off to come and do the inductions.

[Katy]

The above suggested the issue of timing, particularly for working parents who may need to make arrangements for someone else to take their child to any planned transition opportunities, or attend daytime events on their behalf, if the parent cannot arrange time off to attend.

5.4.2. Advance Notification of Events

Some of the parents commented about the need for advance notification of events, including Parent 4 who felt particularly strongly about the need for advance notice of transition events in order that time off work could be arranged:

As long as I'm getting to know what's happening or what they've got coming up, which isn't always the easiest. For certain things, obviously work understands we need to be there. As much notice as possible is always helpful for any parent that's working - so you can try and rearrange things.

[Parent 4]

As discussed in 5.4.1., Parent 1 needed to use her annual leave to attend the parent transition talk. Fortunately for Parent 8, if she knew of events coming up, her work agreed to give her the time off to attend. Therefore, there appears to be a reliance on employers of some working parents to grant time off to employees or authorise holidays for them to attend events that take place during working hours.

5.4.3. Different Care Arrangements

On the surface this theme did not link directly to transition, however, it became obvious that Parents 1, 3 and 5 being unable to drop off and collect their child regularly at Rainbow ELC was impacting on communication from staff about transition events that their child was involved in. Parent 1 commented:

I don't pick him up from nursery. It's my mum. But I know that they will say to my mum, he's been over at Blue today and he's not going to have any problems. You know, he's going over quite happily and so they're relaying it back to my mum and Mum's, obviously telling me so.

[Parent 1]

Further to this, Parent 5 commented:

I am relying on my parents to do that, so they're getting that constant communication with the nursery staff.

[Parent 5]

The points raised by these parents, indicated that the involvement of different family members dropping off/collecting their child at nursery, and sharing information given to that person by the nursery to be relayed to the parent, was a possible barrier to their parental involvement and engagement in their child's transition from nursery to primary school. Although, not directly shared by the parents involved in this study, there could have been issues for families that were co-parenting and information needing to be

shared in a timely manner. The impact of being unable to drop off and collect their child from nursery was causing working Parents 5 and 6 to worry that this lack of direct communication was going to continue when their child started primary school, as they were not going to be dropping off/collecting their child from primary school. Although as discussed within section 5.2.1.1., the School App and newsletters would be used to keep parents informed of what was happening at Blue Primary School.

5.4.4. Possible Solutions to Barriers to Parental Engagement with Transition Opportunities

Solutions to any of the barriers discussed in 5.3 were only suggested by Parent 5 who was a secondary teacher. She used her knowledge of the transition programme she was currently leading from primary school to secondary school to outline possible solutions to making transition events more accessible to parents including working parents. Her suggestions included: more evening opportunities, for example an information evening possibly held via Zoom. This offered a different perspective to that discussed within 5.2.2.2. where Parent 7 stressed the importance of face-to-face interaction. Interestingly the future Primary One teachers stated that, once the children started school, there was an evening curriculum information workshop for Primary One parents and that other events involving parents take place in the evening.

5.4.5. Summary of Key Findings for Aim Three

Barriers to parental engagement for working parents were evident for the parents who took part in this study. This included the time of day for the parent transition talk, where for some of the parents to attend, required their employer to agree time off. This in turn, relates to notification of the events taking place, with parents having sufficient advanced notice to ensure they can personally attend, and/or to arrange someone else to take their child to transition opportunities, if they are not attending Rainbow ELC during that time.

5.5. Policy Awareness

An interesting additional theme, related to staff knowledge of relevant policies, including those discussed in Appendix 1 – *Summary of Publications Relevant to Research Study*, arose when speaking with the future Primary One teachers FG. Participants were asked, ‘What advice and guidance about transition and parental engagement from ELC to primary school are you aware of and what do you use?’.

There was a long pause before Karen commented:

There's nothing specific to Primary One, nothing really that I'm aware of coming from the government or Education Scotland that we use. It's fed to us what we should be doing.

[Karen]

Anna added:

We probably have slightly less to do with the kind of plan and policy around transition. Management will kind of lead.

[Anna]

These points from the future Primary One teachers appeared to indicate that the teachers relied on the Senior Leadership Team to ensure that relevant policies about transition and parental engagement are followed.

When the same question was asked during the ELC staff FG, a member of the group stated:

We kind of put [our] own transition into place and created our own policy. We've got our own package we've created and [Transition Coordinator] is very much on top of all that, liaising with Blue more so than any other school.

[Norma]

These responses indicated that both groups of professionals appear to have no knowledge of current policies or guidance at national or local authority level relevant to either parental engagement or transition. Both the future Primary One teachers and ELC staff implied reliance on their respective leadership team to lead and keep them abreast of anything they need to know regarding transition and parental engagement.

5.5.1. Summary of Policy Awareness

It would appear that the future Primary One teachers rely on their school leadership team to lead, and make sure that what they are implementing for transition to primary school is following suitable guidance. Although it appears the opportunities being offered for parental engagement during transition are generally in line with relevant policies and guidance, even though none of the future Primary One teachers could directly name any. It also appears that the ELC staff rely on the Transition Coordinator, to ensure that Rainbow ELC are following the relevant policies and guidance within the area of transition.

5.6. Findings Related to Research Aim Four

The fourth and final research aim investigated ‘what we can learn about parent and professional partnerships from the participatory research approach of the study’. The findings for this aim focussed on the data collected from the three SG meetings - with a summary of this data collection found in *Appendix 25– Steering Group Data Collection*. This collected data included: minutes of the SG meetings completed by the researcher; reflective notes completed by participants; notes completed as part of activities during SG meeting two; activity from SG meeting three.

In order to respond to this aim, findings have been initially separated into parents’ and professionals’ thoughts and feelings about the participatory research approach, (as outlined in section 4.1.5.).

5.6.1. Parent Reflections on the Participatory Research Approach

Through both individually written and oral reflections about their membership of the SG and its associated tasks, the two parents (Steering Parent 1 (SP1) and Steering Parent 2 (SP2)) who participated in all three meetings, felt they participated collectively, alongside the other members of the SG when making decisions. One such opportunity was during the first SG meeting, where collectively all members decided the final interview questions to be used with parents, ELC staff and future Primary One teachers. SP1 stated in her reflective note after the first meeting:

I felt my views were listened to during the activity. The group worked together to decide which questions were most appropriate for the parental questions.

[SP1]

This comment suggested that for SP1 the importance of being involved in deciding the questions, the significance her opinion had on data to be collected and the general collegiate working with staff from both the ELC and DHT from Blue Primary School in making these decisions. Further to this, SP2's reflective note of the first SG meeting included the comment:

I felt like my views were listened to as much as everyone else. It was really interesting to hear other's opinions and has made me excited to head to the next stage of the transition with my child and excited for the next action group where we will hopefully be able to read the data collected. It's amazing to have this opportunity to be able to help this transition timeframe and maybe improve the following years in the future for other children. I felt the action group went really well. It was easy to discuss with everyone in the group as everyone was open and friendly.

[SP 2]

The comment by SP2 suggests that she valued the openness and friendliness of other members of the SG group and her own active involvement in making decisions. Her participation and involvement were also reflected in the written note she completed following the second meeting, where the data collected was shared with all SG members:

I liked how we took our time to add our bits in and were not influenced by others or rushed. I felt my input was read fairly and taken into account. I could also agree/add to other comments, and it was all anonymous.

[SP 2]

Additionally, both SG parents commented verbally during the third and final meeting how interesting it had been to be an active part in the decisions, with SP1 stating that participating in the SG had given her the opportunity for her 'voice to be heard'. This suggests that both parents felt they had a voice and actively participated in making decisions, that would ultimately impact on parents who would be involved in the transition programme the following year between Rainbow ELC and Blue Primary School.

The reflective notes completed by the researcher (me), after each of the SG meetings recorded my reflections on the parents' participation included:

I felt it was a very positive experience ... All parents voiced opinions, although parent 3 was quieter than everyone else.

[Researcher]

Interestingly Steering Parent 3 (SP3) withdrew after the first SG meeting, stating she was too busy and could no longer dedicate time to the group. In addition, SP2 had intimated from the outset that she was anxious about her son starting primary school and was delighted to be part of this group and was very eager to voice her opinion. She also commented within her reflective note of the second SG meeting that 'different/alternative perspectives welcomed' [SP2], acknowledging that everyone's views were welcome and that she was happy to voice her opinion and ideas.

5.6.2. Professional Reflections on the Participatory Research Approach – Head of ELC, Transition Coordinator and DHT

The professionals taking part in the SG also felt that membership of the SG was important, including working collectively with the parents to make decisions. This viewpoint was reflected in the Transition Coordinator's comment about deciding the interview questions I was to ask:

The activity itself was an excellent way for parents, staff from both establishments to work together and discuss questions that would be beneficial for everyone.

[Transition Coordinator]

The Transition Coordinator's point was supplemented by the Head of ELC who noted in her reflective note of the first SG meeting that, 'all participants were eager to take part and communicated their views in a friendly, respectful manner'. An additional point via email was made by the DHT in reference to this same meeting:

This morning was great! Thought it was very worthwhile as it can only strengthen our links with Rainbow ELC and parents.

[DHT]

These reflective notes suggest the value placed by the staff of Rainbow ELC and the DHT from Blue Primary School not only to work together but also with the parents. Participating in the SG also gave Blue Primary School staff direct access to parents of Rainbow ELC.

When considering the importance of all members of the SG working together to look at the anonymised interview data during the second SG meeting, and the value placed on this, the Transition Coordinator commented, 'The activity was very informative. It was an excellent way to get a wide range of views'. This point was also discussed by the Head of ELC, who reflected:

It was great to see the consultation and collaboration between the participants. Open and honest questions asked. It was good to look at the comments of others. Many were similar.

[Head of ELC]

At the third (final) SG meeting, all participants initially had the opportunity to take part in a couple of tasks. This included a task where all participants (including researcher) split into pairs. The participants were free to decide who to pair up with, and they independently decided upon parents together, ELC staff together, DHT and researcher together. Thereafter the SG members discussed their thoughts regarding the data they had selected for this task (*Appendix 22 – Steering Group Meeting Three Task (Collated Results)*), before collectively deciding for the following year, what to stop doing, keep doing, develop or introduce regarding communication tools used by Rainbow ELC or Blue Primary School and parental engagement opportunities offered during the transition programme. Collective decisions summarised in *Appendix 23 – What to Take Forward* included holding a meeting with the parents of the children transitioning to primary school prior to the transition events for the children beginning - although no specific date or time for this was discussed. It was also collectively agreed, that while the transition programme between Rainbow ELC and Blue Primary School was very good, both the Head of ELC and the Transition Coordinator felt that it was now important to discuss what involvement all the local primary schools would like from the children, staff and parents of children attending Rainbow ELC.

Other collective decisions specific to Rainbow ELC included ensuring that parents/carers were all aware of the different ways that Rainbow ELC currently communicated with them about what was happening, including upcoming transition opportunities. This included use of the Nursery App and the recently adopted Twitter, alongside the forthcoming Glow Blog website. It was also decided that, when issuing a reminder about the Nursery App, nursery staff would include reference to the benefits of family and friends downloading the Nursery App in order to keep up to date with events happening at Rainbow ELC, including transition opportunities.

Decisions were also collectively made by the SG for Blue Primary School regarding transition opportunities for parents. This included an agreement to introduce a walk round for parents and children prior to enrolment for primary school in January. Additionally, to support working parents, an informal information evening in November would be introduced so that parents could have a walk round, hear about the primary school and ask any questions to members of the Senior Leadership Team prior to making the decision if they wished their child to attend Blue Primary School. To keep parents informed, it was agreed by all that from January a monthly newsletter would be sent out detailing upcoming transition events. This monthly newsletter would contain any information that the DHT, who was responsible for transition to Primary One at Blue Primary School felt was important for parents to know or in response to questions that parents had asked. However, following the final SG meeting the DHT produced a template for the newsletter, sharing this via email with the Transition Coordinator and myself. In hindsight, this newsletter should also have been shared with the SG parents, as they represented the target audience and had been part of the SG who made the decision about the transition newsletter being introduced. Furthermore, as the data from some of the parents interviewed had requested information about the uniforms earlier than the transition talk in June, the SG agreed with the DHT that this information could be given as part of the welcome information emailed in January to parents. Finally, it was acknowledged by the DHT after reading the collected data from the parent interviews and discussing this data at the final SG meeting, that the school website was not meeting the needs of parents. In agreement with the rest of the SG, the information requested by the parents interviewed would be included when the website was next updated.

There were also a number of items that were already implemented by Blue Primary School as part of the transition programme to support parental engagement. However, from the collected data, it was evident that reminders were required. Opportunities included reminding parents about information that had already been sent out in January/February after registering their child for Blue Primary School. Further examples included informing parents about the School App that could be downloaded, prior to their child starting school, including setting the notifications to the full primary school or Primary One only.

Above all, the development of the SG and the members participation would not have been possible without the support of the parents and both Rainbow ELC and Blue Primary School management. From the outset, the Head of Rainbow ELC was an advocate for the participatory research approach. She was aware of the benefit to Rainbow ELC her participation would bring and the potential subsequent impact of enhancing both communication and parental engagement during transition. The DHT also recognised the importance of her participation in the SG, as it gave her the opportunity to strengthen links with the two parent representatives as well as Rainbow ELC. Finally, the Transition Coordinator acknowledged that being part of this group would help her to look at ways that the current transition programme could be amended and enhanced.

5.6.3. Summary of Key Findings for Research Aim Four

At the heart of this research, was the active participation of parents in having a voice and making decisions about the communication tools that could be used to support parental engagement during transition from Rainbow ELC to Blue Primary School. Although only two parent representatives attended all three SG meetings, it was evident through their reflective notes, that they had the confidence to make their voice heard. The two parents also appear to have found this a worthwhile experience, ensuring that their voice was heard and having an input into making decisions that would ultimately impact future transition programmes between Rainbow ELC and Blue Primary School. They appear to have felt empowered to make decisions alongside the professional members of the group.

The professional members of the SG acknowledged that, through participating and interacting with the parents, changes arising from the data could enhance the current communication tools used for parental engagement during the transition programme. It was also evident that both the parents and professionals acknowledged the benefits of working together and the parents being involved in making decisions collectively. This was only possible due to the willingness of the senior leaders from both setting to embrace this participatory approach. Finally, almost all the participants of the SG sustained membership of the group, and from their reflections regarding their

membership, all of them have found this partnership working beneficial. Collectively they appear to have felt empowered and involved to make decisions regarding how to enhance the current transition programme between the two settings further.

5.7. Conclusion

In conclusion, the key findings for aim one focussed on the communication tools both digital and traditional used to communicate with parents, with the Nursey App being the prominent way that Rainbow ELC communicated with parents. Although receiving notifications appear to be an issue for some parents. The parents appear to prefer face-to-face communication for gaining information about Blue Primary School. The key finding for aim two, which focussed on parental engagement, found that parents wanted to feel part of their child's transition journey and had a preference to be involved in practical opportunities. The key findings for aim three concentrated on barriers to parental engagement identifying timing of parent events and advance notification of events directly or indirectly involving them were paramount. Finally, the key findings for aim four, discussed what could be learnt about parent and professional partnership when using a participatory approach. Both parents and professionals found this partnership rewarding and beneficial when participating collectively in making decisions that affect them all. *Chapter Six: Discussion and Implications* will now discuss how the key findings of this research, compares to research, policies and guidance discussed in Chapter Two and current research discussed in Chapter Three. It will also discuss implications in relation to the findings discussed within this current chapter.

Chapter Six: Discussion and Implications

6.1. Introduction

Through undertaking this research study, a number of key findings were highlighted and explained in Chapter Five. This Chapter now analyses these findings and discusses implications of them, not only for the two settings involved in this exploratory case study but also the wider Early Years (EY) and Primary sectors in Scotland. The discussion includes how the findings of this study relate to the current policy and guidance, discussed in Chapter Two and recent informing academic research, discussed in Chapter Three. To aid transparency, the analysis and implications of the findings are discussed in relation to each research aim.

6.2. Discussion and Implications Related to Research Aim One

The key findings from research aim one – ‘to investigate whether the communication methods employed by both the ELC and the main feeder primary school for parental engagement during the transition process are meeting parents needs and if not, what alternatives could be used’ - indicated that digital communication was the predominant way that Rainbow ELC communicated with parents, through the recently introduced Nursery App. However, parents who either did not have the Nursery App or had technical issues using the app, needed to source alternative ways to find out the information that Rainbow ELC was posting on the Nursery App. These points were highlighted by parents taking part in my research. As a result, some parents relied on the Facebook page that a parent had established to keep parents abreast of what was happening at Rainbow ELC or relied on ELC staff to keep them informed of what was happening during the drop off and collection of their child. Interestingly, this was in line with the findings of Berkland and Hughes (2020) who identified that more than 10% of the parents in their research had general problems using electronic communications, although in my research a third of the parents interviewed stated they had issues with the Nursery App. This could have been affected by a parent’s ability to actually navigate the different sections of the app that notifications from Rainbow ELC could be uploaded to - a point raised by Parent 4. This point aligns with

Bates, Finlay and O'Connor Bones' (2021) conclusion that parents need suitable ICT skills to access digital communications. The parents of Rainbow ELC may also have been given access to technical support when the Nursery App was first introduced, however, as this was not discussed within the parent interviews or ELC Staff FG, this point could not be clarified. If training had not been offered, then this point would align with Head's (2020) findings that parents should be given training in how to navigate the digital platforms used by schools. Furthermore, in order to access the information from the Nursery App, parents need a data allowance on their mobile and the ability to connect to the internet. Moreover, for the parents who had technical issues with the Nursery App they could have approached the nursery staff for advice. However, they maybe did not feel comfortable about approaching the nursery and speaking to members of staff about the issue, due to perceived hierarchical power between the education professionals and themselves as parents. They may have felt that they should have been able to work out how the app works without additional support. Hence, they might have chosen to rely on the Facebook page for information that they could not get on the app.

Implications of the above for parents/carers of Rainbow ELC in relation to transition to Blue Primary School include, for example, a potential lack of parental engagement. This may lead to a child missing out on possible opportunities to build relationships with new peers and school staff if they do not attend the transition opportunities planned by Rainbow ELC/Blue Primary School. Furthermore, parents/carers may miss the opportunity to discuss these transition opportunities with their child, possibly elevating any anxieties that their child may have following these opportunities. Parents/carers may also miss reminders that may be sent out from Rainbow ELC via the Nursery App updating dates of transition events. There are also implications for the EY sector in Scotland including Rainbow ELC, who use a Nursery App to communicate with parents/carers. For example, they should be mindful that there is no guarantee that parents/carers have a mobile phone with data available to download and, thus, are able to read the information being sent out. This links with the 'cost of the school day' - an initiative currently being promoted by many local authorities in Scotland. It may be that alternative communication modes need to be considered, including making the communication available in print – a point advocated by Epstein

et al., (2019) - or making greater use of the face-to-face communication to parents/carers when dropping off or collecting their child.

The findings of my research, also suggest a lack of communication prior to some of the transition opportunities taking place. This particular point links directly to guidance from the '*National Improvement Framework: Parents Communication Plan A parent communication plan for the National Improvement Framework*' (Scottish Government, 2016) which states that information should be given as far in advance as possible. This is something that Rainbow ELC, Blue Primary School and both EY and Primary sectors in Scotland should consider as best practice when communicating with parents/carers. On the other hand, if information is given too far in advance and not repeated, closer to the event, this could also lead to difficulties.

Implications of this not happening, include parents/carers not having the opportunity to discuss and prepare their child for these transition events, especially if their child benefits from being prepared for any change to their daily routine. In addition, the child may be absent, possibly on holiday, if dates are not given in advance – particularly for events taking place in June. Furthermore, it may be hard for parents/carers to get time off work at short notice, if it is an event that parents/carers are invited to attend. There is also a question to be considered around the optimal time for events, particularly those directly involving parents/carers, which may be that one set time does not suit the needs of all parents. A point that should be considered not only for Blue Primary School but for the EY and Primary sectors in Scotland.

For Blue Primary School, the findings also revealed a lack of clarity amongst the parents as to the exact information initially received via email. It could be that the amount of information received at one time could have been overwhelming as too many attachments had been sent out attached to one email. Head (2020) emphasises this point, as the parents in her study decided that the amount of information being received via email from their child's primary schools could be overwhelming. Therefore, an implication of sending out too much information via one email, not only

for Blue Primary School but for both the EY and Primary sectors in Scotland, is that parents/carers might not open all the attachments if they become overwhelmed by the amount of information being received. As a result, they might not engage fully or understand the significance of all the information that has been sent out. Whilst not the case with the parents involved in my research, consideration should also be given to ensuring that parents/carers actually receive emails being sent out, thereby giving parents/carers the opportunity to take part in events involving them. A possible solution to sending lots of information via email is changing the way the transition information is presented for example, by distributing the information via video. Videos were used within Walsh, Romo and Jeon (2018) research, with the researchers stating that whilst the information was similar to other information already distributed, the videos were more accessible. Using videos could assist developing communication between the school, teachers, parents/carers and children, as key information regarding different aspects of transition could be shared via videos. A positive implication for Blue Primary School and the EY and Primary sectors in Scotland of using videos is that this mode of communication promotes inclusivity as subtitles could be provided in a variety of languages. However, the need to download videos could be affected by a connectivity barrier, as some parents/carers may not have the data allowance available on their mobile phone to download the videos. Possible solutions to this include parents/carers having access to the educational setting's guest Wi-Fi to download within the setting any large files, including video links that have been sent out via email or an app to their mobile phone, or via a borrowed setting laptop/computer/iPad.

Another key finding was that Blue Primary School relied on Rainbow ELC to distribute the transition induction day letters on Blue Primary School's behalf. As discussed within the findings, Parent 7 did not receive this important letter. Fortunately for this parent, he did find out from an alternative source about the event and ultimately attended. An implication for Blue Primary School is that if parents/carers do not receive the letter, then they will not be able to attend the transition talk. This would result in parents/carers not finding out relevant information about Blue Primary School, ways to support both their child and themselves through this period of change, or meet key school staff who will be responsible for their child. There is possibly a requirement

for Blue Primary School to look at alternative ways of sending out the letter. These include via email, by post or notification on the Nursery App used by Rainbow ELC.

In addition, the findings highlight that Blue Primary School would have benefitted from ascertaining the information that parents wanted to know about their child starting Blue Primary School. During the final SG meeting, the DHT acknowledged that the school website did not contain up to date information. This finding is in line with Gilleece and Eivers' (2018) Irish website research, whereby many of the websites analysed contained obsolete information, including outdated staff lists. Although not ascertained during the individual parent interviews or from the DHT whether any parents required information in a language other than English, it may be beneficial for information at least on the website to be available in the home languages used by the children and families. This would help with promoting inclusivity as well as parental engagement by keeping parents/carers abreast of what was happening during the transition to primary school. Thereby supporting Piller, Bruzon and Torsh's (2021) research that websites should contain information in languages used at home, as well as English. An implication of not providing information that parents/carers want is that the parents/carers may become anxious and worried if they do not have sufficient information when required. This links to Bérubé *et al.*'s findings (2018) and the importance of parents supporting both themselves and their child during a period of change.

The final finding regarding communication, was the parents' face-to-face opportunity to attend the transition talk, including the value placed on this opportunity to meet and speak to the staff who would be responsible for their child from August. This finding aligns with Griebeling and Gilbert's (2020) recognition of the importance of face-to-face transition opportunities involving parents. Moreover, this finding reinforces the positive impact of face-to-face communication. This contrasts with Woodhouse, Passey and Anderson's (2024) findings related to positive transition experiences happening through digital technologies. However, an implication of face-to-face meetings is that, if parents/carers cannot attend in person, they do not have the opportunity to ask questions. Consequently, the parent/carer may search for the information from an

alternative source which may give them the wrong information. Linking again to Bérubé *et al.*, (2018) and the importance of preparing both their child and themselves for the change that comes with starting school. Therefore, there may need to be provision made by Blue Primary School to cater for parents/carers who are unable to attend transition events in person. Moreover, for the parents who attended the transition talk, there were no opportunities to speak directly to their child's new teacher about their child, even informally. This contrasts with Leenders *et. al.*, (2019) where parents who were able to talk about their child, both formally and informally, developed two-way communication and a more trusting relationship. An implication of Blue Primary School not facilitating this may be that some parents/carers feel anxious about their child starting school, which could impact parents/carers being able to support their child during this period of change.

There are also a number of implications for both the EY and Primary sectors in Scotland. These include considering how education settings communicate with parents/carers, because if parents/carers are not receiving information or cannot readily access information that has been sent then they could miss transition events. This implication links to '*Learning Together Scotland's national action plan on parental involvement, parental engagement, family learning and learning at home 2018-2021*' (Scottish Government, 2018). The guidance states that parents/carers should be asked about the communication tools that work for them. This point reiterates the recommendation of both Berkland and Hughes (2020) and Head (2020) that parents should be consulted about the best ways to communicate with them, including digitally. Failure to communicate effectively with parents/carers about events may have long term effects on the relationship that settings have with parents and their active involvement in their child's education. Furthermore, consideration needs to be given to communicating with parents/carers who are not digitally literate so alternative ways to communicate key information should be available in order to promote inclusivity. This point resonates with Head's (2020) research where a primary school had not sent out information about how to use the digital software that the school used to communicate with parents. Additionally, to promote 'collaboration' and 'communication' two of the five 'C' s (Burns, 2019) to positive transition between ELC and primary schools during transition, it is vital that both the EY sector and Primary

sector staff involved directly in the transition between both sectors work together to support both the child and parents/carers during this period of change. It is therefore important that the ELC know important events and dates planned by the different primary schools, thereby allowing the ELC to support parents/carers including those who are having issues with digital technology as required.

Moreover, there are implications for the use of digital communication versus analogue communications with parents for both EY and Primary sectors in Scotland. For example, the integration of digital communication assumes that teachers/practitioners are digitally literate and able to use specific platforms to support communication with parents. This may not always be the case, with additional training being required to enhance teachers/practitioners' digital literacy skills to be able to communicate with parents. The same might equally be said for parents' digital literacy when accessing communications from their child's setting. However, this may be something that parents feel embarrassed about if they are unable to do. Additionally, parents may not have the confidence to contact the education setting to explain that they cannot navigate the digital technology being used to promote links between home and education setting. However, analogue communication including paper communications, for example through the use of newsletters, are not inherently 'better' than digital. Although they do provide parents with an artefact (a piece of paper as a reminder of communication), parents still need the commitment and capacity to engage with the communication (by whatever mode) and act upon it for example, attend an event or record a date on their calendar. An example of this would be Parent 9, who chose not to access the digital communication provided by Rainbow ELC via the Nursery App and preferred paper communication. Reflecting back on this, I am informed by my dual role as an employee and as a researcher. As an employee, I could see that the nursery seemed to be doing a good job of communicating with parents via the Nursery App - information was timely, consistent and available to all parents. However, from a researcher role it was evident that not all parents were being effectively communicated with via the Nursery App – as was the case for Parent 9. An implication of the aforementioned is that some parents may not become involved/engaged in their child's transition experiences because they have not been provided with the necessary information in a way that is accessible to them. The onus

is therefore on the education setting to respond appropriately to the needs of the parents using different communication platforms to promote parental engagement and parental involvement in their child's education.

Finally, the finding related to the lack of parents' understanding of the placing request protocol, has an implication at local authority level. The lack of knowledge of this protocol, may lead to parents/carers who have submitted a placing request to become worried when they hear of other parents/carers finding out about transition opportunities. As no transition opportunities can be provided until the placing request decision has been made, parents waiting on a placing request will only receive communication around transition after the request has been resolved. It is therefore important that these parents are informed of the timescale for the outcome of the application to be known and of the corresponding communication regarding transition opportunities. As with Bérubé *et al.*, (2018) note, it is important to ensure that parents, as well as children, are supported during the period of transition to primary school.

6.3. Discussion and Implications Related to Research Aim Two

The key findings for research aim two – 'to identify parental engagement opportunities that parents would like to be involved in during their child's transition to primary school' - suggested that parents wanted to be part of their child's transition journey, including the opportunity to take part in practical opportunities. This view is in line with guidance from '*Realising the ambition: Being Me*' (Education Scotland, 2020) which recommends that parents have the opportunity to actively take part in 'priming' events. In addition, it reinforces Tobin *et al.*'s (2022) findings that the parents in their study wanted to become more familiar with the new school environment. This supports the child and parent during this period of change, which Bérubé *et al.*, (2018) state is vital in helping a child cope emotionally with starting school. Furthermore, my research findings align with the active engagement of parents in the transition programme in Griebing and Gilbert's (2020), Merideth *et al.*'s (2022) and Fan *et al.*'s (2023) research, which recognised the benefits of engaging parents as active participants. The positive implication of this is that parents/carers are more relaxed and able to support their child through their transition to primary school.

Another related finding within my research, was that parents wanted to have the opportunity to physically see Blue Primary School for themselves prior to the transition talk in June in order to become familiar with the new environment and get to know some of the staff that their child had talked about. However, once the parents had taken part in the transition talk, they were able to see for themselves the school, new class teacher and meet key staff. The three parents interviewed after the transition confirmed feeling more positive about their child starting school. This aligns with the finding of Merideth *et al.*, (2022), whereby parents stated that attending the face-to-face sessions of the Kindergarten Family First Programme had a positive impact on them as they had a better familiarity with the school environment and key staff. It also linked to Tobin *et al.*'s (2023) findings and the importance of relationships for first time parents – which eight parents in my research were. An implication of failing to give parents/carers the opportunity to see and meet key staff alongside offering practical opportunities, may be that they are unable to offer sufficient support to their child during this period of change. Therefore, consideration needs to be given not only by Blue Primary School but also both the EY and Primary sectors in Scotland about how to actively involve parents/carers during the period of transition to primary school, including the possibility of a parent and child working together and having the opportunity to see round the new primary school and meet key staff. Research by OECD (2017) highlighted that positive transitions can have a lasting positive impact on the child. Furthermore, actively involving parents/carers and families, links to the policy '*Achieving Excellence and Equity – 2024 National Improvement Framework and improvement plan*' (Scottish Government, 2023), as schools must provide opportunities for parents/carers and families to be involved in their child's educational journey. However, it is important to acknowledge that to provide more parental involvement and parental engagement there is an impact on time for professionals and parents. To facilitate parental involvement and parental engagement in transition events time must be found for liaison between settings to agree suitable times and consideration must be given to spreading events over a period of time, especially if parents/carers were to require time off work to attend. Consideration would also need to be given within both the EY and Primary sectors to agree suitable dates and times that link in with children's individual pattern of attendance at the ELC. Adopting a long-term timetable would provide an overview of events/dates, reinforcing Bateson (2013) point that transition events should be planned and not ad-hoc. Providing increased

opportunities for both parents and children may increase parents' confidence in talking to their child about the new school and decrease anxieties and concerns of both. This is important as parents are preparing themselves as well as their child for the changing role (Bérubé *et al.*, 2018). A general implication of this is that if parent/carer anxieties are not addressed then these anxieties may pass onto the child, thereby affecting the child's ability to cope with the transition to school (STTCPPG, 2019).

The parents involved in my research, also valued the opportunity to establish a relationship with the school staff at Blue Primary School during the first face-to-face transition day. This particular finding was in line with both Griebeling and Gilbert's (2020) and Fan *et al.*'s (2023) research where parents involved in a transition programme took part in face-to-face opportunities, including talks and other activities while their child attended transition activities. As with both Griebeling and Gilbert's (2020) and Fan *et al.*'s (2023) findings, the parents in my research, who were interviewed after the transition talk, felt they had the start of a relationship with key primary school staff and felt less anxious, as they had been able to see for themselves the key staff and how they interacted with their child. However, unlike Tobin *et al.*'s (2023) research, it was not known whether establishing a relationship with school staff was only important to first time parents from a working-class background within my research, as this was not part of the questions asked of the parents taking part. The parents also had the opportunity to ask questions at the transition talk, a point that parents involved in Fan *et al.*'s (2023) research too found valuable.

An implication for not only Blue Primary School but the EY and Primary sectors in Scotland, is how to develop trust between the parent/carer and members of staff. Consideration needs to be given to how this relationship can be initiated, sustained and used to support children during this transition period and throughout primary school, with the important caveat that often first impressions last. Leenders *et al.*, (2019) state the importance of two-way communication both formally and informally with teachers, as this can help develop a trusting relationship between the parent and the teacher. Therefore, this too needs to be considered when planning transition events. Finally, the parents in my research were eager to hear about the school and

what they could do to help their child starting primary school. This finding agreed with both Fan *et al.*'s (2023) and Kuusimäki, Uusitalo-Malmivaara and Tirri's (2019) findings that parents wanted to learn more about what was expected of them and how they could support their child. Interestingly this contrasted with Rogers' (2018) finding that, while parents wanted opportunities to share information about their child with their educators, they did not want to participate in information sessions about the school.

6.4. Discussion and Implications Related to Research Aim Three

The key findings for aim three - 'to identify any barriers to parental engagement during their child's transition from the ELC to the main primary school and how these might be overcome'- indicated for Blue Primary School that there are barriers to parental engagement, including providing advance notification and timing of events. This included the transition talk at Blue Primary School which took place during the day. As Hornby and Blackwell (2018) stated, school opening hours can be a barrier to parental engagement. For Blue Primary School there was no option provided for an evening talk. The implication of this could have been that although all parents taking part in the research study ultimately attended, almost all took time off work in order to attend, other parents/carers may not have been able to attend when they would have liked to due to work or family commitments. Consequently, parents/carers unable to attend may end up finding information from a secondary source instead. Concern about work commitments by some of the parents taking part in my research aligns with Lohmann, Hathcote and Hogan's (2018) findings that parental workload can directly impact a parent's ability to attend events, even if they wanted to attend. My research study finding is also in line with the finding of the '*Parental Involvement/Engagement Census*' cited in '*Strategic Framework for: Parental Involvement, Parental Engagement, Family Learning and Learning at Home*', (Education Scotland, 2022) which indicated that in 2019 72% of parents had work commitments that affected their ability to attend events at schools. Interestingly, in my research 89% of the parents had to take time off work to attend the transition talk. Advice within the Education Scotland (2022) document suggests the need for educational settings to consider the timing of parental engagement opportunities. The timing of events is also an implication Senior Leadership Teams within the wider EY and Primary sectors in

Scotland should consider when involving parents/carers in their child's transition to primary school. However, it may be challenging to decide and agree planned transition events well in advance, because once event notification is sent out and the event date and/or time changed parents/carers may be upset at not being able to attend the rescheduled date.

Another finding related to the barrier to parental engagement, was the different care arrangements for the children attending Rainbow ELC. Although parents interviewed did not share whether they were separated from their child's other parent, it is an important barrier to acknowledge as a few of the parents taking part in my research stated that they were not able to hear first-hand information shared at drop off and collection times due to childcare arrangements. Separated parents was acknowledged as a barrier to parental involvement in their child's education by Hornby and Blackwell (2018). The implication of this for Rainbow ELC and the wider EY and Primary sectors in Scotland is that if information is not passed on by the adult dropping off/collecting the child to the parent then, this may result in the parent not being kept abreast of transition events, possibly leading the child or parent to miss events that they had been invited to attend. Consideration needs to be given to how information is shared, with parents/carers who are not able to drop off and collect their child from nursery. This also aligned with Oke, Butler and O'Neill (2021) findings whereby parents wanted more one-to-one discussions about their child. Therefore, consideration also needs to be given to how two-way communication could be promoted for parents/carers who were not able to drop off/collect their child, by asking parents what form the two-way communication should take - a suggestion made by Oke, Butler and O'Neill (2021). Moreover, according to Desmarchelier *et al.*, (2022) parents who are separated should both receive information. While not directly discussed by the two working fathers who participated in my research, Lechowicz *et al.*, (2019) states that, for working fathers to engage, opportunities should be provided out with working hours. Interestingly within my research, this point was also true for the six mothers who worked. However, in Scotland since Covid-19 there has been a shift in the working hours that parents may be undertaking with a greater flexibility of the hours they work and where they undertake this work, due to the *Employment Relations (Flexible Working) Act 2023*, with more parents engaging in hybrid

working/flexible working by splitting their working pattern between home and the office. This may mean that parents may be able, depending on the job that they have, to attend a meeting or event at the ELC or school that they have been invited to during the ELC/school day (Flexibility Works, 2025) and if needed repay the hours owed due to attending the event at a later time. Additionally, some parents have more flexibility through the *Employment Relations (Flexible Working) Act 2023* to work hours that enable a more work life balance, including sharing the parenting responsibility with the other parent/family members whereby they work more in the evenings giving the flexibility to engage in events that take place during ELC/school hours (Flexibility Works, 2025). There are also more child friendly policies that some employers have implemented, encouraging parents to be more involved in their child's education, as there is recognition that this is important to both the parent and the child's wellbeing, therefore allowing them to take time off to attend meetings with the caveat that this might not be paid time off. Whilst Lechowicz *et al.*'s research (2019) offers interesting provocations perhaps parental flexibility within work and its impact on potential engagement with the child's educational setting is less bounded by parental gender and more influenced by individual day-to-day experience. Thus, consideration might be given by each setting to the needs of the parent cohort when deciding the timing of events if they are hoping for the majority of parents/carers to attend. In light of this it is, perhaps, inevitable that settings may not be able to engage all parents in all face-to-face transition activities, despite their best efforts.

6.5. Discussion and Implications Related to Research Aim Four

The key findings for aim four - 'to investigate what we can learn about parent and professional partnerships from the participatory approach of the study' - established that the steering group (SG) of professionals and parents was worthwhile, as all members participating stated that their voice and opinion was valued. Through the collegiate nature of the group and opportunities offered, I sought to empower the parents to help make decisions alongside the professional members of the group at these meetings. It appears that comments from all SG participants support Macaulay's (2017) stance of inclusivity and the importance of involving those who are to benefit from the research in the research process. In their research into parental

involvement, Hornby and Blackwell (2018) state that schools must collaborate with parents, thereby supporting the relevance of my research and what I had set out to achieve. Additionally, this study put into practice the *Scottish Schools (Parental Involvement) Act 2006*, as parent members of the SG were invited to be actively involved in the transition planning between the two settings. The findings from my study also align with Smith's (2022) conclusion that parents should be viewed as 'insiders' - the same as teachers, as the parents in my research were making sense of how parental engagement in the SG related to them.

Although Rainbow ELC and Blue Primary School were not on the same campus, the collaboration between them was still effective, as SG members from both settings worked collaboratively with the parent members, thereby embracing recommendations from '*Thematic inspection of Empowerment for Parent and Parent Participation*' (Education Scotland, 2019b) that educational settings work collaboratively with parents. Furthermore, as Dunlop (2017) notes, parents and teachers should have the opportunity to work together, thereby establishing a trusting relationship and valuing the input that parents have in their child's lives including supporting their child during this period of change. Positive implications of adopting a participatory approach within education include that parents/carers can provide insightful information, particularly about decisions that ultimately affect them. However, failure to include parents/carers may result in them feeling they do not have a voice in making decisions that will ultimately affect them and their child. This may lead to a lack of parental engagement and involvement within both the EY and Primary sectors in Scotland, whilst also contravening the *Scottish Schools (Parental Involvement) Act 2006*. Parents/carers involved in SGs or similar with professionals can feel empowered and want to be involved in their child's experiences, particularly at significant periods of their child's life, including transition to primary school. The support and willingness of Senior Leadership Teams is critical if a participatory approach is to be successfully adopted. If parents/carers and professionals do not feel empowered and genuinely involved in making informed decisions, then there is a risk of paying lip service, as the power is still held by the Senior Leadership Team, as they continue to ultimately make the final decisions. It is important to note that these particular implications, whilst relevant to the settings involved in my research, are also relevant to the wider education sectors within Scotland. Within the context of

transition, Dunlop (2017) states that if parents work in partnership with schools to co-construct the transition to school, then this may have a positive impact on the child (OECD (2017; 2020)). Furthermore, engagement around transition can also support the long-term development of cooperation and engagement between the family and school. Additionally, through participating in the steering group, the professionals (Transition Coordinator, Head of ELC and Depute Head Teacher) also had the opportunity to work together endorsing 'professional linkages' stated by Dockett and Perry (2020) as a vital component of transition.

6.6. Discussion and Implications of Policy Awareness

From my research study, there appeared a lack of professional awareness and knowledge of current policies and guidance by both the ELC staff and the future Primary One teachers related to communication, transition and parent engagement/parental involvement. Implications of this include not being able to commit to enacting the practices of the policy and guidance if staff are not clear as to the expectations. There also appeared an over reliance on members of the Senior Leadership Team within both settings, and the Transition Coordinator within Rainbow ELC, to keep abreast of guidance and policy. It is important to note, that the implications discussed here, are relevant not only for the two settings involved in this research study, but for both the EY and Primary sectors in Scotland. The policy and guidance discussed in Chapter Two are relevant for all staff in ELC and the early stages of primary schools in Scotland, as they include current expectations and *best practice* for communicating with parents and parental engagement and involvement. Additionally, there appears to be a reliance on members of the Senior Leadership Teams who already have a huge workload to pass on their interpretation of the policy or guidance. Furthermore, as Ball, Maguire and Braun (2012) note, policies may be interpreted differently depending on a teacher's/practitioner's role within the school. Therefore, an implication is that Senior Leadership Teams, may interpret and translate policies and guidance differently to teachers and Early Years Practitioners on the front line, who are responsible for actually putting policies and guidance into practice.

The final finding, links directly to some parents' understanding of the local authority *placing request policy*. As discussed in section 5.2.4., conversations with the primary

schools about the placing request policy (no contact with either setting until a placing request is resolved) would have been face-to-face. However, since placing request application forms are now completed online, there is no guarantee that parents read all the supplementary information about placing requests before submitting an application. This lack of in-person opportunity for school leaders to speak directly to parents about submitting a placing request brings to the fore the possible misunderstanding of this protocol by parents. This point highlights the important role the senior leadership had, prior to moving applications online, in ensuring that parents knew the necessary information about catchment schools and placing requests. Consequently, now that application forms are completed online there is no way of supporting parents' understanding of the placing request policy. Once the parent interviewed (Parent 1) had received confirmation of a place at Blue Primary School they received a welcoming phone call from a member of the senior leadership team referencing the transition that would take place prior to their child starting Blue Primary School. The implication of placing request confusion is that parents/carers may not understand that the timing of the information they are given is dependent upon their placing request outcome which is controlled centrally by the local authority, not the primary school. It is therefore important for parents/carers to be better informed from the outset of the application for a placing request, about the policy related to their child's placing request, and why the primary schools in the local authority are not allowing children and their parents/carers to take part in transition opportunities until the outcome of the placing request is known.

6.7. Conclusion

Within this chapter a number of findings and associated implications have been discussed in relation to each of the four research aims. It is evident that some of the findings from my research study are consistent with current academic research discussed previously within Chapter Three. Examples include the importance of consulting parents about their preferred communication methods including digital ones, the importance of parental engagement and the benefits for parents, child and school when these include practical opportunities. Furthermore, the finding regarding a lack of knowledge of current policies by the ELC staff and future Primary One staff

was unexpected. Finally, recommendations for some of the implications outlined in this chapter are discussed within Chapter Eight.

Chapter Seven: Researcher Reflections on Adopting a Participatory Research Approach

7.1. Introduction

From the outset of this study, I sought to actively involve parents/carers by adopting a participatory research approach. From my previous research, I was aware the important role that parents/carers played in their child's transition from ELC to primary school. This included any concerns that parents/carers had being transferred to their child, leading to the child possibly becoming worried and anxious about starting formal education. As explained in Chapter Two, the *Scottish Schools (Parental Involvement) Act 2006*, requires parents/carers to be actively involved in their child's education in a way that is more than just attending events and meetings directed by educational settings. Interestingly, these events may not be what the parents/carers actually want or feel are beneficial to supporting their child's educational journey. Therefore, I wanted to investigate through this exploratory case study how parents/carers could be purposefully involved in the transition programme from Rainbow ELC to Blue Primary School. As part of the participatory research approach this included a small group of parents, who were part of a Steering Group (SG), alongside representatives from both settings involved in the case study, responding to the data collected by me which was shared and discussed with the SG. The SG also agreed actions to amend the current transition programme in response to the collated data. This chapter focuses on my researcher reflections on adopting a participatory research approach. It will discuss positionality and power and my understanding of a participatory research approach within education through the adoption of Galletta and Torre's (2019) key elements of participatory action research (PAR). The chapter will conclude by reflecting on the practical barriers to participation encountered during the initial stages of my research.

7.2. Positionality and Power

When undertaking any research, it is important to consider both critically and reflexivity the role you take during the research study (Braun and Clarke, 2013). As discussed previously in section 4.1.4., I felt I was an inbetween researcher, as I had different roles within the research (Milligan, 2016). Although I ultimately led the research, which

was constructed by me and informed by my axiology of promoting parental voice, I wanted to ensure that as far as possible the research was participatory, especially when making decisions collectively and in partnership with all members of the SG, including the parents. Promoting inclusivity was important to me - to involve and engage with the ultimate beneficiaries of the research (Macaulay, 2017).

Navigating power, discussed previously within section 4.1.6., outlined the premise that I sought to share power with the participants of the SG, which in hindsight was something that I found particularly hard to do. Reflecting back, this was partly due my employment as a teacher, where I have a level of autonomy and regularly make decisions based on the situation before me. A specific example for me, discussed in section 5.5., was discovering both ELC staff's and future Primary One teachers' lack of current policy and guidance awareness. From the collated data shared with the SG, I had hoped that responses to the question about knowledge of policies/guidance, would have been picked up by the Head of ELC and DHT as interesting and one to take forward for the professionals, but it was not. On reflection, I should have mentioned what I had noticed from this data at the second SG meeting, as something that interested me, and an area that could be taken forward for the ELC staff and future Primary One teachers. To address this specific point, it has been subsequently included as part of the recommendations discussed within section 8.6.

Another example related to the DHT, who embraced the participatory approach during the SG meetings, but on reflection may have found it hard to sustain this beyond the final meeting, perhaps due to other workload. This related to the DHT immediately acting on a decision made at the final SG meeting, to produce a transition newsletter template, sharing it with the Transition Coordinator and the researcher (me) via email for our feedback. Reflecting back, this template should have been shared with the parent representatives of the SG as they agreed with the decision to produce a transition newsletter, and represented the target audience, therefore their feedback would have been insightful. This represented an example whereby, the participatory approach out with the SG was not sustained. It also represented possible issues and

tensions, with the position the DHT held and time available out with the SG meeting to endorse a participatory approach when trying to develop new resources.

Additionally, to ascertain the SG participant's view regarding my role and power within the research, on reflection, I should have questioned the participants taking part about the role and power, they felt I held within the research, as opposed to hypothetically guessing the role I played in the eyes of the different participants and the educational settings involved. This would ultimately have enhanced further the discussion on the participatory research approach I adopted and the power I still held.

7.3. An Understanding of What a Participatory Research Approach Involves within Education Through the Adoption of Galletta and Torre (2019) Key Elements of Participatory Action Research

The participatory research approach, discussed in detail within section 4.1.5., involved an ontological shift from a more traditional way of undertaking research whereby the researcher collects data from participants, whose involvement ceases following the completion of data gathering (Warwick-Booth, Bagnall and Coan, 2021). This was the way I had undertaken previous research, therefore the shift to adopting a participatory research approach was at times challenging. In reflecting on adopting the participatory research approach, I make reference to Galletta and Torre's (2019) key elements of participatory action research (PAR) within education. I acknowledge that while my research does not fully adopt this method of research, it does contain many elements and is therefore helpful to inform my reflection. The elements are stated here, before being reframed into guiding reflective questions.

Firstly, the authors state that participatory action research:

Challenges exclusive academic notions of expertise, legitimizing, and prioritizing the expertise and perspectives that come from lived experience and situated knowledge.

(Galletta and Torre, 2019, p. 1)

A second element focuses specifically on PAR within education, stating:

In education research, a PAR approach typically centers the wisdom and experience of students ... and educators, positioning them as architects of research rather than objects of study.

(Galletta and Torre, 2019, p. 1)

Another element focuses on involving others in the research, stating:

Youth and educators are invited as colleagues to design research programs, determine research questions, gather and make sense of relevant literatures/existing knowledge, decide useful methods, collect and analyze data and create meaningful products.

(Galletta and Torre, 2019, p. 1)

Another element focuses on acknowledging everyone's knowledge, stating:

Each member/co-researcher brings her/his/their own reservoir of experiential knowledge differing angles of vision to the table, PAR understands the diverse range of standpoints, and the potential dissonance and/or clashes that come with them.

(Galletta and Torre, 2019, p. 1)

Finally, the authors suggest that participants should seek to understand/embrace alternative perspectives stating:

When discordance within the research collective, or between the collective and the outside world, is engaged rather than denied or smoother over, new and different ways of seeing and being emerge.

(Galletta and Torre, 2019, p. 1)

7.4. Galletta and Torre (2019) as a Tool for Reflection

The first element above (Galletta and Torre, 2019) was reframed into the reflective question 'How did my research challenge notions of academic/professional expertise?' As discussed previously, my research was not participatory action research, but it sought to embrace participatory elements. This included the overarching reason for establishing a SG, which was to give a voice and promote genuine active participation of parent representatives, thereby challenging the notion of professional expertise. The parent members of the SG worked collaboratively with members of staff from Rainbow ELC and Blue Primary School who were also part of the SG. As explained previously, basic ground rules were established in an attempt to ensure that all SG members had the freedom to voice their opinion and, if required, challenge notions of professional expertise. Although the parents had a professional relationship with the Head of ELC and the Transition Coordinator, they had not had the opportunity to establish a relationship with either the DHT or myself, prior to attending the first SG meeting. To attempt to address this, as part of the first SG meeting all members introduced themselves and why they wanted to be part of the SG. I also emphasised during this meeting, that all views and opinions were valued. Additionally, all SG members were actively involved in deciding the research methods that were to be employed to interview the parents and the final questions I was to ask the parents, ELC staff and future Primary One teachers. Alongside an active involvement in the initial stages of becoming familiar with the collected data. These examples sought to challenge the notion that I, as the researcher, held the academic expertise as I acknowledged that both the parents and staff members of the SG had knowledge of the current transition programme between both educational settings and that was integral to my research. As well as the parents' insider knowledge of the parent/carer participants I was to interview and the preference for FGs as opposed to interviewing individually.

The second element (Galletta and Torre, 2019) led me to ask, 'How did my research position the parents/educators as engaged in/committed to the research rather than objects of study?' As discussed within sections 4.3.1. – 4.3.4., all participants who took part indicated their commitment to the research by accepting an invitation to

participate. The participants were either higher-level participants (Coghlan and Brydon-Miller, 2014), engaged in the active involvement in the SG and directly involved in making decisions about communication tools and parental engagement, or lower-level participants (Coghlan and Brydon-Miller, 2014) who took part in interviews or FGs to give their experiences and opinions that would ultimately be used to help the SG make decisions. From the outset, this study embraced a participatory approach, thereby positioning the parents/educators as engaged in the research. The Head of ELC was fully supportive of the research and from the outset was eager for as many parents as possible who met the criteria to take part. Additionally, following my discussion with the DHT about the research, she indicated her own eagerness to become a member of the SG as well as stressing the importance of involving the future Primary One teachers. Thereby both the DHT and the Head of ELC agreed about the importance of parents/educators to be engaged in the research. However, as it was a small-scale piece of doctoral research, with a restricted timescale to complete the data collection before the end of school academic year, it would have been challenging to more fully engage parents/educators in the research design. Therefore, on reflection, for some aspects of the research the participants were not involved in making decisions and having direct ownership of the research. Examples included the initial ideas for the study coming from me rather than the settings involved in the study reaching out to me, thereby not giving them ownership of the research only the decisions and recommendations made. Although members of the SG did appear satisfied from the findings with being involved in the research and actively participating in the SG meetings and the collective decisions and recommendations made.

The third element (Galletta and Torre, 2019) was reframed by changing the reference from *youth* to *parent*, asking, 'How (and to what extent) were parents and educators (professionals) invited as colleagues to design research, determine research questions, gather and make sense of relevant literature/existing knowledge, decide useful methods, collect and analyse data, and create meaningful research products?' Although the final decision for the first research question and aims were mine, they were both informed by discussions with both the Head of Rainbow ELC and the DHT of Blue Primary School, prior to embarking on the research. The other SG participants, alongside the Head of Rainbow ELC and the DHT of Blue Primary School were

involved in a variety of decisions, including the final interview questions to be asked and the data method to be used when asking the wider group of parents/carers who met the purposive sampling criteria, discussed within section 4.2. On reflection this was beneficial, as the participants discussed the merits of asking each question with irrelevant questions removed. This SG activity also actively promoted the importance of different opinions being valued with a consensus reached as everyone's opinion was valued, not just the education professionals including me. The discussion with the SG parents about using FGs as opposed to individual interviews with the parents was also informative, as they used their insider knowledge to support their preferred decision that FGs should be used. Furthermore, the initial analysis and sharing of the collated data, allowed collective decisions to be made by the SG, whereby amendments were to be made to the current transition programme between the settings. Additionally, during the SG meetings both parents and educators had the opportunity to voice their opinion and engage in tasks that informed decisions made. An example of this included the need for first-time parents to have the opportunity to see round Blue Primary School.

Reflecting specifically on the two parents who attended all three SG meetings, both parents appeared to feel empowered, becoming more relaxed and vocal, as the meetings progressed. All SG members took part in reviewing the interview data, offering initial insights into participant responses. Interestingly, the parents appeared to have found it hard to refrain from adding in their own reflections to the questions asked, occasionally adding their personal thoughts to the post-it notes rather than analysing the participant responses. This was also true of the Head of ELC and the Transition Coordinator. On reflection, more support should have been offered regarding how to engage with this task, including how to analyse data, as I do not think the members of the SG had the necessary skills to analyse the collated data.

In relation to the above there are areas I would do differently if I were to repeat the research. These include undertaking individual interviews after the final SG meeting with the parent members to find out exactly what their thoughts were about their experience of this participatory research approach. This would also be offered to the

Head of Rainbow ELC, DHT and Transition Coordinator, with the addition of ascertaining whether they would adopt a participatory approach with parents/carers and staff in the future when developing/evaluating a different focus.

The fourth element (Galletta and Torre, 2019) was reframed into the reflective question 'How was each member enabled to bring her/his/their own reservoir of experiential knowledge and differing angles of vision to the table, contributing to a diverse range of standpoints, and the potential dissonance/and or clashes?' Firstly, in order to acknowledge everyone's knowledge, purposive sampling (discussed in section 4.2.) was employed. By inviting all parents/carers who had a child starting at Blue Primary School, I had no influence over the parents' background and position their child starting school had in the family, thus enabling different knowledge, views and perspectives about the transition programme to be brought to the research. As a result, all but one parent interviewed were first-time parents, eight out of the nine were working parents, two were male and the rest female. The predominance of working parents opened up different viewpoints, including ones that I had not considered, for example the barriers to parental engagement making the research more professionally enlightening. As discussed within the findings for aims one, two, and three, there were a number of conflicting understandings amongst the parents interviewed. On reflection, it was disappointing that the FGs were not possible. I feel FGs may have addressed more directly the disagreement about the communication tools used and parental engagement opportunities preferred. Moreover, although parents/carers who met the purposive criteria were given the opportunity to take part, involvement could have affected due to the restricted data collection timeframe.

The purposive criteria for ELC staff (educators) selection required that they had knowledge of the current Rainbow ELC transition programme. Four members of ELC staff agreed to participate in a FG, as did all three future Primary One teachers. The importance of both their individual and collective knowledge, gave me an insight into both the communication tools used to communicate with parents and parental engagement during the period of transition from the educators' perspective. When reflecting on the ELC staff FG, it would appear that there were no significant

differences of opinion. In the future Primary One teachers' FG some participants supported or elaborated a comment made by a colleague. However, the future Primary One teachers appeared to rely on the Senior Leadership Team to tell them what their part was in the transition programme, with limited direct input from the future Primary One teachers permitted. When discussing the ideas put forward by the future Primary One teachers with the DHT – in lieu of her attending the second SG - a variety of reasons why their ideas could not be taken forward were given. These included teacher workload and general school staffing. For me this was interesting, as the DHT was supportive of the participatory research approach when working with parents but, due to other pressures out with her control, the ideas from members of the school staff, were not taken forward at that time.

The final element (Galletta and Torre,2019) was reframed to the reflective question, 'Did discordance occur within the research collective? What happened then? Was it engaged with rather than denied or smoothed over? Did new or different ways of seeing and being emerge?' From a researcher perspective, I had envisaged that sharing the data collected from both FGs with the SG would have invoked some discussion. Examples of such discussion might have included taking up ideas from the future Primary One teachers about enhancing the parental engagement opportunities or consideration of the lack of knowledge by ELC staff and future Primary One teachers about policies and guidance. However, these points were not picked up by any of the SG members. It appeared the SG collectively, were focused solely on the data from the parents, rather than the FG data from the ELC staff or future Primary One teachers. This proved hard for me as a researcher, as I felt that at least these two points should have been addressed, even if only by the professionals. As the research adopted a participatory research approach, I reminded myself that whilst I may still be leading the research, I wanted to value the priorities of the SG members. With hindsight, as a member of the SG, I should have shared my views to see if other members agreed or felt these points needed to be taken forward.

However, an example of discordance did occur during the discussion with the DHT about the data that would be shared at the second SG meeting (the meeting she could

not attend). This led to the DHT stating her displeasure at the responses the parents had given (discussed previously in section 5.2.1.2.) about not receiving information about the primary school. The discussion highlighted that the DHT was probably upset, as she had spent time collating and preparing the information she felt should be shared in the introductory email about Blue Primary School. She may also have felt disheartened that some of the parents interviewed possibly had not read or could not recall the information that had been sent out four months prior to being interviewed for my research study. Furthermore, as she was unable to attend the second SG meeting, she did not have the opportunity to clarify from the parent members of the SG what their thoughts were about the information already sent out, and the comments made by the parents interviewed. In hindsight, it may have been better to re-schedule the second SG meeting, so that the DHT could have attended. Thereby giving her the possibly to discuss openly what the parents had said in the interviews with the members of the SG, including the parent members.

7.5. Overcoming Practical Barriers to Participation

As discussed in section 4.2., it had been extremely challenging to get parent participants together to be part of focus groups (FG), therefore the research method used to collect the data from the parent participants was changed to *individual* parent interviews. Reflecting on the individual interviews and their relationship to adopting a participatory research approach, I have a better understanding of the need to reduce as many barriers as possible to engage parents who wish to participate. In this study, this included the timing of the interview, whether an online or face-to-face interview was preferable and parent confidence and ability to use online digital platforms. As a researcher, it became evident that I needed to be flexible and adaptable to the needs of the participants who had agreed to take part in the research. Additionally, I wanted to ensure that I kept parent voice at the heart of the research, and therefore I adapted to enable this to happen.

7.6. Conclusion

As discussed at the start of this chapter, I adopted a participatory research approach, as I was keen to better understand parental engagement/involvement across the EY

and Primary sectors in Scotland, not just the two settings involved in this case study. Reflecting on Galletta and Torre's (2019) five elements, both my professional and academic knowledge of employing this approach has developed. As a professional, I would like to use this approach within my professional practice as a teacher in the future when working with parents/carers. This includes involving parents/carers through the development of a SG as a more effective and innovative way of promoting parental engagement and involvement in their child's educational journey. For me, the SG has highlighted how information can be acquired from participants, who may view the focus through a different lens to that of educators. However, a participatory approach does appear to bring to the fore some issues of power, and the hierarchical structure within education, which may need to be more fully explored with senior leaders who wish to adopt this approach while taking into account their role and remit within the school/ELC setting.

Moreover, when considering adopting a participatory approach within education, there are points that should be considered. These include deciding the best time to engage directly with parents/carers; how to practically involve them in making decisions about things that involve and affect them; and considering the individual circumstances of hard-to-reach parents. Other considerations include: the role of senior leaders and their understanding of participatory approaches, including how they envisage these happening within their own context; what they want the adoption of such approaches to achieve; and a willingness for practice to change as a result of responses received.

Chapter Eight: Recommendations and Conclusion

8.1. Introduction

After undertaking this research study, a number of recommendations have been identified specifically for Rainbow ELC and Blue Primary School, but also for both the Early Years (EY) and Primary sectors in Scotland. A few recommendations have also been identified for the local authority, where the 'case' was located and a recommendation for policy makers. Within this chapter, all recommendations will be discussed in relation to each of the four aims, the findings discussed in Chapter Five and the discussion and implications discussed in Chapter Six. The chapter will then provide a response to the research questions posed at the start of the thesis 'What communication tools are pertinent to successfully supporting parental engagement during transition programmes from Early Learning and Childcare to primary school?' and the second research question 'What are the benefits and challenges of parent/professional partnership work within a participatory approach to research?' Thereafter as part of the conclusion, an update of what has happened following the research study's conclusion will be explained, limitations of the research study and recommendations for future research will also be discussed, alongside a final reflection of the research in terms of its contribution to the EY sector and my own professional development.

8.2. Recommendations Related to Research Aim One

The recommendations within this section are related to the first research aim – 'to investigate whether the communication methods employed by both the ELC and the main feeder primary school for parental engagement during the transition process are meeting needs and if not, what alternatives could be used'.

8.2.1. Recommendations for Rainbow ELC/Blue Primary School

The findings for aim one discussed in 5.2.1.1. for Rainbow ELC, identified issues with the Nursery App. A recommendation specific to Rainbow ELC is to ensure

parents/carers using the Nursery App are fully aware of all the ways that the ELC use the app to communicate with them. This includes the calendar section, which could be set up to include transition event information that is regularly updated with a notification informing parents/carers of any updates. A named contact at Rainbow ELC could be provided for parents/carers to contact should they have any technical issues with the app. Consideration should also be given by Rainbow ELC to the importance of face-to-face communication by ELC staff, for parents/carers who do not have the Nursery App as a way to keep abreast of what is happening including upcoming transition events. This type of communication is something that the Head of ELC should remind staff about so that they do not solely rely on the Nursery App when communicating with parents/carers.

A specific recommendation for Blue Primary School is to consider introducing the new parents/carers to Blue Primary School App prior to the transition talk in June. This could possibly include making a section for new parents/carers, with a key contact, that parents/carers could contact if they have anything they wish to discuss (after their child has been registered for Blue Primary School). The app would also give Blue Primary School the opportunity to direct message the parents/carers about transition events that are coming up.

The findings also identified issues with the initial emails being sent to parents by Blue Primary School. A recommendation for emails being sent out by the primary school is to consider the amount of information or number of attachments being sent out in one email. Furthermore, in terms of ensuring the email has been received, a recommendation is that a read receipt should be requested, allowing the primary school to track that they have the correct contact email address. Additionally, the findings identified issues related to the letter given out by Rainbow ELC on behalf of the primary school. A recommendation for Blue Primary School is to consider alternative ways of communicating with the parents/carers of children transitioning to the primary school, instead of relying on Rainbow ELC staff to give out a letter on the primary school's behalf. However, if letters from Blue Primary School are to continue to be given out by the ELC, then consideration should be given to the day of the week

that any letters are handed out. At the time of the study the pattern of attendance indicated that a Wednesday, was the day of the week that most children attended Rainbow ELC. If this day of the week was used, then this would reduce the likelihood of letters being received by parents/carers on different days, with a sweep up day for the children not attending on a Wednesday. Additionally, notification could be placed on the Nursery App that a letter from Blue Primary School is being given out via Rainbow ELC with a reminder to contact the nursery if not received.

Both settings should also consider the best communication methods for parental engagement events. A recommendation to address this is using different communication methods, depending on the event or information being given out. This includes using more than one communication tool to notify parents/carers, alongside considering how *best* to communicate with parents/carers, including separated parents who are not in regular face-to-face contact with Rainbow ELC.

8.2.2. Recommendations for both the EY and Primary Sectors in Scotland

Recommendations related to aim one have also been identified for EY and Primary sectors in Scotland related to methods and tools used to communicate with parents/carers. It is evident from the findings that education settings should consider the best ways to communicate with parents within their own context. One way to achieve this, is that the education settings consult their parents/carers through a survey asking how they would prefer the education setting to communicate with them as a collective. A second way is for education settings to explain to their parents/carers the different forms of communication the setting already uses to communicate with them. Furthermore, parents in this study identified school information that was important, for example, knowledge of school uniforms and what the school looks like. These could be addressed without the need for parents to wait until the transition talk to find out this information. A recommendation for EY and Primary sectors in Scotland is to ensure this information is readily available, possibly via their settings website, and that the website's information is current and up to date. This may include a specific section of the website, dedicated to first time/new parents, with core information that has been collated from a consultation with parents/carers to find out information they

want to know about the school. Information available in the home languages of children and families should also be included to promote inclusivity.

8.2.3. Recommendations for Local Authority

Interestingly, since completing this research, the local authority has introduced a 'Parentsportal' – a one stop online digital portal for parents/carers of children in primary or secondary schools to access a variety of information sent out by schools. However, research by Epstein *et al.*, (2019) recommends that hard copies should still be available for parents/carers, who request this type of communication or have technical issues accessing the portal. Therefore, this is something that should be considered by the local authority for parents/carers unable to access 'Parentsportal'.

8.3. Recommendations Related to Research Aim Two

The second research aim was 'to identify parental engagement opportunities that parents would like to be involved in during their child's transition to primary school'. Findings for this aim concentrated on the parents interviewed for the research study, who indicated that they wanted to be involved in practical opportunities during their child's transition programme to Blue Primary School. Examples discussed included gaining knowledge of the primary school prior to their child starting, having the opportunity to get to know the primary school staff and having the opportunity to visit the primary school prior to the transition talk in June.

8.3.1. Recommendation for Rainbow ELC/Blue Primary School

The recommendation related to these findings for Blue Primary School include providing parents/carers with the opportunity to have an in-person tour of the primary school that their child is going to. This particular recommendation was one actually taken forward by the SG to be introduced during the next academic year.

8.3.2. Recommendations for both the EY and Primary Sectors in Scotland

Although pertinent to Blue Primary School, the recommendation of providing parents/carers the opportunity to tour the school is one that all educational settings in Scotland should consider, either in person or as a virtual tour, depending on parental circumstances actively encourages parental involvement/engagement in their child's new school. Additionally, the following recommendations are relevant not only for the Blue Primary School but all primary schools who undertake transition events with parents/carers in Scotland. These include ensuring that information shared with parents/carers is relevant and what parents/carers want to know about the school. Professionals should not assume that they know best, by providing information that *they* feel parents/carers should know. To achieve this, parents/carers should be consulted about the information they feel is important to them, with this information incorporated within the information shared with parents/carers prior to their child starting that primary school. As discussed in section 5.3.1., parents need opportunities to establish relationships with core staff from the primary school as early as possible, because some parents are anxious about their child starting school and parents may want the opportunity to share any concerns with key staff about their child. It is therefore important to find out the transition opportunities that parents/carers want to take part in, in order to meet the needs of both their child and themselves. This includes considering face-to-face events including practical ones. However, it is important to acknowledge workload constraints of settings, and any opportunities offered need to suit the staff as well as the parents/carers. Therefore, any events could only be introduced within the constraints of current staff workloads. The working parents involved in my research study brought a different dimension to the research. Some of the parents mentioned that they needed to take time off to attend the transition talk given by the Head Teacher of Blue Primary School, this has led to some possible ways forward including consideration be given to when any meetings or events involving parents who may be working takes place. This includes the possibility of consulting the parents about what works best for them as a collective. This may include considering the possibility of evening transition events alongside events that take place during the day, so that parents have an option of when to take part. However, such solutions inevitably throw up workforce challenges for educational settings, for example, the constraints of the teachers' working time agreement in

Scotland (35-hour week) and the individual contractual hours of ELC practitioners. Another possibility could be to facilitate for parents to opt in to meetings via Microsoft Teams or to record the events so that parents can watch back in their own time. This would also allow parents who attended in-person to watch back and recall information that had been shared at the meeting. This is an option that could be time consuming but could be beneficial. Clearly there is no simple solution or one *size fits all* solution to the question of how, when and where to engage parents in conversations about transition.

8.4. Recommendations Related to Research Aim Three

The third research aim was 'to identify any barriers to parental engagement during their child's transition from the ELC to the main primary school and how these might be overcome'. The findings for this aim established specific barriers to parental involvement and engagement including timing and advance notice of events.

8.4.1. Recommendations for Rainbow ELC/Blue Primary School and both the EY and Primary Sectors in Scotland

The recommendations for aim three are pertinent not only for both settings involved in the research, but also all EY and Primary sectors in Scotland to reduce barriers. These include considering handing out a full year diary which includes when events will be taking place for parents/carers but also for children. This would particularly assist working parents/carers or those with other commitments, thereby allowing families to plan when they need to take/request time off or enough time to arrange for someone else to attend on their behalf. It is also vital to consider the timing of parental events, including the possibility of offering more than one time slot for transition talks, such as evening events for working parents/carers or for those requiring childcare out with the school day. Additionally, transition events should take place over a longer period of time, in order that working parents/carers can request the time off. Furthermore, settings also need to consider parents who may be separated or require communication in a language other than English.

8.4.2. Recommendations for the Local Authority

Recommendations specific to the local authority include the need to consider the current protocol for children whose parents/carers submit a placing request for their child to attend a non-catchment primary school. The current timescale can involve up to a four month wait (if completed at the same time as enrolment for primary school), as the outcome is not known until the end of April. This wait results in the parents/carers and child unable to take part in specific transition events planned for the catchment or placing request primary school until this outcome is known. Therefore, this protocol for placing requests needs to be made clear in order that parents/carers understand that the ELC/primary school are not involving them in specific transition opportunities due to local authority advice. A solution could be ensuring this information about the placing request protocol is included on the application form and on the local authority website. Additionally, if placing requests had a shorter window for application forms to be submitted, then outcomes could be known quicker, resulting in parents/carers and children being able to take part in more transition opportunities planned by the receiving primary school.

8.5. Recommendations Related to Research Aim Four

The final research aim was ‘to investigate what we can learn about parent and professional partnerships from the participatory approach of the study school’. In terms of findings, aim four established that active involvement of parents in decisions was beneficial to both settings in this exploratory case study and was positively achieved through the development of a steering group (SG) that included parents.

8.5.1 Recommendations for Rainbow ELC/Blue Primary School

For the settings involved in this case study, both the DHT and the Head of ELC should consider sharing how the SG actively involved parents and the positive changes that have arisen from parental participation in transition programme decisions, with the local learning community and the local authority. This could include explaining the advantages of working with parents in a SG and how such a group can positively support development of a school’s future priorities. Furthermore, this approach could

also be rolled out by Rainbow ELC and Blue Primary School senior leaders who may find the notion of a short-life SG helpful in engaging stakeholders, including parents/carers.

8.5.2. Recommendations for Parents

The parent members of the SG could be invited to share their experience with other parents/carers, both within the settings involved and other local authority settings. The parents could also be encouraged to join Blue Primary School Parent Council.

8.5.3. Recommendations for both the EY and Primary Sectors in Scotland

A general recommendation, for the EY and Primary sectors in Scotland includes considering the establishment of transition SGs, consisting of parents/carers from the ELC and staff from both the ELC and primary schools being involved in reviewing current transition programmes, including events involving parents/carers. It is vital to enable parents/carers and staff to bring their own knowledge and different viewpoints to such discussions. As a caveat to introducing a SG, it is important to acknowledge workload constraints, particularly for the professionals invited to participate. As such, a SG could only be replicated within the constraints of current workload of ELC staff and teachers, alongside the agreement and support of Senior Leadership Teams.

8.6. Recommendations Related to Policy Awareness

There are recommendations related to the findings about policies and the fact that both the ELC and future Primary One teachers were unable to discuss current policies and guidance related to communication and transition with parents/carers.

8.6.1. Recommendation for Rainbow ELC/Blue Primary School

One recommendation for Rainbow ELC staff and future Primary One teachers is that they are made aware of relevant policies and guidance, including those outlined in Chapter Two, as part of their professional development. Although much of the

information contained within the policy and guidance were being implemented, it is important for them to know where these requirements and practices have come from and the rationale behind them.

8.6.2. Recommendations for both the EY and Primary Sectors in Scotland

All EY settings and primary schools in Scotland should work with their staff to identify implications for practice arising from policies and guidance, including those related to transition and parental engagement/involvement. Having an understanding of policies and guidance, and why changes to practice have come about, may help bring reluctant staff on board when these policies and guidance have to be implemented.

8.6.3. Recommendation for Policy Makers

There is a recommendation that policy makers support policy roll out so front-line staff are able to keep abreast of policies. These staff are regularly the professionals who are putting what the Scottish Government requires or Education Scotland advises into their everyday practice.

8.6.4. Recommendation for Local Authority

There could be an opportunity for settings to share good practice with other settings, in terms of how they have positively implemented in practice guidance and policies within their own contexts. This could possibly be achieved via local authority 'Showcase' events.

8.7. Response to Research Questions

Responding to the first question, 'What communication tools are pertinent to successfully supporting parental engagement during transition programmes from Early Learning and Childcare to primary school?', the study identified that a mixture of communication methods both traditional and digital could be successfully used to involve parents/carers during the transition of their child from Rainbow ELC to Blue Primary School. For Rainbow ELC, the digital Nursery App supported keeping parents

abreast of the transition opportunities the children will be taking part in. However, the traditional face-to-face communication at drop off/collection by parents/carers of their child, was still an important opportunity for parents/carers to hear first-hand about transition opportunities, although this method focussed mainly on what their child had already been involved in. For Blue Primary School, the digital communication through emails, appeared to be successful at informing the parents about the primary school. Although the traditional communication, in the form of a letter handed out via Rainbow ELC, appeared to be contentious, as the letter was not received by all parents and therefore was not the best communication tool used, when compared to the initial emails. Overall, it appears that digital communication with elements of traditional communication, in the form of face-to-face appears to be best way to inform parents/carers about transition events both for the children and for themselves.

Interestingly, in terms of parental engagement, the traditional face-to-face practical opportunities were important. These included visiting the school building and meeting in person key staff from Blue Primary School, as opposed to providing these opportunities via an online platform. It is important to note that although the research question has been answered, in relation to the exploratory case study undertaken, the response to this research question should also be considered by the EY and Primary sectors in Scotland.

Responding to the second research question 'What are the benefits and challenges of parent/professional partnership work within a participatory approach to research?', there were a number of benefits from undertaking a participatory approach to this study. Adopting this approach enabled me, to some extent, to challenge the traditional hierarchy of power by creating a space where decisions were made collectively and not solely by senior leaders. In doing so, decisions were informed by the participants' knowledge and experience (both parent and professional). The opportunity for parents and professionals who were members of the SG to actively contribute to decision making appears to have had a positive impact on the communication tools and methods used and parental engagement opportunities proposed for the transition from Rainbow ELC to Blue Primary School. Moreover, all the parents and professionals

who took part in the research, within the SG or individual interviews, committed to give their opinion to influence the future of the transition programme between the two settings. It was ultimately their knowledge and experience that were at the heart of the decisions made in response to the data collected.

Challenges from undertaking a participatory approach within an educational context include the requirement of the senior leadership team to be on board, as they have the power to decide whether to take on board and implement participant ideas and reflections. Another challenge for this research, was getting parents to come forward to join the SG or take part in interviews (to contribute their voice), as many parents have very busy lives or may just be reluctant to come forward. For this research, it was important to adapt where possible to engage with parents/carers at times and in ways that were suitable to both the school/ELC and the parents/carers.

8.8. The Uniqueness of this Professional Doctorate Research Study

Through undertaking this professional doctorate research study, I identified a number of unique contributions of my research study. The first was ultimately that this research study was undertaken by a professional with a commitment to promoting parental voice and a passion for undertaking research within the context of transition from nursery to primary school in Scotland. Moreover, the research ultimately addressed a knowledge gap from a Scottish perspective regarding communication methods and tools related to transition. This included identifying that parents/carers participating in this research valued human interaction and direct communication with professionals within the primary school in order that they can begin to establish trusting relationships with the adults who would be responsible for their child's future academic progress and wellbeing. This knowledge was particularly important as we are living in an ever-evolving digital world, and this research outlined that while there was a place for digital communication with parents/carers, Early Years professionals need to remember that the traditional forms of communication, including face-to-face and letters, are still valued. In addition, the research has outlined some current barriers for working parents in Scotland. Furthermore, the participatory approach within this research has highlighted the importance of involving parents/carers and other professionals in

making decisions that will ultimately affect early years to primary transition. As such, the study provides examples of participatory approaches to parental engagement in early years transition that can be helpful to other Scottish settings, in support of the *Scottish Schools (Parental Involvement) Act 2006*. Additionally, as a peripatetic nursery teacher I am in the fortunate position to be able to share my findings and recommendations with local authority Early Years managers and other colleagues who work alongside me in the Early Years department. In conclusion my research study offers something new and makes a contribution to knowledge from a Scottish perspective using a participatory research approach in the Early Years context of transition in Scotland for the first time.

8.9. Update Since Conclusion of Research

Having returned in August 2024 to Rainbow ELC, I was fortunate to have a discussion with the Transition Coordinator (a member of the SG) about areas agreed by the SG in June 2023. She stated that a face-to-face open information evening held in November 2023 was positively received by the parents/carers. Feedback from this event, suggested that it gave parents/carers an understanding of the transition programme that Blue Primary School had with the different ELC settings within the town of Westland, including Rainbow ELC. This information session also gave parents/carers and children the opportunity to visit Blue Primary School in person prior to making the decision about enrolling or submitting a placing request in January 2024 for their child to attend Blue Primary School. The newsletter developed by the DHT, following the final SG meeting was shared monthly from January 2024 with parents/carers and would start again in January 2025. The overall timetable has continued to be shared digitally with parents. Overall, it was reassuring that some decisions made by the SG had been implemented and positively received.

Moreover, it is worthy to note that '*How good is our early learning and childcare?*' (Education Scotland, 2016) was replaced in September 2025 with the self-evaluation document '*A Quality improvement framework for the early learning and childcare sectors: early learning and childcare*' (Education Scotland, 2025). The quality indicators within this framework will be used by both HMIE and Care Inspectorate

during inspections in ELC settings from September 2025 onwards. Interestingly there will no longer be a quality indicator dedicated to transition, as different types of transition including children moving from ELC to primary school will be integrated into a variety of quality indicators. Furthermore, communication with parents and other partners will also be embedded within a variety of quality indicators. Finally, this framework still does not indicate explicitly or implicitly preferred/desirable modes of communication with families other than suggesting verbally and in writing.

8.10. Limitations of the Study

This research is however subject to several limitations. Firstly, being an exploratory case study, the research findings are specific to the two settings involved in the 'case', thereby limiting any generalisation of the research (Denscombe, 2014). However, the recommendations discussed earlier in this chapter could be used as part of the professional dialogue within both the EY and Primary sector, with some of the recommendations being relevant to a wider EY context. Furthermore, as discussed in section 4.2. there were limitations in terms of the number of parent participants who took part in the research, due to purposive sampling (Cohen, Manion and Morrison, 2018). It was parents whose children were transitioning to Blue Primary School in August 2023 who were approached to participate in the research, and therefore a finite number of possible participants were available. In addition, there were time constraints within the data collection phase, as all the data for the research and all SG meetings needed to be completed by the summer holidays in June 2023, as the cohort of children were finishing at the nursery and transitioning to Blue Primary School. Finally, although the research set out to embrace a participatory research approach, with a particular focus on parent empowerment, I did not specifically ask the parents about this. With hindsight, I would have liked to have known from the parent participants, particularly those in the SG, whether (and to what extent) the research supported a sense of empowerment.

8.11. Recommendations for Future Study

This research has contributed to research related to early years to primary school transition from a Scottish perspective by focussing specifically on communication with

parents/carers. Future research in Scotland could embrace the participatory research approach, by focussing on a different aspect of transition alongside a longer timescale, thereby allowing for an opportunity to undertake a full participatory action research cycle. This would provide the opportunity to determine if any decisions taken forward had actually been beneficial and had a positive impact and whether any further amendments were required.

8.12. Final Reflections

As a final reflection on this research study, it is important to summarise the contribution to the EY sector and my own professional development. For the EY sector, the research has highlighted the advantages of actively giving parents/carers, ELC staff and teachers who wish to take up the offer the opportunity to voice their opinion, through adopting a participatory research approach. The opinions offered particularly by the parents were pertinent to decisions made by the SG. Therefore, it is important that we, as professionals, seek to engage and involve parents/carers in their child's journey by connecting with them in a way that allows them to be actively involved, if they choose to do so. As society moves to using more digital communication tools, settings need to be mindful of the importance of traditional communication methods, including face-to-face interaction and the human connection that this affords. We need to ensure that we communicate with parents/carers to find out exactly what they want in terms of parental engagement and how this can be enabled by recognising, regardless of the feedback received from parents/carers, that they have a legal right to be actively involved in changes that affect them and their child.

As for my own professional development, I have a greater awareness and understanding of parental engagement and barriers to parental involvement/engagement experienced by some parents. This exploratory case study has highlighted the importance of senior leaders and their necessary support to change and adapt the transition programme between Rainbow ELC and Blue Primary School, in response to data collected from the parents. In order to make changes to any parental engagement opportunities or communication methods/tools within the EY and Primary sectors in Scotland, senior leaders and staff need to be committed and

willing to make changes in light of information presented to them. Through adopting a participatory research approach, this study has highlighted positive ways that a researcher could give ownership of some of the research decisions to participants, whose insider knowledge is invaluable.

It has also been important for me to reflect on my dual positionality of being a practising teacher undertaking a professional doctorate. There were times when I needed to remind participants taking part in the research that I was speaking to them in the role as a researcher and not as a teacher or colleague. This included the meeting with the DHT who was unable to attend the second SG meeting, where the information gathered from the parent participants and the two FGs – ELC staff and the future primary one teachers was to be shared. At this meeting the DHT became annoyed at some of the information that had been shared, particularly by the parents. This was hard, as I really had to listen with empathy to her point of view, knowing that lots of information about transition had been shared with the parents. I chose to remain impartial and I was able to agree that lots of information had been shared with the parents. However, as a researcher I was also aware that there is a space between communicating with parents and being open to parental perspectives that would be challenging for many educators to navigate (not least because of constraints of time, resources and working time agreements). A further example was when no other member of the SG picked up the lack of policy awareness by either the ELC staff or the future primary one teachers at the final SG meeting. As a member of the SG and a professional, I should have had the confidence to speak up and not shy away from what I felt was important in the data. However, as a researcher I did not want to lead the SG participants in what they decided was noteworthy in the data. At times it was also hard for me to navigate my responsibilities as a professional and as a researcher (discussed in Section 4.6.). This has required me to be strong in the knowledge that, as a researcher undertaking the research study, I cannot disclose individual's contribution to the data, even with colleagues, as I am bound by research ethics. To date everyone I have shared the research findings with have accepted this stance and have not questioned me further as to the identify of participants or settings.

As part of my final reflection, it is important to reflect on the direct impact the research has had on the settings involved. In response to findings related to mode of communication, Rainbow ELC now ensure monthly newsletters are provided through the Nursery App and are also displayed in paper form at the entrance to each playroom. The ELC is also engaging parents through direct consultation activity. For example, they have used post-it notes (during drop-off times) to consult parents over their preferences related to the qualities a new practitioner should have. There are also implications of the research for others and myself as practitioners. These include ensuring that we, as professionals, seek to engage and involve parents/carers in their child's journey by connecting with them in a way that allows parents/carers to be actively involved, should they choose to do so. Practitioners also need to ensure that they communicate with parents/carers to find out how they want to be engaged, recognising that they have a legal right to be actively involved in changes that affect them and their child. It is also important that senior leaders of the research settings are supportive, understand the purpose of the research and are open to taking recommendations forward. Finally, there are implications of this research for other teacher researchers wishing to engage in a participatory research approach. These include giving consideration to the dual role that such a researcher may have from the start of the research. Other teacher researchers will want to carefully consider how they will navigate the role of researcher alongside that of insider or employee. They will need to ensure that they are confident in adhering to necessary codes of conduct and navigating any tricky situations. For example, a teacher researcher in a participatory research context will need to consider how they will deal with the push and pull of the different viewpoints/ideas. They will also need to be clear about their responsibility to ensure confidentiality of collected data when sharing research findings with senior leaders. Finally, as a practitioner who intends to continue to undertake participatory research within my practice I will be sure to carry this learning forward.

References

- Ahmed, S. K. (2024) 'The pillars of trustworthiness in qualitative research', *Journal of Medicine, Surgery and Public Health*, 2 (2024), pp. 1-4. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.glmedi.2024.100051> (Accessed: 30 August 2024).
- Ball, S. J., Maguire, M., and Braun, A. (2012) *How schools do policy: Policy enactments in secondary schools*. Routledge.
- Bates, J., Finlay, J., and O'Connor Bones, U. (2021) "Education cannot cease": the experiences of parents of primary age children (age 4-11) in Northern Ireland during school closures due to COVID-19', *Educational Review*, 23 (1), pp. 657-679. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00131911.2021.1974821> (Accessed: 25 October 2021).
- Bateson, J. (2013) 'From Nursery to Reception', in L. Todd, (ed), *Transitions in the Early Years: Working with Children and Families*. Sage, pp. 39-55.
- Bergen, N. and Labonte. R., (2020) "Everything Is Perfect, and We Have No Problems": Detecting and Limiting Social Desirability Bias in Qualitative Research', *Qualitative Health Research*, 30 (5), pp. 783-792. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1049732319889354> (Accessed: 10 May 2024).
- Berklan, S., and Hughes, T.R. (2020) 'Is innovation outpacing insight: Why schools need policy to address communication practices with parents', *eJournal of Education Policy*, 21(1), pp. 59-76. <https://doi.org/10.37803/ejepS2010> (Accessed: 25 October 2021).
- Bérubé, A., Ruel, J., April, J., and Moreau, A. (2018) 'Family preparations for school entry and the role of transition practices', *The Journal of Educational Research*, 111 (4), pp. 398-403. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00220671.2017.1284039> (Accessed: 10 October 2020).
- Borgonovi, F. and G. Montt (2012) "Parental Involvement in Selected PISA Countries and Economies", *OECD Education Working Papers*, (73), OECD Publishing. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1787/5k990rk0jsji-en> (Accessed: 10 November 2025).
- Braun, V., and Clarke, V. (2013) *Successful Qualitative Research a practical guide for beginners*. Sage.
- Braun, V., and Clarke, V. (2022) *Thematic Analysis A Practical Guide*. Sage.

British Education Research Association (2024) *Ethical Guidelines for Educational Research*. (5th edn). London: British Educational Research Association. Available at: [Ethical Guidelines for Educational Research, fifth edition \(2024\) | BERA](#) (Accessed: 20th May 2025).

Bronfenbrenner, U., 1994. Ecological models of human development, *International encyclopedia of education*, 3(2), pp. 37-43. Available at: [artikel bronfenbrenner.pdf](#) (Accessed: 30 October 2025).

Burns, M. (2018) 'Please Miss, I did that before in nursery!' *Achieving curriculum continuity and progression in children's learning across the Scottish Curriculum for Excellence - Early Level from nursery settings to Primary 1*. EdD thesis. University of Strathclyde. <https://stax.strath.ac.uk/downloads/wp988k227?locale=en>

(Accessed: 20 November 2022).

Burns, M. (2019) 'The five 'C's that contribute to a positive transition', in *Realising the ambition*. Education Scotland (2020). Crown, p. 96.

Clark, S. C. (2000) 'Work/Family Border Theory: A New Theory of Work/Family Balance', *Human Relations*, 53(6), pp. 747-770. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0018726700536001> (Accessed: 10 November 2025).

Campbell, A., McNamara, O., and Gilroy, P. (2004) *Practitioner Research and Professional Development in Education*. Paul Chapman Publishing.

Coghlan, D. and Brydon-Miller, M. (2014) *The Sage encyclopedia of action research*. 2nd edn. Sage.

Cohen, L., Manion, L., and Morrison, K. (2018) *Research Methods in Education*. 8th edn. Routledge.

Creswell, J., and Creswell, J.D. (2020) *Research Design Qualitative, Quantitative and Mixed Methods Approaches*. 5th edn. Sage.

Dawson, C. (2015) *Introduction to Research Methods A practical guide for anyone undertaking a research project*. 4th edn. Robinson.

Denscombe, M. (2014) *The Good Research Guide: For Small-scale Social Research Projects*. 5th edn. McGraw-Hill Open University Press.

Desmarchelier, R., Bryce, I., Schaffer, K., Lawrence, J., and Cantrell, K. (2022) 'Separated parents' experiences with the Australian school system: an overview, *The Australian Education Researcher*, 51, pp. 255-274. Available at: [Separated parents' experiences with the Australian school system: an overview | The Australian Educational Researcher \(springer.com\)](#) (Accessed: 11 August 2024).

Dockett, S. and Perry, B. (2014) 'Research to Policy: Transition to School Position Statement', in B. Perry, S. Dockett, and A. Petriwskyj (eds). *Transitions to School - International Research, Policy and Practice, International perspectives on early childhood education and development*, vol 9. Springer: Dordrecht, pp. 277-295. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-94-007-7350-9_20 (Accessed: 10 February 2023).

Dockett, S. and Perry, B. (2020) 'Professional linkages at the transition to school: Boundaries and linked ecologies', *Policy Futures in Education*, 19(4), pp. 459-477. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1478210320973116> (Accessed: 10 February 2023).

Dockett, S. and Perry, B. (2022) 'Defining transitions' in S. Dockett and B. Perry (eds), *Evaluating Transition to School Programs Learning from Research and Practice*. Routledge, pp. 15-26.

Dunlop, A. W. (2017) 'Transitions as a Tool for Change', in N. Ballam, B. Perry and A. Garpelin (eds), *Pedagogies of Educational Transitions*. Springer Cham, pp. 257-273. Available at: [Transitions as a Tool for Change | SpringerLink](#) (Accessed: 10 February 2023).

Dunlop, A.W. (2024) 'A Long-Longitudinal Qualitative Study: Framing Transitions through Education from Early Childhood to School Leaving' in A.W. Dunlop, S. Peters and S.L. Kagan (eds), *The Bloomsbury Handbook of Early Childhood Transition Research*. Bloomsbury Academic, Bloomsbury Publishing Plc, pp. 311-332.

Dunlop, A. W., Peters, S. and Kagan, S. L. (2024) 'Transitions at a Crossroads: Editors' Introduction', in A.W. Dunlop, S. Peters and S.L. Kagan (eds), *The Bloomsbury Handbook of Early Childhood Transition Research*. Bloomsbury Academic, Bloomsbury Publishing Plc, pp. 20-23.

Education Scotland (2015) *How good is our school?* Crown.

Education Scotland (2016) *How good is our early learning and childcare?* Crown.

Education Scotland (2019a) *Engaging parents and families - A toolkit for practitioners*. Available at: [Engaging parents and families - A toolkit for practitioners | Resources | Education Scotland](#) (Accessed: 10 January 2020).

Education Scotland (2019b) *Thematic Inspection of Empowerment for Parent and Pupil Participation*. Available at: [thematicinspectionparentpupilparticipation250619.pdf](#) (Accessed: 10 January 2020).

Education Scotland (2020) *Realising the ambition: Being Me*. Crown.

Education Scotland (2022) *Strategic Framework for: Parental Involvement, Parental Engagement, Family Learning and Learning at Home*. Livingston: Crown. Available at: [Strategic Framework for Parental Involvement, Parental Engagement, Family Learning and Learning at Home \(education.gov.scot\)](#) (Accessed: 10 February 2023).

Education Scotland (2024) *Engaging parents and families A toolkit for Practitioners*. Livingston: Crown. Available at: [Engaging parents and families - A toolkit for practitioners | Resources | Education Scotland](#) (Accessed: 10 October 2024).

Education Scotland (2025) *A quality improvement framework for the early learning and childcare sectors: early learning and childcare*. Available at: [A quality improvement framework for early learning and childcare settings](#) (Accessed 10 May 2025).

Eisner, E. W. (2002) 'From episteme to phronesis to artistry in the study and improvement of teaching', *Teaching and Teacher Education*, 18, pp. 375-385. [https://doi.org/10.1016/s0742-051x\(02\)00004-5](https://doi.org/10.1016/s0742-051x(02)00004-5) (Accessed: 9 November 2020).

Employment Relations (Flexible Working) Act 2023, c. 33. Available at: [Employment Relations \(Flexible Working\) Act 2023](#) (Accessed: 10 December 2025).

Epstein, J., Sanders, M., Sheldon, S., Simon, B., Clark Salinas, K., Rodriguez Jansorn, N., Van Voorhis, F., Martin, C., Thomas, B., Greenfield, M., Hutchins, D., and Williams, K. (2019) *School, Family and Community Partnerships Your Handbook for Action*. Corwin.

Eraut, M. (2004) 'Informal learning in the workplace', *Studies in Continuing Education*, 26 (2), pp. 247-273. <https://doi.org/10.1080/158037042000225245> (Accessed: 2 November 2020).

Eraut, M. (2014) 'Developing Knowledge for Qualified Professionals' in O. McNamara, J. Murray and M. Jones (eds), *Workplace Learning in Teacher Education International Practice and Policy*. Springer, pp. 47-72.

Fan, X., D'Amico, L.K., Kilburn, J., Jones, A., Richard, C., Zollars, L, Garrett, S. and Johnston, D. (2024) 'Perspectives of Parents and Caregivers on Kindergarten Readiness: A Focus on the Impact of a Summer Transition Program', *International Journal of Early Childhood*, 56, pp. 555–583. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s13158-023-00378-7> (Accessed: 10 April 2025).

Flexibility Works (2025) *Flex for Life 2025 Are we nearly there yet?! Analysis of Scottish parents' experiences of working flexibly and their efforts to find flexible jobs*. Available at: [Flex for Life Parents Report 2025 - Flexibility Works](#) (Accessed: 10 December 2025).

Flyvbjerg, B. (2006) 'Five misunderstandings about case-study research', *Qualitative Inquiry*, 12 (2), pp. 219-245. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1077800405284363> (Accessed: 10 February 2024).

Galletta, A. and Torre, M. E. (2019) 'Participatory Action Research in Education', *Oxford Research Encyclopedia Education*, pp. 1-28. <https://doi.org/10.1093/acrefore/9780190264093.013.557> (Accessed: 10 May 2024).

General Teaching Council for Scotland (GTCS) (2021) *The Standard for Career-Long Professional Learning An Aspirational Professional Standard for Scotland's Teachers*. Edinburgh: GTC Scotland. Available at: [Document > The Standard for Career-Long Professional Learning \(gtcs.org.uk\)](#) (Accessed: 10 October 2021).

Gilleece, L., and Eivers, E. (2018) 'Primary school websites in Ireland: how are they used to inform and involve parents', *Irish Educational Studies*, 37 (4), pp. 411-430. <https://doi.org/10.1080/03323315.2018.1498366> (Accessed: 30 November 2021).

Goodall, J. (2022) 'A framework for family engagement: Going beyond the Epstein framework' *Wales Journal of Education*, 24(2), pp. 74-96. Available at: [wje-463-goodall.pdf](#) (Accessed: 12 November 2025).

Goodall, J. (2025) 'Parent Involvement Through a Practice Theory Lens', *Education Sciences*, 15(7), 793, pp. 1-16. <https://doi.org/10.3390/educsci15070793> (Accessed: 12 November 2025).

Goodall, J., & Montgomery, C. (2014) 'Parental involvement to parental engagement: A continuum', *Educational Review*, 66(4), pp. 399–410. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00131911.2013.781576> (Accessed: 5 November 2025).

Griebing, S., and Gilbert, J. (2020) 'Examining the Value of a Summer Kindergarten Transitioning Program for Children, Families, and Schools', *School Community Journal*, 30(1), pp. 191-208. Available at: [ERIC - EJ1257659 - Examining the Value of a Summer Kindergarten Transitioning Program for Children, Families, and Schools, School Community Journal, 2020](https://eric.ed.gov/?id=EJ1257659) (Accessed: 10 October 2021).

Hall, B. (2005) 'Breaking the monopoly of knowledge: research methods, participation and development', in R. Tandon (ed), *Participatory Research: Revisiting the Roots*. Mosaic Books, pp. 9-21.

Hammarberg, K., Kirkman, M, and de Lacey, S. (2016) 'Qualitative research methods: when to use them and how to judge them', *Human Reproduction*, 31 (3), pp. 498-501. Available at: [Qualitative research methods: when to use them and how to judge them | Human Reproduction | Oxford Academic](https://academic.oup.com/humrep/advance-article-abstract/doi/10.1093/humrep/dew001/2871000) (Accessed: 1st February 2024).

Hayes, C. (2019) 'Case Study', in C. Costley and J. Fulton (eds), *Methodology for Practice Research Approaches for Professional Doctorates*. Sage, pp. 173-188.

Head, E. (2020) 'Digital technologies and parental involvement in education: the experiences of mothers of primary school-aged children', *British Journal of Sociology of Education*, 41(5), pp. 593-607. <https://doi.org/10.1080/01425692.2020.1776594> (Accessed: 25 October 2021).

Hickey, G., Brearley, S., Coldham, T., Denegri, S., Green, G., Staniszewska, S., Tembo, D., Torok, K and Turner, K. (2018) *Guidance on co-producing a research project*. INVOLVE.

Hornby, G., and Blackwell, I. (2018) 'Barriers to parental involvement in education: an update', *Educational Review*, 70 (1), pp. 109-119. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00131911.2018.1388612> (Accessed: 10 June 2023).

Huat See, B. and Gorard, S. (2015) 'The role of parents in young people's education – a critical review of the causal evidence', *Oxford Review of Education*, 41 (3), pp. 346-366. <https://doi.org/10.1080/03054985.2015.1031648> (Accessed: 29 September 2024).

Huser, C., Dockett, S. and Perry, B. (2016) 'Transition to school: revisiting the bridge metaphor', *European Early Childhood Education Research*, 24 (3), pp. 439-449. <https://doi.org/10.1080/1350293X.2015.1102414> (Accessed: 8 April 2021).

Israel, B.A., Schucoltz, A.J., Parker, A.E., Becker, A.B., Allen, A.J., and Guzman, J.R. (2008) 'Critical issues in developing and following CBPR principles', in M. Minkler and N. Wallerstein (eds), *Community-based participatory research for health: from process to outcomes*. 2nd edn. Jossey-Bass, pp. 2094-2102.

Jackson, S. (2008) 'A participatory group process to analyse qualitative data', *Progress in Community Health Partnerships: Research, Education and Action*, 2(2), pp. 161-170. <https://doi.org/10.1353/cpr.0.0010> (Accessed: 5 January 2025).

Jeynes, W. H. (2018) 'A practical model for school leaders to encourage parental involvement and parental engagement', *School Leadership & Management*, 38(2), pp. 147–163. <http://doi.org/10.1080/13632434.2018.1434767> (Accessed: 10 December 2025).

Jose, K., Banks, S., Hansen, E., Jones, R., Zubrick, S.R., Stafford, J., and Taylor, C.L. (2022) 'Parental Perspectives on Children's School Readiness: An Ethnographic Study', *Early Childhood Education Journal*, 50 (1), pp. 21–31. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10643-020-01130-9> (Accessed: 5 January 2025).

Kagan, S. L., and Neuman, M. J. (1998) 'Lessons from Three Decades of Transition Research', *The Elementary School Journal*, 98(4), pp. 365–379. Available at: <http://www.jstor.org/stable/1002193> (Accessed: 10 November 2025).

Kuusimäki, A.M., Uusitalo-Malmivaara, L., and Tirri, K. (2019) 'Parents' and Teachers' Views on Digital Communication in Finland', *Education Research International*, 2019 (1), pp. 1-7. <http://doi.org/10.1155/2019/8236786> (Accessed: 15 October 2021).

Learning and Teaching Scotland (2009) *Curriculum for Excellence*. Scottish Government.

Lechowicz, M., Jiang, Y., Tully, L. A., Burn, M. T., Collins, D. A. J., Hawes, D.J., Lenroot, R. K., Anderson, V., Doyle, F.L., Piotrowska, P. J., Frick, P. J., Moul, C., Kimonis, E. R., and Dadds, M.R. (2019) 'Enhancing Father Engagement in Parenting Programs: Translating Research into Practice Recommendations', *Australian Psychologist*, 54 (2), pp. 83-89. <https://doi.org/10.1111/ap.12361> (Accessed: 10 June 2022).

Leedy, P.D., and Ormrod, J. E. (2015) *Practical Research: Planning and Design*. 11th edn. Pearson.

Leenders, H., de Jong, J., Monfrance, M., Haelermans, C. (2019) 'Building strong parent-teacher relationships in primary education: the challenges of two-way communication', *Cambridge Journal of Education*, 49(4), pp. 519-533. <https://doi.org/10.1080/0305764X.2019.1566442> (Accessed: 10 June 2022).

Ling, L. and Ling P. (2017) *Methods and Paradigms in Education Research*. IGI Global.

Lincoln, Y. S. and Guba, E. G. (1985) *Naturalistic inquiry*. Sage.

Lohmann, M. J., Hathcote, A. R., Hogan, K. A. (2018) 'Addressing the Barriers to Family-School Collaboration: A Brief Review of the Literature and Recommendations for Practice', *International Journal of Early Childhood Special Education*, 10 (1), pp. 25-31. Available at: [\(PDF\) Addressing the Barriers to Family-School Collaboration: A Brief Review of the Literature and Recommendations](#) (Accessed: 30 April 2023).

Macaulay, A. (2017) 'Participatory research: what is the history? Has the purpose changed?', *Family Practice*, 34 (3), pp. 256-258. Available at: [Participatory research: What is the history? Has the purpose changed? | Family Practice | Oxford Academic \(oup.com\)](#) (Accessed: 12 April 2021).

Menter, I., Elliot, D., Hulme, M., Lewin, J., and Lowden, K. (2011) *A Guide to Practitioner Research in Education*. Sage.

Newby, P. (2014) *Research Methods in Education*. 2nd edn. Routledge.

Merideth, C., Cavanaugh, B., Romas, S., Ralston, N., Arias, E., Tarasawa, B., and Waggoner, J. (2022) 'Family Perceptions of Participating in a Structured Summer Kindergarten Transition Program', *Early Childhood Education*, 50 (1), pp. 1383–1394. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10643-021-01268-0> (Accessed: 10 June 2023).

Milligan, L. (2016) 'Insider-outsider-inbetweener? Researcher positioning participative methods and cross-cultural educational research', *Compare: A Journal of Comparative and International Education*, 46 (2), pp. 235-250. <https://doi.org/10.1080/03057925.2014.928510> (Accessed: 1st February 2024).

Mind (2025) *Working and Steering Groups*. Available at: [Working and steering groups | Mind - Mind](#) (Accessed: 10 February 2025).

Oke, A., Butler, J. E., and O'Neill, C. (2021) 'Identifying Barriers and Solutions to Increase Parent-Practitioner Communication in Early Childhood Care and Education Services: The Development of an Online Communication Application'. *Early Childhood Education Journal*, (49) pp. 283-293. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10643-020-01068-y> (Accessed: 10 January 2022).

Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD) (2017) *Starting Strong V: Transitions from Early Childhood Education and Care to Primary Education*. OECD Publishing.

Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD) (2020) *Early Learning and Child Well-being: A Study of Five-year-Olds in England, Estonia and the United States*. Available at: [Early Learning and Child Well-being | OECD](#) (Accessed: 10 February 2023).

Petriwskyj, A., Thorpe, K. and Tayler, C. (2005) 'Trends in construction of transition to school in three Western regions 1990–2004', *International Journal of Early Years Education*, 13(1), pp. 55–69. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09669760500048360> (Accessed: 10 November 2025).

Petticrew, M. and Roberts, H. (2006) *Systematic Reviews in the Social Sciences: A Practical Guide*. Blackwell.

Piller, I., Bruzon, A. S. and Torsh, H. (2021) 'Monolingual school websites as barriers to parent engagement', *Language and Education*, 37(3), pp. 328–345. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09500782.2021.2010744>. (Accessed: 10 April 2025).

Robson, C. and McCartan, K. (2016) *Real World Research*. 4th edn. Wiley.

Rogers, S. (2018) "'She thinks her toys don't understand Romanian": family engagement with children's learning during the transition to school', *European Early*

Childhood Education Research Journal, 26 (2), pp. 177-186.
<https://doi.org/10.1080/1350293X.2018.1441986> (Accessed: 12 May 2022).

Rogoff, B. (2003) *The Cultural Nature of Child Development*. Oxford University Press.

Scottish Executive (2006) *Scottish schools (parental involvement) act 2006 guidance*. Scottish Executive.

Scottish Government (2016) *National Improvement Framework: Parent Communication Plan A parent communication plan for the National Improvement Framework*. Available at: [Principles - National Improvement Framework: Parent Communication Plan - gov.scot \(www.gov.scot\)](https://www.gov.scot/resources/documents/2016/09/Principles_-_National_Improvement_Framework:_Parent_Communication_Plan_-_gov.scot.pdf) (Accessed: 30 January 2022).

Scottish Government (2017) *A Blueprint for 2020: The Expansion of Early Learning and Childcare in Scotland*. Available at: [A Blueprint For 2020: The Expansion of Early Learning and Childcare in Scotland](https://www.gov.scot/resources/documents/2017/03/A_Blueprint_for_2020:_The_Expansion_of_Early_Learning_and_Childcare_in_Scotland.pdf) (Accessed: 1 March 2021).

Scottish Government (2018) “*Learning together*” *Scotland’s national action plan on parental involvement, parent engagement, family learning and learning at home 2018-2021*. Available at: [Learning together: national action plan on parental involvement, engagement, family learning and learning at home 2018 – 2021 - gov.scot](https://www.gov.scot/resources/documents/2018/03/Learning_together:_national_action_plan_on_parental_involvement_engagement_family_learning_and_learning_at_home_2018_-_2021_-_gov.scot.pdf) (Accessed: 10 March 2019).

Scottish Government (2020) *Coronavirus – guidance on reducing the risks from Covid-19 in schools*. Available at: [Coronavirus \(COVID-19\): Guidance on reducing the risks from COVID-19 in schools](https://www.gov.scot/resources/documents/2020/03/Coronavirus_COVID-19_Guidance_on_reducing_the_risks_from_COVID-19_in_schools.pdf) (Accessed: 15 November 2021).

Scottish Government (2023) *Achieving Excellence and Equity: national improvement framework and improvement plan 2024*. Available at: [Education: National Improvement Framework and improvement plan 2024 - gov.scot \(www.gov.scot\)](https://www.gov.scot/resources/documents/2023/02/Education:_National_Improvement_Framework_and_improvement_plan_2024_-_gov.scot.pdf) (Accessed: 10 February 2024).

Scottish Schools (Parental Involvement) Act 2006 (asp 8). Available at: <https://www.legislation.gov.uk/asp/2006/8/> (Accessed: 13 February 2017).

Scottish Transitions as a Tool for Change Project Group (2019) *Scottish Early Childhood, Children and Families Transition Position Statement*. University of Strathclyde. Available at: [Scottish Early Childhood and Families Transitions Statement](https://www.strath.ac.uk/resources/stcrp/transition-statement/) (Accessed: 20 February 2021).

Schubotz, D. (2020) *Participatory Research Why and How to Involve People in Research*. Sage.

Smith, M. (2022) 'Enacting Parental Engagement: Policy Work in a Primary School Setting', *New Zealand Journal of Educational Studies*, 57 pp. 103-123. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s40841-021-00227-y> (Accessed: 12 April 2023).

Thomas, G. (2010) *How to do your Research Project*. Sage.

Tobin, E., Sloan, S., Symonds, J., and Devine, D. (2022) 'Family-school connectivity during transition to primary school', *Educational Research*, 64 (3), pp. 277-294. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00131881.2022.2054451> (Accessed: 10 June 2022).

Tobin, E., Symonds, J. E., Sloan, S., Devine, D., Torsney, B. M., & D'Urso, G. (2023) 'Multigroup model of transition experiences: how parents' school readiness beliefs and practices change with another child in school', *Irish Educational Studies*, 43(4), pp. 1249–1269. <https://doi.org/10.1080/03323315.2023.2220704> (Accessed: 10 April 2025).

Vogler, P., Crivello, G., and Woodhead, M. (2008) 'Early childhood transitions research: A review of concepts, theory, and practice' *Working Paper 48*. The Hague, The Netherlands: Bernard van Leer Foundation. Available at: [Early childhood transitions research A review of concepts theory and practice \[1\].pdf](#) (Accessed: 10 November 2025).

Walsh, B.A., Romo, G. and Jeon, H. J. (2018) 'Parental Perspectives on Transition to Kindergarten Videos to Promote Family Involvement', *Early Childhood Education Journal*, 46 (6), pp. 655-663. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10643-018-0890-1> (Accessed: 10 June 2022).

Warwick-Booth, L., Bagnall, A.M., and Coan, S. (2021) *Creating Participatory Research Principles, Practice and Reality*. Bristol University Press.

Winter, K., Flewitt, R., El Gemayel, S., Bunting, L., Arnott, L., Connolly, P., Dalziell, A., Gillen, J., Goodall, J., Liu, M, McLaughlin, K., Savadova, S., and Timmins, S. (2025) 'The Rights of Very Young Children in the Digital Environment of the Family Home: Findings From a UK Survey of Children 0-36 Months and Their Parents', *Children and Society*, pp. 1-17. <https://doi.org/10.1111/chso.12968> (Accessed: 10 May 2025).

Woodhouse, H., Passey, D., and Anderson, J. (2024) 'Using Digital Technologies to Build Connections between Families and Schools as Children Transition to School, *Education Sciences*, 14 (520), pp. 1 – 19. <https://doi.org/10.3390/educsci14050520> (Accessed: 11 August 2024).

Yin, R. (2018) *Case Study Research and Applications Design and Methods*. 6th edn. SAGE.

Appendix 1 - Summary of Publications Relevant to Research Study

Document Title	Published When and by Who? Is it Policy or Guidance?	What is its Purpose? Who is the Intended Audience?	Brief Summary (related to transition/ communication/digital tools/parents')	How it Informs this Research? (why is your research still required in light of the document?)
<i>How Good is our Early Learning and Childcare? (HGIOELC)</i>	Education Scotland (2016) Guidance	Purpose – Self-Evaluation Tool For – Managers/ Senior Leadership Team (SLT) Practitioners/ Teachers	This document has fifteen quality indicators (QI) including 'QI 2.6 Transition Themes' <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Quality of support for children and their families Collaborative planning and delivery Continuity and progression in learning' (Education Scotland, 2016, p. 35). 'QI 2.7 Partnerships Themes' <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Engagement of parents and carers in the life of the setting The promotion of partnerships Impact on children and families' (Education Scotland, 2016, p. 37) Quality indicators are used to grade the setting from excellent (6) to unsatisfactory (1).	As His Majesty's Inspectorate of Education (HMIE) include reporting on 2.7 partnership. My research findings might suggest how positive parental engagement may be undertaken. This includes the formation of a steering group consisting of parents and staff and/or the use of focus groups/ individual interviews to help evaluate parent/carer programmes. For 2.6, my research findings might support educational settings to enhance their current transition opportunities further, by using the parental opportunities suggested by the participants in my research. This includes communication preferences for parental engagement during their child's transition from ELC to primary school.
<i>National Improvement Framework: Parent Communication Plan A parent communication plan for the National Improvement Framework (NIF)</i>	Scottish Government (2016) Guidance	Purpose - Supporting educational settings to promote good communication with parents to address the NIF key driver – parental engagement. For - Local Authority Managers/SLT Practitioners/ Teachers	Identifies good practice principles developed when communicating with parents: <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Simplicity and clarity 2. Transparency 3. Relevance 4. Partnership 5. Flexibility and adaptation 6. Timeliness' (Scottish Government, 2016, p. 5-6) Each principle is supported by an explanation of its meaning/intent.	The document does not provide examples of how these principles might be enacted in practice, leading to settings investing time addressing these principles within their own context. My research informed findings might assist them with this. This includes what parents who voiced their opinion within my research actually thought about communication tools used between settings and themselves. Settings may use <i>Chapter Five: Findings</i> , and <i>Chapter Eight: Recommendations</i> , to review and reflect on how they communicate with parents in order to meet the needs of all their parents. This could include the importance of face-to-face communication and how to address any communication barriers including digital ones.
<i>Learning Together: Scotland's national action plan on parental involvement, parental engagement, family learning and learning at</i>	Scottish Government (2018) Guidance	Purpose - Supports Scottish Government vision '... that every parent and family should be supported to be involved and engaged in their child's education throughout their learning journey' (Scottish	An action plan to improve practice and achieve the Scottish Government vision, through 13 goals, including: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> 'Goal A (Representation): Strengthen parental representation in the life and work of early learning and childcare settings and schools' 	Although all goals have key steps and a few case studies have been included. Individual settings will still need to invest time addressing each goal. My findings, which are research informed, might assist particularly with developing parental engagement. This includes: what barriers (if any) parents face and how to

<p>home 2018-2021</p>		<p>Government, 2018, p. 3).</p> <p>For - Local Authorities Practitioners/ Teachers Managers/SLT Families</p>	<p>(Education Scotland, 2018, p. 5).</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 'Goal B (Collaboration): Expand opportunities for ALL parents to collaborate at every level of the education system' (Education Scotland, 2018, p. 8) • 'Goal C (Communication): Improve communication with parents and families' (Education Scotland, 2018, p. 10) • 'Goal D (Information technology): Support early learning and childcare settings, schools and parents to exploit the opportunities provided by information technology to improve parental involvement and engagement' (Education Scotland, 2018, p. 12) • 'Goal F (Parental Engagement): Improve support to parents and families to help them to engage with their child's learning and development' (Education Scotland, p. 16). • 'Goal H (Equalities and Equity): Work together to address barriers that limit parents' involvement and engagement' (Education Scotland, 2018, p. 22). <p>Each goal has key steps to support achieving each one via national actions; local authority; practitioner, manager and families.</p>	<p>address these; how parental voice and active involvement can positively be promoted; how adopting a participatory research approach in EY can be undertaken in practice e.g., the formation of a steering group to find out what information would be beneficial to parents on school/ELC website or what parental engagement opportunities parents find beneficial during transition programmes e.g., face-to-face; and/or digital.</p>
<p><i>Engaging parents and families – A toolkit for practitioner's</i></p>	<p>Education Scotland (2019a)</p> <p>Updated in 2024 (online)</p> <p>Guidance</p>	<p>Purpose – Support schools/ELC seeking to further develop parental engagement.</p> <p>For – Managers/ SLT Practitioners/ Teachers Parents</p>	<p>Variety of separate sections related to engaging parents and families. These include:</p> <p>Section 1: Background and definitions</p> <p>Section 2: Benefits of involving and engaging parents in their children's learning</p> <p>Section 3: Involving all parents</p> <p>Section 5: Home-school partnership (Education Scotland, 2024)</p> <p>Section 5 includes a specific discussion about how to involve parents in transitions and about developing communication and positive relationships.</p>	<p>The toolkit contains some sections with reflective questions and activities to support the enhancement of parental engagement. However, there are limited examples about how to implement the reflective questions in practice. My findings in Chapter Five and <i>Chapter Eight: Recommendations</i>, which are research informed, may suggest ways to promote parental engagement during transition from ELC to primary school, including barriers to parents being actively involved in their child's learning. Communication ideas discussed within Section 5: Home – School Partnership' although informative, does not indicate how successful these have</p>

				been. My research findings would outline how successful some of the suggestions are in reality – digital methods and face-to-face. This may support settings discussing communication between home and school/ELC.
<i>Thematic Inspection of Empowerment for Parent and Pupil Participation</i>	Education Scotland (2019b) Guidance	<p>Purpose – It draws on thematic inspections by HMIE inspectors on school empowerment undertaken in Spring 2019.</p> <p>For - Managers/SLT Practitioners/ Teachers</p>	<p>The document summarised two questions. The first question relevant to my study focussed on 'How well do schools engage parents ...in the life of the school and their child's learning to improve outcomes for children and young people? (Education Scotland, 2019b, p. 1).</p> <p>The key messages identified included: positive relationships and trust between schools and parents; inconsistent capacity and willingness to involve parents to improve outcomes for children; more work needed by schools to 'illustrate to parents how their views influence and lead to school improvement' (Education, Scotland, 2019b, p. 5); different communication methods used to communicate with parents.</p> <p>The findings also identified that digital technology is used more to communicate with parents.</p> <p>For Scottish schools in relation to parent and pupil participation the inspections 'identified six dimensions of empowerment which are important levers for change... autonomy, professional learning, participation and engagement, collaboration, resources and impact' (Education Scotland, 2019b, p.15).</p>	<p>As HMIE inspections will report on parental engagement undertaken by educational settings, my research informed findings in Chapter Five and recommendations in Chapter Eight might support settings with strengthening the empowerment of parents. This may include the adoption of a participatory research approach via consultation with parents and the formation of a steering group thereby specifically addressing the dimensions participation and engagement and collaboration.</p>
<i>Realising the Ambition: Being Me</i>	Education Scotland (2020) Guidance	<p>Purpose – Guidance for ELC/early stages of primary school</p> <p>For – Local Authorities Managers/SLT Practitioners/ Teachers</p>	<p>Section 8 is dedicated to transition including highlighting the five 'C' s for a positive transition - collaboration, communication, culture, consistency, and child-centred (Burns, 2019).</p> <p>Key features discussed for transition to school included parents being active participants in priming activities for ELC to primary school transitions.</p>	<p>The five 'C's (Burns, 2019) does not include any examples of how these could be interpreted, leading to each setting investing time in developing examples for each. My research findings (Chapter Five) which are research informed might assist. This includes communication tools which parents feel are suitable to be used to communicate with them during transition programmes.</p> <p>The importance of priming events is acknowledged, but no guidance of how to undertake these or what they could be are included. My research informed recommendations (Chapter</p>

				Eight) might state opportunities that within their own school context might be taken forward. My research outlines ways in which parents and other professionals can be involved in making the priming events relevant including through consultation.
<i>Strategic Framework for: Parental Involvement, Parental Engagement, Family Learning and Learning at Home</i>	Education Scotland (2022) Guidance	<p>Purpose – Practical guidance for practitioners about ‘what effective parental involvement, parental engagement, family learning and learning at home should look like in Scotland’ (Education Scotland, 2022, p. 18).</p> <p>For – Managers/SLT Practitioners/ Teachers</p>	<p>The framework outlines knowledge that people need to have when engaging with parents and families. There are different sections including Section Five – ‘what do we all need to know?’ This section focussed on different areas including transition, outlining what working with parents and families should look like in practice. Within transition we should ‘recognise the vital role of parents in supporting their children and young people at key transitions ...work with parents to promote positive transition processes and embed effective parental involvement and engagement structures’ (Education Scotland, 2022, p. 25). Another focus area was effective communication methods. Within this area we should ‘consider a variety of methods and ways to communicate with parents and families’ (Education Scotland, 2022, p. 25). This includes testing out different approaches when communicating with parents and families. Section Four included a timeline of barriers to engaging and involving parents and families, making reference to a 2019 Parental Involvement/Engagement Census by Education Scotland. In 2019 barriers included:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • ‘Work commitments • Caring for younger children • Lack of confidence • Not aware of opportunities’ <p>(Education Scotland, 2022, p. 14).</p>	<p>Section Five of the guidance discusses what we need to do when supporting and/or delivering parental engagement including transition and effective communication. However, it does not give examples of how this might be achieved in practice. With my research being research informed, <i>Chapter Five: Findings</i> and <i>Chapter Eight: Recommendations</i> might suggest some answers to the points outlined. Some of the barriers identified from the 2019 Census, may within my research be confirmed as still parental barriers today with the recommendations (Chapter Eight) suggesting ways to address these.</p>
<i>Achieving Excellence and Equity - 2024 National Improvement Framework (NIF) and Improvement Plan</i>	Scottish Government (2023) Policy	<p>Purpose – Supporting educational settings to promote equity and excellence.</p> <p>For - Local Authority Managers/SLT Practitioners/ Teachers</p>	<p>NIF is updated yearly focussing on six drivers. ‘The drivers of improvement in the outcomes achieved by children and young people through education are: to improve outcomes for children:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • School and ELC leadership 	<p>This policy itself does not include any examples of how to develop each driver. One case study based on an HMIE Inspection is included with each driver. Although individual settings will still need to spend time developing plans to address each driver within their own context. Whereas, my research which is research</p>

			<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Teacher and practitioner professionalism • Parent/carer engagement and family learning • Curriculum and assessment • School and ELC improvement • Performance information' <p>(Scottish Government, 2023, p. 5). The driver 'parent/carer engagement and family learning' replaced 'parent/carer involvement and engagement' that had been present in previous versions of the NIF.</p>	<p>informed, might assist with the parent/carer engagement and family learning driver. My research discusses ways that parents could be actively involved during transition programmes and why. The recommendations, (Chapter Eight) may support ELC/schools discussing any changes to their current practice within the area of parental engagement and communication with parents.</p>
--	--	--	---	--

Appendix 2 – Process for Searching and Selection of Literature Articles

Database	Search Terms	Search Result Number	Number & Rationale for including	Rationale for excluding
Education Source	Digital communication with parents AND Academic Journal AND English	5	0 Included	Excluded – related to pre-service teachers; school system not similar to Western countries; not relevant to topic.
	Communication with parents in education AND Academic Journal AND English	66	1 Included – reference made to parent-teacher partnership/relationship. <i>Leenders et al., (2019)</i>	Excluded –not linked to education; ASN specific; out with educational stages – secondary; topic not pertinent to research; teacher training.
	School communication with parents AND Academic Journal AND English	70	2 Included – discussed specifically communication with parents. <i>Berklan and Hughes (2020)</i> <i>Walsh, Romo and Jeon (2018)</i>	Excluded – ASN specific; ESL; School system not similar to Western countries; cultural context; study timescale; parental engagement too wide e.g., K - year 12; periodical and not peer reviewed.
	Parent engagement during transition AND Academic Journal AND English	1	0	Excluded – topic not relevant to own study.
	Parent Involvement AND Transition AND Academic Journal AND English	31	1 included – discussed parent involvement relevant to research transition stage. <i>Fan et al., (2023)</i>	Excluded – School system not similar to Western countries; out with ELC and primary school transition; not education.
	Parent participation AND Transition AND Academic Journal AND English	38	4 included but 2 already included in another search above. They discussed transition to primary school and parent involvement. <i>Rogers (2018);</i> <i>Woodhouse, Passey and Anderson (2024)</i> <i>Fan et al., (2023)</i> <i>Walsh, Romo and Jeon (2018)</i>	Excluded – ASN specific; out with ELC and primary school transition; not education; school system not similar to Western countries; comparison contexts/cultural background/ socio-economic specific; parental involvement too wide e.g., ELC to high school; child specific; not peer reviewed.
	Barriers to parent engagement in education AND Academic Journal AND English	0		0
	Home/school communication AND Academic Journal AND English	22	1 included as it discussed home to school communication and included age range covered by research. <i>Bates, Finlay and O'Connor Bones (2021)</i>	Excluded - not relevant to research focus; not age group focussed by research; not Western education system.
	Transition to primary school	173	1 included but already included in previous	Excluded - not relevant to research focus; not age

	AND Academic Journal AND English		search. It discussed perspectives of parents and caregivers. <i>Fan et al., (2023)</i>	group covered within research; not Western education system.
SpringerLink	Digital communication with parents AND Education AND English AND Research articles AND Education general	483	1 Included – discussed communication with parents through technology. <i>Oke, Butler and O'Neill (2021)</i>	Excluded – school system not similar to Western countries; ASN specific; K-year 12; ECEC specific; non education; teacher training; child specific; socio-economic specific.
	Communication with parents during transition to primary school AND Education AND English AND Research article AND Education general	327	3 Included – discussed transition to primary school and home/school communication. <i>Desmarchelier et al., (2022)</i> <i>Lechowicz et al., (2019);</i> <i>Merideth et al., (2022)</i>	Excluded – school system not similar to Western countries; ASN specific; out with ELC to primary school transition; non education; teacher training; child specific; socio-economic specific; K-year 12.
	School communication with parents during transition to primary school AND Education AND English AND Research article AND Education general	327	5 included but all already included in other searches. Discussed – transition to primary school; Primary One; home/school communication. <i>Desmarchelier et al., (2022)</i> <i>Lechowicz et al., (2019)</i> <i>Merideth et al., (2022)</i> <i>Fan et al., (2023)</i> <i>Walsh, Romo and Jeon (2018)</i>	Excluded – school system not similar to Western countries; ASN specific; out with ELC to primary school transition; ECEC specific; non education; teacher training; child specific; socio-economic specific; K-year 12.
	Parent engagement during transition AND Education AND English AND Research article AND Education general	305	4 included but all already included in searches above. Discussed – parental engagement; home/school communication; transition to school. <i>Desmarchelier et al., (2022)</i> <i>Lechowicz et al., (2019)</i> <i>Merideth et al., (2022)</i> <i>Fan et al., (2023)</i> <i>Walsh, Romo and Jeon (2018)</i>	Excluded – school system not similar to Western countries; ASN specific; out with ELC to primary school transition; context not relevant to own study; non education; teacher training; child specific; socio-economic specific; K-year 12; out with age range (secondary school or later).
	Parent involvement AND Education AND English AND Research article AND Education general	219	6 included but only 1 not already included in previous searches. They discussed home/school communication; parental involvement; transition programmes involving parents. <i>Desmarchelier et al., (2022)</i> <i>Lechowicz et al., (2019)</i> <i>Merideth et al., (2022)</i> <i>Fan et al., (2023)</i> <i>Walsh, Romo and Jeon (2018)</i> <i>Dockett and Perry (2020)</i>	Excluded – school system not similar to Western countries; ASN specific; out with ELC to primary school transition; context not relevant to own study; non education; teacher training; child specific; socio-economic specific; K-year 12; out with age range (secondary school or later).

	Family engagement during transition AND Education AND English AND Research article AND Education general	531	In total 5 included but all already included within other searches. They discussed - transition to primary school; Primary One; parental engagement. <i>Desmarchelier et al., (2022)</i> <i>Lechowicz et al., (2019)</i> <i>Merideth et al., (2022)</i> <i>Fan et al., (2023)</i> <i>Walsh, Romo and Jeon (2018)</i>	Excluded – school system not similar to Western countries; ASN specific; out with ELC to primary school transition; context not relevant to own study; non education; teacher training; child specific; socio-economic specific; K-year 12; out with age range (secondary school or later); under 3 participants.
	Barriers to parental engagement during transition AND Education AND English AND Research article AND Education general	94	3 with all included in previous searches. They discussed barriers to parent involvement; transition to primary school. <i>Desmarchelier et al., (2022)</i> <i>Lechowicz et al., (2019)</i> <i>Walsh, Romo and Jeon (2018)</i>	Excluded – school system not similar to Western countries; ASN specific; out with ELC to primary school transition; ESL; ASN; ECEC specific; non education; teacher training; child specific; education area specific e.g. STEM.
	Barriers to parental involvement during transition AND Education AND English AND Research article AND Education general	79	4 included but already included in previous searches. They discussed barriers to parent involvement; transition to primary school. <i>Desmarchelier et al., (2022)</i> <i>Lechowicz et al., (2019)</i> <i>Walsh, Romo and Jeon (2018)</i> <i>Merideth et al., (2022)</i>	Excluded – school system not similar to Western countries; ASN specific; out with ELC to primary school transition; ESL; ASN; ECEC specific; non education; teacher training; child specific; education area specific e.g. STEM.
	Home to school communication AND Education AND English AND Research article AND Education general	1384 (only able to access 1000)	4 included but already included in previous searches. They discussed parent involvement; transition to school. <i>Desmarchelier et al., (2022)</i> <i>Fan et al., (2023)</i> <i>Merideth et al., (2022)</i> <i>Lechowicz et al., (2019)</i>	Excluded – school system not similar to Western countries; ASN specific; out with ELC to primary school transition; context not relevant to own study; non education; teacher training; child specific; socio-economic specific; K-year 12; out with age range (secondary school or later).
	Transition to primary school AND Education AND English AND Research article AND Education general	1009	3 included but already included in previous searches. They discussed transition to primary school; parental involvement. <i>Fan et al., (2023)</i> <i>Desmarchelier et al., (2022)</i> <i>Merideth et al., (2022)</i>	Excluded – school system not similar to Western countries; ASN specific; out with ELC to primary school transition; context not relevant to own study; non education; teacher training; child specific; socio-economic specific; out with age range (secondary school or later).
Taylor and Francis	Barriers to parent engagement during transition AND Review Article	87	0	Excluded – context not relevant to my research; system not similar to Western countries education system; out with

	AND English AND Education			ELC to primary school transition; non-education.
	Parent engagement during transition AND Review Article AND English AND Education	221	0	Excluded – context not relevant to my research; system not similar to Western countries education system; out with ELC to primary school transition; non-education.
	Parent involvement AND Review Article AND English AND Education	245	0	Excluded – context not relevant to my research; system not similar to Western countries education system; out with ELC to primary school transition; non-education.
	Family Engagement AND Review Article AND English AND Education	215	0	Excluded – context not relevant to my research; system not similar to Western countries education system; out with ELC to primary school transition; non-education.
	School communication during transition to primary school AND Review Article AND English AND Education	234	0	Excluded – context not relevant to my research; system not similar to Western countries education system; out with ELC to primary school transition; non-education.
	Communication during transition to primary school AND Review Article AND English AND Education	234	0	Excluded – context not relevant to my research; system not similar to Western countries education system; out with ELC to primary school transition; non-education.
	Digital communication with parents AND Review Article AND English AND Education	146	0	Excluded – context not relevant to my research; system not similar to Western countries education system; non-education.
	Home to school communication AND Review article AND English AND Education AND Abstract	116	3 included with 1 already included in previous searches. They discussed communication between home and school. <i>Tobin et al., (2022)</i> <i>Bates, Finlay and O'Connor Bones (2021)</i> <i>Piller, Bruzon and Torsh (2021)</i>	Excluded – context not relevant to my research; system not similar to Western countries education system; non-education.
	Transition to primary school AND Review article AND English AND Education AND Abstract	182	1 included – discussed transition to school. <i>Tobin et al., (2023)</i>	Excluded – context not relevant to my research; system not similar to Western countries education system; non-education.

UWS Research Portal	Digital Communication with parents AND Article	69	0	Excluded – not relevant to own research study context.
	Communication with parents in education AND Article AND School of Education and Social Sciences	75	0	Excluded – not relevant to own research study context.
	Barriers to parent engagement during transition AND Article AND School of Education and Social Sciences	16	0	Excluded – not relevant to own research study context.
	Parent participation during transition AND Article AND School of Education and Social Sciences	48	0	Excluded – not relevant to own research study context.
	Transition to primary school AND Article AND School of Education and Social Sciences	4	0	Excluded – not relevant to own research study context.
	Home to school communication AND Article AND School of Education and Social Sciences	158	0	Excluded – not relevant to own research study context; not western education system.
ProQuest	Digital communication with parents (within abstract) AND English AND Peer Reviewed	188	2 included but 1 already included in previous search. They discussed digital communication. <i>Woodhouse, Passey and Anderson (2024)</i> <i>Kuusimäki, Uusitalo-Malmivaara and Tirri (2019)</i>	Excluded - health based; not western education; ASN; out with age range of research.
	Digital communication with parents AND During transition to primary school (within abstract) AND English AND Peer Reviewed	3	0	Excluded - health or religion based.
	Communication with parents in education (within abstract) AND English AND Peer reviewed AND Journals in Education	176	0	Excluded – health context; not relevant to research topic; out with age range.
	Communication with parents in education (within abstract) AND During transition to primary school	3	0	Excluded – health or religion based.

	AND English AND Peer reviewed AND Journals in Education			
	School communication with parents in education (within abstract) AND English AND Peer reviewed AND Journals in Education	322	0	Excluded – out with age range of research; health based; not education.
	School communication with parents in education (within abstract) AND during transition to primary school AND English AND Peer reviewed AND Journals in Education	3	0	Excluded – health based; out with age range of research.
	Parent engagement during transition (within abstract) AND English AND Scholarly Journals AND Peer reviewed	35	0	Excluded - health based; not education, out with age range of research.
	Parent involvement during transition (within abstract) AND English AND Scholarly Journals AND Peer reviewed	50	1 included but already included in previous search. It discussed transition and parental involvement. <i>Merideth et al., (2022)</i>	Excluded - health based, not education; out with age range of research.
	Parent participation during transition (within abstract) AND English AND Scholarly Journals AND Peer reviewed	41	0	Excluded – health based; not relevant to own research context.
	Barriers to parent engagement in education (within abstract) AND English AND Scholarly Journals AND Peer reviewed	32	0	Excluded – health based; not research topic; not western education system.
Web of Science	Communication with parents (within abstract) AND English AND Education Educational Research AND	56	0	Excluded – not western education system; not within age range of research.

	UK, USA, Canada, Australia, New Zealand and European Countries AND Relevant journals			
Web of Science	School communication with parents in education (within abstract) AND English AND Article AND Education Educational Research	401	4 included but 3 already included in previous searches. They discussed communication between home and school. <i>Merideth et al., (2022)</i> <i>Desmarchelier et al., (2022)</i> <i>Bates, Finlay and O'Connor Bones (2021)</i> <i>Head (2020)</i>	Excluded – health based; not correct age group; topic not relevant to research; not Western education system.
	School communication with parents (within abstract) AND English AND Article AND Education Educational Research AND UK, USA, Canada, Australia, New Zealand and European Countries AND Relevant journals	21	1 included but already mentioned in previous searches. It discusses communication with parents and their perspectives. <i>Merideth et al., (2022)</i>	Excluded – health based; not correct age group; topic not relevant to research; not Western education system.
	Barriers to engagement in education (within abstract) AND English AND Article AND Education Educational Research	71	0	Excluded – health based; not correct age group; topic not relevant to research; not Western education system.
	Parent engagement during transition (within abstract) AND English AND Article AND Education Educational Research	29	1 included but already included in previous searches. It talks about parent engagement during transition to school. <i>Tobin et. al., (2023)</i>	Excluded – health based; not correct age group; topic not relevant to research; not Western education system.
	Parent involvement during transition (within abstract) AND English AND Article AND Education Educational Research	34	1 included but already included in previous searches. It talks about parent involvement during transition to school. <i>Merideth et al., (2022)</i>	Excluded – health based; not correct age group; topic not relevant to research; not Western education system.
	Parent participation during transition (within abstract) AND English AND Article AND	28	1 included but already included in previous searches. It talks about parent engagement during transition to school. <i>Tobin et. al., (2022)</i>	Excluded – health based; not correct age group; topic not relevant to research; not Western education system.

	Education Educational Research			
	Digital communication with parents (within abstract) AND English AND Article AND Education Educational Research	468	3 included but all already included in previous searches. They discussed communication with parents particularly digital. <i>Woodhouse, Passey and Anderson (2024)</i> <i>Kuusimäki, Uusitalo-Malmivaara and Tirri (2019)</i> <i>Head (2020)</i>	Excluded – health based; not correct age group; topic not relevant to research; not Western education system.
	Home to School (within abstract) AND English AND Article AND Education Educational Research AND UK, USA, Canada, Australia, New Zealand and European Countries	296	6 included but all already included in previous searches. They discussed communication between home and school within research. <i>Bates, Finlay and O'Connor Bones (2021)</i> <i>Head (2020)</i> <i>Woodhouse, Passey and Anderson (2024)</i> <i>Tobin et al., (2022)</i> <i>Piller, Bruzon and Torsh (2021)</i> <i>Merideth et al., (2022)</i>	Excluded – health based; not correct age group; topic not relevant to research; not Western education system.
	Transition to primary school (within abstract) AND English AND Article AND Education Educational Research AND UK, USA, Canada, Australia, New Zealand and European Countries	479	2 included but both already included in previous searches. They discussed digital communication or transition to school. <i>Woodhouse, Passey and Anderson (2024)</i> <i>Tobin et al., (2022)</i>	Excluded – health based; not correct age group; topic not relevant to research; not Western education system.
Scopus	Digital communication with parents and transition to primary school (abstract and articles) AND Articles AND UK, USA, Canada, New Zealand, Australia and European Countries	2	1 included but already included in previous searches. It discusses digital communication. <i>Woodhouse, Passey and Anderson (2024)</i>	Excluded - not relevant to education.
	Communication with parents (abstract and title) AND Transition AND Articles AND UK, USA, Canada, New Zealand, Australia and European Countries	43	2 included but already included in previous searches. They discuss communication with parents. <i>Woodhouse, Passey and Anderson (2024)</i> <i>Tobin et al., (2022)</i>	Excluded -health related, out with age range; topic not relevant to research focus; not primary school transition.

	Barriers and parent engagement in education AND Articles AND UK, USA, Canada, New Zealand, Australia and European Countries	297	1 included but already included on previous searches. It discusses communication with parents through websites. <i>Piller, Bruzon and Torsh (2021)</i>	Excluded -health related, out with age range; topic not relevant to research focus; not primary school transition.
	Parent engagement during transition to primary school AND Articles AND UK, USA, Canada, New Zealand, Australia and European Countries	26	2 included but already included in previous searches. They discussed transition to school. <i>Woodhouse, Passey and Anderson (2024)</i> <i>Tobin et al., (2022)</i>	Excluded -health related, out with age range; topic not relevant to research focus; not primary school transition.
	Parent involvement during transition to primary school AND Articles AND UK, USA, Canada, New Zealand, Australia and European Countries	30	0	Excluded -health related, out with age range; topic not relevant to research focus; not primary school transition.
	Family engagement during transition to primary school AND Articles AND UK, USA, Canada, New Zealand, Australia and European Countries	27	3 included but already included in previous searches. They discussed transition to school. <i>Woodhouse, Passey and Anderson (2024)</i> <i>Tobin et al., (2022)</i> <i>Tobin et al., (2023)</i>	Excluded -health related, out with age range; topic not relevant to research focus; not primary school transition.
	Transition to primary school (abstract and title) AND Article AND English AND Social Science AND Keywords – transition, preschool, school	359	3 included but already included in previous searches. They discussed transition to school. <i>Woodhouse, Passey and Anderson (2024)</i> <i>Tobin et al., (2023)</i> <i>Dockett and Perry (2020)</i>	Excluded -health related, out with age range; topic not relevant to research focus; not primary school transition.
	Home to school communication AND Article AND English AND Social Science AND Keywords – transition, preschool, school	40	0	Excluded -health related, out with age range; topic not relevant to research focus; not primary school transition.
Education in the North Journals	Looking at titles and abstracts within all journal articles	2018-present	0	Excluded - None of the articles were relevant to the research focus.
International Journal of Educational and Life Transitions	Looking at titles and abstracts within all journal articles	2018-present	0	None of the articles were relevant to research focus. Many of the research articles were primary to secondary transition.
Academic research recommended from academics and supervisors	Smith (2022) Ball, Maguire and Braun (2012)	3	3 - Included as both discussed policy and parental engagement.	

	Hornby and Blackwell (2018)			
Literature referred to in previous Academic work	Griebling and Gilbert (2020) Bérubé <i>et al.</i> , (2018) Epstein <i>et al.</i> , (2019) Dunlop (2017) Bateson (2013) Dockett and Perry (2014) Huser, Dockett and Perry (2016) Lohmann, Hathcote and Hogan (2018)	8	8 - Included as they discussed specifically communication or parental engagement regardless of methodology.	
Other	Winter <i>et al.</i> , (2025)	1	1 – interesting current information about number of parents access to a smartphone from a UK perspective.	

Appendix 3 – ELC Letter

School of Education and Social Studies

LETTER TO HEAD OF ESTABLISHMENT

Dear Head of Establishment

I am a Professional Doctorate student studying at the University of the West of Scotland and as you will be aware I am entering the research phase of the Professional Doctorate programme. The focus for my research is the communication and parental engagement during the transition from the Early Learning and Childcare (ELC) to primary school. I am therefore writing to ask for permission to use your ELC as the basis for my research into communication tools that are pertinent to support parental engagement during the transition from ELC to primary school.

Information for the research will be gathered via the development of a steering group consisting of a small group of parents/carers whose children will be starting primary school in August 2023 and members of staff from the ELC and the largest feeder primary school. In addition, focus groups/semi-structured interviews with these and other parents/carers of children starting primary school in August 2023 about communication methods and parental engagement using them and any possible changes to the current transition programme related to the data collected. I will also be conducting a focus group with staff from Blue Primary School and the ELC to discuss from the ELC and primary school perspective. The participants will also be asked to keep notes of their engagement in the participatory research process.

I would be looking to use a space within the ELC for the steering group meetings and focus group/semi-structured interviews. If you are willing to host this research in your ELC please email me at [REDACTED]. I will then approach the participants and ask if they would like to participate in the research.

The research will have possible benefits as it will provide participants with the opportunity to give their own opinion and experiences of communication and parental engagement, they would like to have during the transition of their children from ELC to primary school. Resulting conclusions may highlight changes that can be implemented to enhance the current transition programme and actively involving

parents in this process. All participants will be anonymous and have the right to withdraw from the research within the data collection phase.

My lead supervisor is Dr. Carole Bignell, a lecturer from the School of Education and Social Studies at the University of the West of Scotland. You can contact my lead supervisor via email [REDACTED] or myself [REDACTED] at any stage of the research should you have any questions.

Yours sincerely

Carol Strom

Appendix 4 – Primary School Letter

School of Education and Social Studies

LETTER TO HEAD TEACHER

Dear Head Teacher

I am a Professional Doctorate student studying at the University of the West of Scotland and as you will be aware I am entering the research phase of the Professional Doctorate programme. The focus for my research is the communication and parental engagement during the transition from the Early Learning and Childcare (ELC) to primary school. I am therefore writing to ask for permission to involve members of staff within your primary school who are pertinent to my research – staff who are involved in the transition programme between Rainbow ELC and Blue Primary School.

Information for the research will be gathered via the development of a steering group consisting of a small group of parents whose children will be starting primary school in August 2023 and members of staff from the ELC and at least one representative from Blue Primary School. I would also like to conduct a focus group with staff from Blue Primary School and the ELC to discuss from the ELC and primary school perspective. The participants will also be asked to keep notes of their engagement in the participatory research process.

I would be looking to use a space within the school to host the focus group/semi-structured interviews. If you are willing to allow the school to take part, please email me at [REDACTED]. I will then approach the participants and ask if they would like to participate in the research.

The research will have possible benefits as it will provide participants with the opportunity to give their own opinion and experiences of communication and parental engagement, they would like to have during the transition of their children from ELC to primary school. Resulting conclusions may highlight changes that can be implemented to enhance the current transition programme and actively involving parents in this process. All participants will be anonymous and have the right to withdraw from the research within the data collection phase.

My lead supervisor is Dr. Carole Bignell, a lecturer from the School of Education and Social Studies at the University of the West of Scotland. You can contact my lead supervisor via email [REDACTED] [REDACTED] [REDACTED] any stage of the research should you have any questions.

Yours sincerely

Carol Strom

Appendix 5 – Participant Information Sheet – Steering Group (Parents)

School of Education and Social Sciences

Participant Information Sheet – Steering Group (Parents)

You are being invited to take part in a research study. Before you decide, it is important for you to understand why the research is being done and what it will involve. Please take time to read the following information carefully and discuss it with others if you wish. Please ask me if there is anything that is not clear or if you would like more information. Take time to decide whether or not you wish to take part.

Title of the study: Communication and Parental Engagement during the Transition from Early Learning and Childcare (ELC) to Primary.

Introduction

This research project is run by Carol Strom, Professional Doctorate student at the School of Education and Social Sciences, University of the West of Scotland.

What is the purpose of this study?

This research study addresses the following question:

‘What communication tools are pertinent to successfully supporting parental engagement during the transition from Early Learning and Childcare to primary school?’

Do you have to take a part?

It is up to you to decide whether or not to take part and you have the right to decline the offer to take part in this study without giving a reason. If you do decide to take part you will be given this information sheet to keep and be asked to sign a consent form. If you decide to take part you are free to withdraw up until 2 weeks after the date of the last steering group meeting without giving a reason. Should you wish to do this please contact Carol Strom or the Lead Supervisor Dr. Carole Bignell.

What will you do in this research project?

You will become a member of a steering group that will look to actively participate in helping with my research – including looking at and agreeing questions that I am planning to ask parents, ELC and primary teaching staff in the focus groups/interviews. Once the data has been collected from the focus groups/interviews and analysed, the steering group members will be invited to join me in reviewing the findings and forming a plan for proposed changes to the current transition programme in terms of the communication tools used and the parental engagement opportunities. As part of the steering group, we will be looking for notes to be kept reflecting upon your involvement in the group. It is envisaged that steering group meetings will be held on 4 occasions between January and June, with each meeting lasting no more than one and a half hours.

Why have you been invited to take part?

Your child is currently in their pre-school year and will be starting primary school in August 2023.

What are the potential risks to you in taking part?

There will be no risks to you in taking part in this research project, except taking time to participate in the steering group and completing notes about your involvement in the group.

What will happen to the information I provide?

Data collected from steering group meetings will be recorded in the form of short reflective notes with points recorded not being attributed to individuals, thus ensuring anonymity. Participants of the steering group will be asked to ensure that all discussions during these meetings remain confidential.

Data collected by the researcher from focus groups/semi-structured interviews that the steering group will be looking at will be anonymised prior to being shared with the steering group to ensure confidentiality. Notes taken by steering group participants will be shared with the researcher only at the end of each meeting and will be destroyed within three years of the notes being recorded by them. All data associated with this research project will be securely stored via the UWS One Drive and will be deleted within 36 months of being collected.

All the data collected in this research will be treated in accordance with the Data Protection Act (1998) and the UWS Code of Ethics. Your personal data such as contact details and reflective notes will be processed for the purposes outlined in this notice. The legal basis that would be used to process your personal data will be the provision

of your consent. Your personal data will be processed so long as it is required for the research project but not exceeding three years. We will do our best to minimise the processing of personal data wherever possible. We will anonymise or pseudonymise the personal data you provided within 30 days.

If you are concerned about how your personal data is being processed, please contact UWS in the first instance at dataprotection@uws.ac.uk. If you remain unsatisfied, you may wish to contact the Information Commissioner's Office (ICO). Contact details, and details of data subject rights, are available on the ICO website at: <https://ico.org.uk/for-organisations/data-protection-reform/overview-of-the-gdpr/individuals-rights/>

What will happen to the results of the research study?

The results of the research study will be presented as a thesis for the award of a Professional Doctorate and may form part of a presentation to interested parties thereafter or part of a publication.

Who has reviewed the study?

The study has been reviewed by the University of the West of Scotland Education and Social Sciences (ESS) Ethics Committee.

What will happen next?

If you are happy to be involved in the research, you will be asked to sign a consent form to confirm this. I am extremely grateful for your involvement. Thanks, are also expressed to those who have taken the time to read this information sheet but who now choose not to take part.

If you have any questions/concerns, during or after the investigation, or wish to contact an independent person to whom any questions may be directed or further information may be sought from, please contact:

Dr. Carole Bignell
Lead Supervisor
University of the West of Scotland
[REDACTED]

Researcher Contact Details:
Carol Strom
School of Education and Social Sciences
[REDACTED]

Appendix 6 - Consent Forms (Steering Group)

RESEARCH INFORMED CONSENT FORM (STEERING GROUP)

Title of Project: Communication and Parental Engagement during the Transition from Early Learning and Childcare (ELC) to Primary School.

Ethics Application Number: 18022

Investigators names: Carol Strom

Researcher Email: [REDACTED]

You have been invited to take part in a study on the communication tools that are pertinent to supporting parental engagement during the transition of children from an Early Learning and Childcare setting to primary school. By completing this form and agreeing to give your full consent, you agree that you have read and understood the participant information sheet and understand what is being asked of you in this study.

Please read the following statements and, if you agree, initial the corresponding box to confirm your agreement

	Initial below:
I confirm that I have read and understood the participant information sheet and instruction sheet for the study. I have had the opportunity to consider the information, ask questions and have had these answered satisfactorily.	
I understand that my participation is voluntary, and I need not answer any questions, and that I am free to withdraw up until 2 weeks after the date of the last steering group meeting without giving any reason.	
I understand that the information I give is confidential and any publications or presentations resulting from this work will not identify me personally unless my prior permission has been given.	
I consent to the processing of personal information I may provide e.g. contact details, sex, background etc. for the purposes explained to me. I understand that such information will be handled in accordance with all applicable data protection legislation.	
I agree to become involved in identifying actions from the research and be involved in the dissemination of research findings should I wish to do so.	
I freely agree to participate in this study and complete reflective notes of my involvement in steering group meetings.	
I agree to the researcher completing written notes of the steering group meetings.	

Name of participant (block capitals):

Date:

Signature:

Name of researcher (block capitals):

Date:

Signature:

Appendix 7 - Participant Information Sheet – Steering Group (ELC/Primary Staff)

School of Education and Social Sciences

You are being invited to take part in a research study. Before you decide, it is important for you to understand why the research is being done and what it will involve. Please take time to read the following information carefully and discuss it with others if you wish. Please ask me if there is anything that is not clear or if you would like more information. Take time to decide whether or not you wish to take part.

Title of the study: Communication and Parental Engagement during the Transition from Early Learning and Childcare (ELC) to Primary.

Introduction

This research project is run by Carol Strom, Professional Doctorate student at the School of Education and Social Sciences, University of the West of Scotland.

What is the purpose of this study?

This research study addresses the following question:

‘What communication tools are pertinent to successfully supporting parental engagement during the transition from Early Learning and Childcare to primary school?’

Do you have to take a part?

It is up to you to decide whether or not to take part and you have the right to decline the offer to take part in this study without giving a reason. If you do decide to take part you will be given this information sheet to keep and be asked to sign a consent form. If you decide to take part you are free to withdraw up until 2 weeks after the date of the last steering group meeting without giving a reason. Should you wish to do this please contact Carol Strom or the Lead Supervisor Dr. Carole Bignell.

What will you do in this research project?

You will become a member of a steering group that will look to actively participate in helping with my research – including looking at and agreeing questions that I am planning to ask parents, ELC and primary teaching staff in the focus groups/interviews. Once the data has been collected from the focus groups/interviews and analysed

steering group members will be invited to join me in reviewing the findings and forming a plan for proposed changes to the current transition programme in terms of the communication tools used and the parental engagement opportunities. As part of the steering group, we will be looking for notes to be kept reflecting upon your involvement in the group. It is envisaged that steering group meetings will be held on 4 occasions between January and June, with each meeting lasting no more than one and a half hours.

Why have you been invited to take part?

You are actively involved in the transition programmes and will be involved in the transition of children starting primary school in August 2023.

What are the potential risks to you in taking part?

There will be no risks to you in taking part in this research project, except taking time to participate in the steering group and completing notes about your involvement in the group.

What will happen to the information in this research project?

Data collected from steering group meetings will be recorded in the form of short reflective notes with points recorded not being attributed to individuals, thus ensuring anonymity. Participants of the steering group will be asked to ensure that all discussions during these meetings remain confidential.

Data collected by the researcher from focus groups/semi-structured interviews that the steering group will be looking at will be anonymised prior to being shared with the steering group to ensure confidentiality. Notes taken by steering group participants will be shared with the researcher only at the end of each meeting and will be destroyed within three years of the notes being recorded by them. All data associated with this research will be securely stored via the UWS One Drive and will be deleted within 36 months of being collected.

All the data collected in this research will be treated in accordance with the Data Protection Act (1998) and the UWS Code of Ethics. Your personal data such as contact details and reflective notes will be processed for the purposes outlined in this notice. The legal basis that would be used to process your personal data will be the provision of your consent. Your personal data will be processed so long as it is required for the research project but not exceeding three years. We will do our best to minimise the processing of personal data wherever possible. We will anonymise or pseudonymise the personal data you provided within 30 days.

If you are concerned about how your personal data is being processed, please contact UWS in the first instance at dataprotection@uws.ac.uk. If you remain unsatisfied, you may wish to contact the Information Commissioner's Office (ICO). Contact details, and details of data subject rights, are available on the ICO website at: <https://ico.org.uk/for-organisations/data-protection-reform/overview-of-the-gdpr/individuals-rights/>

What will happen to the results of the research study?

The results of the research study will be presented as a thesis for the award of a Professional Doctorate and may form part of a presentation to interested parties thereafter or part of a publication.

Who has reviewed the study?

The study has been reviewed by the University of the West of Scotland Education and Social Sciences (ESS) Ethics Committee.

What will happen next?

If you are happy to be involved in the research, you will be asked to sign a consent form to confirm this. I am extremely grateful for your involvement. Thanks, are also expressed to those who have taken the time to read this information sheet but who now choose not to take part.

If you have any questions/concerns, during or after the investigation, or wish to contact an independent person to whom any questions may be directed or further information may be sought from, please contact:

Dr. Carole Bignell
Lead Supervisor
University of the West of Scotland
[REDACTED]

Researcher Contact Details:
Carol Strom
School of Education and Social Sciences
[REDACTED]

Appendix 8 - Participant Information Sheet – Individual Interview (Parent/Carer)

School of Education and Social Sciences

You are being invited to take part in a research study. Before you decide, it is important for you to understand why the research is being done and what it will involve. Please take time to read the following information carefully and discuss it with others if you wish. Please ask me if there is anything that is not clear or if you would like more information. Take time to decide whether or not you wish to take part.

Title of the study: Communication and Parental Engagement during the Transition from Early Learning and Childcare (ELC) to Primary.

Introduction

This research project is run by Carol Strom, Professional Doctorate student at the School of Education and Social Sciences, University of the West of Scotland.

What is the purpose of this study?

This research study addresses the following question:

‘What communication tools are pertinent to successfully supporting parental engagement during the transition from Early Learning and Childcare to primary school?’

Do you have to take a part?

It is up to you to decide whether or not to take part and you have the right to decline the offer to take part in this study without giving a reason. If you do decide to take part you will be given this information sheet to keep and be asked to sign a consent form. If you decide to take part you can skip over any questions you do not wish to answer during the individual interview and are free to withdraw up until 2 weeks after the date of the interview without giving a reason. Should you wish to do this please contact Carol Strom or the Lead Supervisor Dr. Carole Bignell.

What will you do in this research project?

You will take part in an individual interview where the researcher will ask a variety of questions decided in conjunction with a steering group about your experiences and ideas of communication methods and parental engagement during the transition of children from ELC to primary school currently used or may wish to be considered. Once the data from the interviews have been collated, the steering group will join me in reviewing the findings and form a plan for proposed changes to the current transition programme in terms of the communication tools used and the parental engagement opportunities. It is envisaged that the interview will take place on a specific date and time for about 1 hour within the nursery or online. As part of the interview process, we will be looking for reflective notes reflecting upon your involvement in the interview after the meeting, which may take up to 10 minutes to complete.

Why have you been invited to take part?

Your child is currently in their pre-school year and will be starting primary school in August 2023.

What are the potential risks to you in taking part?

There will be no risks to you in taking part in this research project, except taking time to participate in the individual interviews.

What will happen to the information in this research project?

Data collected from the individual interviews will be recorded either visually or auditory and during transcription by the researcher will be anonymised to ensure confidentiality.

Data collected by the researcher from the individual interviews will be anonymised prior to being shared with the steering group to ensure confidentiality. Notes taken by the interview participants will be shared with the researcher only at the end of the individual interviews and will be destroyed within three years of the notes being recorded by them. All data associated with this research project will be securely stored via the UWS One Drive and will be deleted within 36 months of being collected. Video/audio recordings of the individual interviews will be disposed once they have been transcribed.

All the data collected in this research will be treated in accordance with the Data Protection Act (1998) and the UWS Code of Ethics. Your personal data such as contact details and responses to questions will be processed for the purposes outlined in this notice. The legal basis that would be used to process your personal data will be the provision of your consent. Your personal data will be processed so long as it is required

for the research project but not exceeding three years. We will do our best to minimise the processing of personal data wherever possible. We will anonymise or pseudonymise the personal data you provided within 30 days.

If you are concerned about how your personal data is being processed, please contact UWS in the first instance at dataprotection@uws.ac.uk. If you remain unsatisfied, you may wish to contact the Information Commissioner's Office (ICO). Contact details, and details of data subject rights, are available on the ICO website at: <https://ico.org.uk/for-organisations/data-protection-reform/overview-of-the-gdpr/individuals-rights/>

What will happen to the results of the research study?

The results of the research study will be presented as a thesis for the award of a Professional Doctorate and may form part of a presentation to interested parties thereafter or part of a publication.

Who has reviewed the study?

The study has been reviewed by the University of the West of Scotland Education and Social Sciences (ESS) Ethics Committee.

What will happen next?

If you are happy to be involved in the research, you will be asked to sign a consent form to confirm this. I am extremely grateful for your involvement. Thanks, are also expressed to those who have taken the time to read this information sheet but who now choose not to take part.

If you have any questions/concerns, during or after the investigation, or wish to contact an independent person to whom any questions may be directed or further information may be sought from, please contact:

Dr. Carole Bignell
Lead Supervisor
University of the West of Scotland
[REDACTED]

Researcher Contact Details:
Carol Strom
School of Education and Social Sciences
[REDACTED]

Appendix 9 – Consent Forms (interviews)

RESEARCH INFORMED CONSENT FORM (Interview)

Title of Project: Communication and Parental Engagement during the Transition from Early Learning and Childcare (ELC) to Primary School.

Ethics Application Number: 18022

Investigators names: Carol Strom

Researcher Email: [REDACTED]

You have been invited to take part in a study on the communication tools that are pertinent to supporting parental engagement during the transition of children from an Early Learning and Childcare setting to primary school. By completing this form and agreeing to give your full consent, you agree that you have read and understood the participant information sheet and understand what is being asked of you in this study.

Please read the following statements and, if you agree, initial the corresponding box to confirm your agreement

	Initial below:
I confirm that I have read and understand the participant information sheet and instruction sheet for the study. I have had the opportunity to consider the information, ask questions and have had these answered satisfactorily.	
I understand that my participation is voluntary, and I need not answer any questions, and that I am free to withdraw up until 2 weeks after the date of the interviews. This date will be _____ without giving any reason.	
I understand that the information I give is confidential and any publications or presentations resulting from this work will not identify me personally unless my prior permission has been given.	
I consent to the processing of personal information I may provide e.g. contact details, sex, background, etc. for the purposes explained to me. I understand that such information will be handled in accordance with all applicable data protection legislation.	
I agree to being audio and visually recorded.	
I freely agree to participate in this study.	
I will complete a reflective note following my involvement in the interview.	

Name of participant (block capitals):

Name of researcher (block capitals):

Date:

Date:

Signature:

Signature:

Appendix 10 - Participant Information Sheet – Focus Group (ELC/Primary School Staff)

School of Education and Social Sciences

You are being invited to take part in a research study. Before you decide, it is important for you to understand why the research is being done and what it will involve. Please take time to read the following information carefully and discuss it with others if you wish. Please ask me if there is anything that is not clear or if you would like more information. Take time to decide whether or not you wish to take part.

Title of the study: Communication and Parental Engagement during the Transition from Early Learning and Childcare (ELC) to Primary.

Introduction

This research project is run by Carol Strom, Professional Doctorate student at the School of Education and Social Sciences, University of the West of Scotland.

What is the purpose of this study?

This research study addresses the following question:

‘What communication tools are pertinent to successfully supporting parental engagement during the transition from Early Learning and Childcare to primary school?’

Do you have to take a part?

It is up to you to decide whether or not to take part and you have the right to decline the offer to take part in this study without giving a reason. If you do decide to take part you will be given this information sheet to keep and be asked to sign a consent form. If you decide to take part you can skip over any questions you do not wish to answer during the focus group and are free to withdraw up until 2 weeks after the date of the focus group without giving a reason. Should you wish to do this please contact Carol Strom or the Lead Supervisor Dr. Carole Bignell.

What will you do in this research project?

You will become a member of a focus group where the researcher will ask collectively to the group a variety of questions decided in conjunction with a steering group about your experiences and ideas of communication methods and parental engagement during the transition of children from ELC to primary school currently used or may wish to be considered. Once the data from the focus group has been collated, a steering group will join me in reviewing the findings and form a plan for proposed changes to the current transition programme in terms of the communication tools used and the parental engagement opportunities. It is envisaged that the focus group will meet on a specific date and time for about 1 hour within the nursery/school. As part of the focus group, we will be looking for notes reflecting upon your involvement in the group after the meeting, which may take up to 10 minutes to complete.

Why have you been invited to take part?

You are actively involved in the transition of children from ELC to primary school and will be involved in the transition of children to primary school in August 2023.

What are the potential risks to you in taking part?

There will be no risks to you in taking part in this research project, except taking time to participate in the focus group.

What will happen to the information in this research project?

Data collected from the focus group will be recorded either visually or auditory and during transcription by the researcher will be anonymised to ensure confidentiality. Participants of the focus group will be asked to ensure that all discussions during these meetings remain confidential.

Data collected by the researcher from the focus group will be anonymised prior to being shared with the steering group to ensure confidentiality. Notes taken by the focus group participants will be shared with the researcher only at the end of the focus group and will be destroyed within three years of the notes being recorded by them. All data associated with this research project will be securely stored via the UWS One Drive and will be deleted within 36 months of being collected. Video/audio recordings of the focus groups interviews will be disposed once they have been transcribed.

All the data collected in this research will be treated in accordance with the Data Protection Act (1998) and the UWS Code of Ethics. Your personal data such as contact details and responses to questions will be processed for the purposes outlined in this notice. The legal basis that would be used to process your personal data will be the

provision of your consent. Your personal data will be processed so long as it is required for the research project but not exceeding three years. We will do our best to minimise the processing of personal data wherever possible. We will anonymise or pseudonymise the personal data you provided within 30 days.

If you are concerned about how your personal data is being processed, please contact UWS in the first instance at dataprotection@uws.ac.uk. If you remain unsatisfied, you may wish to contact the Information Commissioner's Office (ICO). Contact details, and details of data subject rights, are available on the ICO website at: <https://ico.org.uk/for-organisations/data-protection-reform/overview-of-the-gdpr/individuals-rights/>

What will happen to the results of the research study?

The results of the research study will be presented as a thesis for the award of a Professional Doctorate and may form part of a presentation to interested parties thereafter or part of a publication.

Who has reviewed the study?

The study has been reviewed by the University of the West of Scotland Education and Social Sciences (ESS) Ethics Committee.

What will happen next?

If you are happy to be involved in the research, you will be asked to sign a consent form to confirm this. I am extremely grateful for your involvement. Thanks, are also expressed to those who have taken the time to read this information sheet but who now choose not to take part.

If you have any questions/concerns, during or after the investigation, or wish to contact an independent person to whom any questions may be directed or further information may be sought from, please contact:

Dr. Carole Bignell
Lead Supervisor
University of the West of Scotland
[REDACTED]

Researcher Contact Details:
Carol Strom
School of Education and Social Sciences
[REDACTED]

Appendix 11– Consent Forms (Focus Groups)

RESEARCH INFORMED CONSENT FORM (FOCUS GROUP)

Title of Project: Communication and Parental Engagement during the Transition from Early Learning and Childcare (ELC) to Primary School.

Ethics Application Number: 18022

Investigators names: Carol Strom

Researcher Email: [REDACTED]

You have been invited to take part in a study on the communication tools that are pertinent to supporting parental engagement during the transition of children from an Early Learning and Childcare setting to primary school. By completing this form and agreeing to give your full consent, you agree that you have read and understood the participant information sheet and understand what is being asked of you in this study.

Please read the following statements and, if you agree, initial the corresponding box to confirm your agreement

	Initial below:
I confirm that I have read and understand the participant information sheet and instruction sheet for the study. I have had the opportunity to consider the information, ask questions and have had these answered satisfactorily.	
I understand that my participation is voluntary, and I need not answer any questions, and that I am free to withdraw up until 2 weeks after the date of the focus group. This date will be _____ without giving any reason.	
I understand that the information I give is confidential and any publications or presentations resulting from this work will not identify me personally unless my prior permission has been given.	
I consent to the processing of personal information I may provide e.g. contact details, sex, background, etc. for the purposes explained to me. I understand that such information will be handled in accordance with all applicable data protection legislation.	
I agree to being audio and visually recorded.	
I freely agree to participate in this study.	
I will complete a reflective note following my involvement in the focus group.	

Name of participant (block capitals):

Name of researcher (block capitals):

Date:

Date:

Signature:

Signature:

Appendix 12 – Reflective Notes Completed

Participant	Note completed
DHT	Email response following Steering Group Meeting 1 (17/03/23)
Head of ELC	Steering Meeting 1 (Reflective Note (RN), 17/03/23) Steering Meeting 2 (RN, 09/06/23)
Transition Coordinator of ELC	Steering Meeting 1 (RN, 17/03/23) Steering Meeting 2 (RN, 09/06/23)
Steering Parent 1 (SP1)	Steering Meeting 2 (RN, 09/06/23)
Steering Parent 2 (SP2)	Steering Meeting 1 (RN, 17/03/23) Steering Meeting 2 (RN, 09/06/23)
Steering Parent 3 (SP3)	Steering Meeting 1 (RN, 17/03/23)
Parent 6	Individual Interview (RN, 31/05/23)
Parent 3	Individual Interview (RN, 22/03/23)
Anita *	Future P1 Teacher Focus Group (RN, 12/05/23)
Karen *	Future P1 Teacher Focus Group (RN, 12/05/23)
Norma *(Team Leader)	ELC Staff Focus Group (RN, 18/05/23)
Katy * (Parent Support Worker)	ELC Staff Focus Group (RN, 18/05/23)
Lynsey * (Early Years Practitioner)	ELC Staff Focus Group (RN, 18/05/23)

* Pseudonyms are used ** RN – reflective note

Appendix 13 – Steering Group Members

Name	Position
Steering Parent 1	Parent of first child starting primary school
Steering Parent 2	Parent of first child starting primary school
Steering Parent 3	Parent of a second child start primary school. Older child currently attended Blue Primary School
Head of ELC	Head of Establishment of Rainbow ELC
DHT	Depute Head Teacher of Blue Primary School. Responsible for overseeing transition from all ELC's to Primary One at Blue Primary School
Transition Coordinator	Early Years Practitioner at Rainbow ELC. Transition Leadership Role – this includes liaison with all primary schools that the children from Rainbow ELC will be going to
Researcher	

Appendix 14 – Final Questions (Individual Interviews)

Starting Questions

- What communication tools do you use in your everyday life?
- If these communication tools are digital, how confident are you at using the digital communication?

Communication with Parents

- What communication tools does the ELC use to communicate with you? Have you any issues with receiving and reading them on the devices you have at home?
- Do you feel that the communication between the ELC and home is two-way? Please explain your answers.
- What communication have you had with the primary school your child will be going to so far? What communication tools did they use? Do you feel that the communication between the primary school and home is two-way? Please explain your answers.
- Have the ELC or primary school sent home any home learning activities? What communication tools were used? Were they suitable?

Digital Communication with Parents/Carers

- What digital communication devices do you have readily available at home?
- What digital communication tools has your child's ELC used to engage you generally in the life of the ELC? Do you feel that these tools are suitable?
- Do you feel that these tools are suitable? Please explain your answer.
- What devices do you use to access the digital communication from the ELC? If on a mobile phone is the communication readable/accessible?
- Do you feel that the purpose of the communication affects the tool that should be used? Can you give any examples?

Digital Impact

- Are there any other communication tools used by the ELC to communicate with you? In your view are the tools well matched to the purpose?
- If you cannot visit the ELC in person, how do they communicate with you? How effective is this?

- Do you feel that the ELC communicate with you regularly enough? Why? Why not? Is the timing of them suitable?
- Does the new primary school have a website? Have you used it? What for? What information would you like to see on it?

Parental Involvement in Transition

- Do you have knowledge of your child's new primary school? Where has this come from?
- Have you had the opportunity to visit your child's new primary school and engage with the staff? If so, how effective was this in providing you with information about transition? Did you know you will have the opportunity to visit the primary school before your child starts school?
- What communication have you had with your child's primary school so far about the transition process? What has been most effective in your view?
- How actively would you like to be involved in your child's transition to primary school? Please explain your answer.
- What activities or communication not already discussed would you like to be involved in to support your child during their transition to primary school and how actively would you like to be involved?
- What communication methods would you like used before your child starts primary school?

Moving Forward

- Are there any specific communication tools that you would like the primary school to use with you when involving you in your child's transition to primary school? Please explain.
- What information would you find useful as a new parent on a primary school website?

Closing

- Do you have any other thoughts or views that you would like to share?

Appendix 15 – Final Questions (Focus Group)

Starting Questions

- What communication tools do you use in your everyday life?
- Are there any communication tools that you find you use on a regular basis? Why this one/these ones?

Policies

- Have the Covid-19 mitigations affected the communication tools you use to communicate with parents/carers? What communication tools did you use to support the transition during Covid-19? Do you still use them?
- What parental engagement activities do you seek to involve parents/carers in during the transition process?
- Do you use any specific Education Scotland guidance or Scottish Government policies and guidance to support the communication with parents? Please explain/
- What advice and guidance about transition and parental engagement from ELC to primary school are you aware of/used?

Communication with Parents

- Do you engage in learning opportunities with the parents/carers regarding transition to primary school? Are they general or specific?
- Do you have opportunities to use both written and digital communication tools with parents/carers regarding transition? Please give examples
- What communication tools do you currently use to engage parents during the transition process?

Digital Communication with Parents/Carers

- Do you feel that the purpose of the communication affects the tool used e.g. newsletters, SWAY? Can you give any examples?
- Have any parents/carers contacted you regarding problems/concerns with using ICT at home?

Digital Impact

- What digital communication tools does your setting currently use to communicate with parents/carers about the life of the setting? About their individual child?
- Do you feel that these tools are effective? Please explain your answer.
- What communication tools do you use to communicate with parents/carers about starting school and helping the children to settle in? What is the frequency?
- What do you think is the impact of these communications?

Parental Involvement in Transition

- What parental engagement opportunities have you implemented as part of the transition process? How successful have these been? Please explain your answer.

Moving Forward

- What parental engagement opportunities would you like to do with parents/carers that you do not already do, and the communication tools would you like to use during transition?
- What challenges do you experience or envisage with respect to communication with parents regarding transition from early years to primary school?

Closing

- Do you have any other thoughts or views that you would like to share?

Appendix 16 – Data Posters

What communication tools does the ELC use with you? Any issues?
Do you feel communication between ELC and home is ~~way~~?

What digital communication tools does the ELC use with you to engage you in life of nursery? Suitable?
Do you feel that the purpose of the communication affects the tool that should be used?

Do you feel the ELC communicates regularly enough? Why? Why Not? Timing suitable?

Regularly enough – 80%

- ❖ They would contact you if anything happens to let you know.
- ❖ I quite liked when we can come in because you get to see what they have been doing. The sways I think are now seasonally. You get a kind of mixture of all the different pictures so sometimes my child is on the sway and sometimes they're not.
- ❖ Not about my individual child but very good at communicating dates, events and transition.
- ❖ Journals are amazing they have loads and it's so nice to look back on. I know they are very hard working and I know they put effort into the journals and stuff but I think an app or social media like a daily kind of update and what your child's up to is a nice touch.

**Regularly enough?
No – 20%**

- ❖ In terms of communication about my child. I would like more and I don't feel that I always know what's going on, but I don't have a solution to that.
- ❖ My child only tells me what they liked because they had fun. In terms of how that are getting on with their learning and things like that it is quite limited.

Timings

Yes – 60%
No – 20%

- ❖ Don't mind time of day receiving information on app.
- ❖ I can't get them when the notifications or emails come through right away including immediate announcements. I can't tap into them straight away.

Has ELC or primary school sent home any home learning activities? Suitable?

- Nursery – yes 60% no – 40%
 - ❖ Nursery rhymes
- ❖ Sporadic ideas from Sway, Bookbug but good ideas for a rainy day.
- School – yes 20% no 80%

What communication have you had with the primary school? What communication tools did they use? Do you feel communication between the primary school and home is okay?

Welcome note/Email - 60%

- ❖ Emailed handbook
- ❖ Received an email reply to say thank you for letting them know we are attending the induction days.

Letters – 40%

- ❖ Via nursery about transition days.
- ❖ Sent letters including one congratulating my child on starting primary and about the two-day induction.

Phone – 20%

- ❖ Can phone up if any problems. I phoned up about induction days, staff spoke to were very friendly.

Other Comments:

- Had lots of stuff and doing a lot more to help transition.
- We've had load.
- There hasn't been anything I've had to ask them
- All information about transition from nursery.
- Only one way from school – information.
- Not spoken to school yet.
- Two-day induction and we will get to meet the teacher and buddy.

Parental Involvement in Transition

Does the new primary school have a website?

Yes – 80% Unsure 20%

What information would you like to see on it

- ❖ Information about uniforms including photographs of them in the uniform.
 - ❖ What first day will look like.
- ❖ How to prepare our child for school – top tips.
- ❖ Even a section for prospective parents to tell us what to expect and what our children will expect.
 - ❖ Stuff to help my child fit in
- ❖ Events that are up and coming – as much notice as possible for parents that are working
 - ❖ Things that make you feel like you're a partnership.
 - ❖ Daily and weekly routine
 - ❖ Bit of the curriculum overview each term
 - ❖ Policies

Other comments

- I am sure it's happening with my child when they go and and has the buddy up and I'm sure it's happening for them but I feel quite out of the loop.
- Not sure but have a Facebook page.

Have you had the opportunity to visit your child's primary school?

No – 100%

Comments

- I know the children have been including an assembly, but we just dropped them.
- It would be interesting to go round and see exactly where they are going so that you can put a picture to it.
 - Going on 6th and 7th June for induction (60%)
 - Going 6th and 7th June but need to take the days off work as during the day.
 - It would be interesting to see round.
 - Tuesday 6th June it will be good to see round the building.
- No not yet – only been in building to vote, not had a reason to go in with my child.

What communication have you had with your child's primary school so far about the transition process? What has been most effective in your view?

Emails – 100%

Comments

- ❖ Welcome email not a generic one.
- ❖ Very friendly communication in email.
- ❖ Email saying they were accepted/confirming place.

Comments

- ❖ Gives everything I need to know
- ❖ It's not set in stone even although they are in catchment because there's that many kids ,so I was quite pleased with that.
- ❖ Know child has been visiting school from nursery but don't always know in advance when my child will be doing transition things – find out after it has happened either hat day or the following day depending if I pick them up.
- ❖ All during the day. Its' a Tuesday morning and a Wednesday afternoon. Getting told which teacher and we should see their classroom and they'll go through like the uniform.
 - ❖ Welcoming ethos.

Letter – 60%

Comment

- ❖ Including about 6th and 7th June

Effective?

- Think all effective.
- Not effective as it didn't tell you anything about meeting on 6th June, not giving me any further information in the letter about it. It's not giving me anything to work with till then. I can make the meeting on the 6th June but only because owed time at work.

What activities or communication not already discussed would you like to be involved in to support your child during their transition to primary school?

What communication methods would you like used before your child goes to school?

Are there any specific communication tools that you would like the primary school to use with you when involving your child's transition to primary school?

Activities

- ❖ A walk round the school with child to explore together or after the child has been round could show parent.
 - ❖ Getting to meet the teacher and having a chat with them – putting faces to names.
 - ❖ Looking forward to seeing the school lunches.
 - ❖ No I'm ok.
- ❖ We've been given information like that about what they've been doing in the lead up to the transition to school and I am aware of the days that they go to meet their buddy or go to an assembly. So I think there has been a lot.
- ❖ I would like to know what's going on so I can support any questions my child has. Found out from relative about buddy my child has. I think it would be a nice thing to know about their buddy – name, interests.
 - ❖ Like to know in advance so I can prepare my child for what's going to happen.
 - ❖ Information Evening.
- ❖ Sway from primary school giving a tour, information about the school and what it's all about, video tour of the school – something so that you feel more like what it's gonna look like for my child when they go up and prepare them, because I would know what it looks like, whereas I don't know enough to reassure them.
- ❖ We will get lots of information on the 6th June but earlier would have been better – to put my mind at ease.

Communication

- ❖ A teams, zoom or Sway to get us involved.
 - ❖ Just presume same as the nursery and they would phone if there was anything,
- ❖ The app as I can get the information at any time of the day or email so I don't need to wait for a paper letter – its quicker so I can try and organise things.
 - ❖ I'm happy with the way they're doing it.
- ❖ Been very informative mum passes on eh information about any visits that have taken place that day with the primary school.
 - ❖ More information about the school e.g., learning through play, make us more familiar with the school.
 - ❖ Emails and letters are fine (40%)
- ❖ Don't mind any form of communication to tell me what's happening or coming up so I could arrange time off work. If paper, I may not get it till the next day.

What communication have you had with your child's primary school so far about the transition process? What has been most effective in your view?

Emails – 100%

Comments

- ❖ Welcome email not a generic one.
- ❖ Very friendly communication in email.
- ❖ Email saying they were accepted/confirming place.

Comments

- ❖ Gives everything I need to know
- ❖ It's not set in stone even although they are in catchment because there's that many kids, so I was quite pleased with that.
- ❖ Know child has been visiting school from nursery but don't always know in advance when my child will be doing transition things – find out after it has happened either that day or the following day depending if I pick them up.
- ❖ All during the day. It's a Tuesday morning and a Wednesday afternoon. Getting told which teacher and we should see their classroom and they'll go through like the uniform.
 - ❖ Welcoming ethos.

Letter – 60%

Comment

- ❖ Including about 6th and 7th June

Effective?

- Think all effective.
- Not effective as it didn't tell you anything about meeting on 6th June, not giving me any further information in the letter about it. It's not giving me anything to work with till then. I can make the meeting on the 6th June but only because owed time at work.

Have the Covid19 mitigations affected the communication tools you use to communicate with parents/carers?
 What communication tools did you use to support the transition during Covid19? Do you still use them?
 What digital communication tools does your setting currently use to communicate with parents/carers about the life of the set

Do you feel that the purpose of the communication affects the tool used?
 Any contact from parents/carers regarding problems/concerns with ICT?

Comments

School

- ❖ School diaries – replaced with Google Classroom and school app.
- ❖ Homework now via Google Classroom except primary one who are now back to using jotters
- ❖ Google Classroom including photos and videos both individual and general – not really sent out prior to Covid.
- ❖ Lack of informal communication – more formal when on Google Classroom, email compared to use of diaries (more relaxed)
 - ❖ More phone calls to parents.
- ❖ Day to day – the app – generic across the school, app used more prominently used in lower primary school.
 - ❖ Website
 - ❖ Digital newsletters

Problem/concern using ICT

Yes

- ❖ Google Classroom – may not have looked through paper copy of instructions about how to use.
- ❖ Some parents don't have access to a laptop – we could give them one.

Other Comments

- ❖ Parents can email the school office if they have a concern etc, if don't want to talk about it at gate or come into playground.
 - ❖ Staff will email or phone back.

Have the Covid19 mitigations affected the communication tools you use to communicate with parents/carers?
 What communication tools did you use to support the transition during Covid19? Do you still use them?
 What digital communication tools does your setting currently use to communicate with parents/carers about the life of the set

Do you feel that the purpose of the communication affects the tool used?
 Any contact from parents/carers regarding problems/concerns with ICT?

Comments

Nursery

- ❖ Absolutely affected, for some it was a benefit could reach a lot of working parents as they were working from home.
 - ❖ If doing stay and plays and working they may not be able to attend now
 - ❖ Sways – had lots of information on them – still going out but not as often.
- ❖ Sway not as good as some parents weren't aware of dates etc, used to go out more frequently but feedback from parents included too much to look and hard to ensure every child in it and mainly looked at photographs not the dates.
 - ❖ Telephoned parents to communicate – still used but face to face now and verbal reminders.
 - ❖ Emails and letters still used.
- ❖ Now nursery have app introduced after Covid including putting information on news section – direct messaging as many parents weren't accessing emails or hadn't supplied an email address.
 - ❖ Use the app to keep parents informed of transition and open to everyone, grandparents etc. Short direct information – what's happening, when and time.

Problem/concern using ICT

- ❖ If something wrong with sway they would tell you but not much feedback about sway now we have the app.

Do you engage in learning opportunities with the parents/carers regarding transition to primary school? Are they general or specific?

What parental engagement opportunities have you implemented as part of the transition process?

.School

- ❖ Parents come in on the two-day transition days for children.
- ❖ Parents go for a meeting in canteen for an hour led by management.
- ❖ Parents get a communication pack with lots of written information in it.
 - ❖ Booklet for parents
- ❖ Power Point talked through by HT about their child coming to school in August,
 - ❖ We meet parents when they drop off and collect child.
- ❖ On first induction day bring children to our door, introduce ourselves to both child and parent before parent goes to meeting.
 - ❖ Do an activity with children on both induction days.
 - ❖ Children go with adult for lunch to see the lunch routine
 - ❖ Not a lot of collaborative work for us and the parents.

Nursery

- ❖ Transition meetings for specific children and/or HT from new primary school.
- ❖ Enhanced transition identified for certain children and schools contacted,.
 - ❖ Transition reports for all children going to school.
- ❖ Transition passports for identified children – lets schools know if more needed by them to support the child.
- ❖ Trying to get parents more involved e.g., parents taking child to primary school if not their time at nursery.
 - ❖ Parents are involved in meetings for individual children.

Do you engage in learning opportunities with the parents/carers regarding transition to primary school? Are they general or specific?

What parental engagement opportunities have you implemented as part of the transition process?

What parental engagement opportunities would you like to do with parents/carers that you do not already do

.School

- ❖ Parents come in on the two-day transition days for children.
- ❖ Parents go for a meeting in canteen for an hour led by management.
- ❖ Parents get a communication pack with lots of written information in it.
 - ❖ Booklet for parents
- ❖ Power Point talked through by HT about their child coming to school in August,
 - ❖ We meet parents when they drop off and collect child.
- ❖ On first induction day bring children to our door, introduce ourselves to both child and parent before parent goes to meeting.
 - ❖ Do an activity with children on both induction days.
 - ❖ Children go with adult for lunch to see the lunch routine
 - ❖ Not a lot of collaborative work for us and the parents.
- ❖ Workshop in the evening – curriculum, homework, behaviour policy etc in September.

Would like?

- ❖ To build a relation with parents, particularly before children start in August.
- ❖ Do a lot for the children but not necessarily the parents – parents could join in the activities.
- ❖ Get to know the parents and talk through any worries etc. they may have.

Nursery

- ❖ Transition meetings for specific children and/or HT from new primary school.
- ❖ Enhanced transition identified for certain children and schools contacted,.
 - ❖ Transition reports for all children going to school.
- ❖ Transition passports for identified children – lets schools know if more needed by them to support the child.
- ❖ Trying to get parents more involved e.g., parents taking child to primary school if not their time at nursery.
 - ❖ Parents are involved in meetings for individual children.

Would like?

- ❖ Some parents don't know which school due to placing requests and having to wait so some children are missing out on some of the transition events as parents have a long time to wait to find out.

Appendix 17 – Parent Interviews

Parent Interview	Date of Interview	Any significance of interview timing?
Parent 1	22/05/23	Prior to transition talk for parents
Parent 2	22/05/23	Prior to transition talk for parents
Parent 3	22/05/23	Prior to transition talk for parents
Parent 4	24/05/23	Prior to transition talk for parents
Parent 5	27/05/23	Prior to transition talk for parents
Parent 6	31/05/23	Prior to transition talk for parents
Parent 7	07/06/23	After transition talk for parents
Parent 8	16/06/23	After transition talk for parents
Parent 9	19/06/23	After transition talk for parents

Appendix 18 – Reflective Note Template Steering Group Meeting One/Reflective Note Template ELC/Teacher/Parents

Participant Name:	
Date:	
Time:	Length of Activity:
Location:	
Activity:	
Summary – include details of activity and how it went, how did you feel before, during and after the activity, any other thought regarding what you said during the activity or what other people said, how did you participate in the activity, did you feel your views were listened to, any other comments.	

Appendix 19 – Reflective Note Template Steering Group Meeting Two

Participant Name:	
Date:	
Time:	Length of Activity:
Location:	
Activity:	
Research Question – What communication tools are pertinent to successfully supporting parental engagement during the transition of children from Nursery to Primary One?	
Summary – include details of activity and how it went, how did you feel before, during and after the activity, any other thought regarding the activity, did you feel your views were listened to, do you feel that you experienced partnership working and is there anything further you would like to talk to me about or think about after you have taken part in this activity?	

Appendix 20 – Initial Codes

Individual Interviews with Parents

Active involvement in transition - parental engagement
Any other communication methods between primary school and home
Any other types of communication used by ELC or primary school
Barriers to parental engagement
Best communication methods
Communication between home and primary school
Communication by ELC is suitable to purpose
Communication from ELC about transition dates etc.
Communication from primary school
Communication with ELC and home
Does school have a website
External communication methods about ELC
Final thoughts
First impressions of the primary school staff
Had opportunity to visit the primary school
Helping with research
How do they communicate if cannot go to ELC in person
ICT Barriers
Importance of face to face at ELC
Is communication with ELC enough
Is reading the information on mobile device from ELC ok
Issue during child's transition days
Issues with communication from primary school
Issues with receiving communication
Issues with the communication between ELC and home
Knowledge of new school
Knowledge of own child
Learning Opportunities - ELC
Learning Opportunities - Primary School
Meeting staff at transition session
Nursery App
Parental Concerns or needs
Personal Preferences regarding communication between ELC and home
Possible parental engagement opportunities
School website
School Website did you find what looking for
Suitable Communication Methods by ELC
Support from ELC staff at transition event with parents
Supporting Own Child
Transition Information Session for parents
Transition Information Session Timing
Transition Meeting - daytime
Transition Opportunities with primary school - Adult
Transition Opportunities with primary school - Child
Transition Session content
Transition Thoughts

Two-way between home and ELC
Understanding of catchment school
Understanding placing request protocol
Visit to the primary school
What would you like to see on website

FOCUS GROUPS WITH ELC AND FUTURE PRIMARY ONE TEACHERS

BARRIERS FOR WORKING PARENTS
CHANGES IN HOW COMMUNICATE WITH SCHOOL PARENTS
COMMUNICATION CHALLENGES
COVID-19 COMMUNICATION EFFECTS
COVID-19 ELC PARENTAL ENGAGEMENT
DIGITAL BENEFITS - ELC
DIGITAL COMMUNICATION SET UP WHEN STARTING SCHOOL
ELC COMMUNICATION DURING COVID-19
ELC COMMUNICATION WITH HOME
ELC GENERAL PARENTAL INVOLVEMENT
ELC PARENTAL ENGAGEMENT - TRANSITION
ELC SUPPORTING WORKING PARENTS
ELC TRANSITION COMMUNICATION
ELC TRANSITION COMMUNICATION (2)
EXPECTATIONS OF PRIMARY SCHOOLS FOR PARENTAL ENGAGEMENT DURING TRANSITION
EXPECTATIONS OF THE ELC BY SCHOOL
FINAL THOUGHTS - ELC
FIRST DAYS AT SCHOOL
ICT ISSUES - ELC
IS SCHOOL COMMUNICATION EFFECTIVE
ISSUES WITH ELC COMMUNICATION WITH PARENTS
ISSUES WITH GOOGLE CLASSROOM
LOSING THE NURSERY
NURSERY APP - ELC PERSPECTIVE
PARENTAL ASSUMPTIONS ON TRANSITION
PARENTAL ENGAGEMENT ISSUES - ELC
PARENTAL ENGAGEMENT WHEN CHILD IN PRIMARY ONE
PARENTAL NEEDS OR CONCERNS - ELC PERSPECTIVE
PLACING REQUEST ISSUES - ELC
POLICY GUIDANCE - COMMUNICATION ELC
POLICY GUIDANCE - TRANSITION - ELC
POSSIBLE PARENTAL ENGAGEMENT OPPORTUNITIES - PRIMARY SCHOOL
REDUCING ICT BARRIERS AT SCHOOL
RELATIONSHIP WITH TEACHER
SCHOOL COMMUNICATION WITH PARENTS
SUPPORTING WORKING PARENTS WHEN CHILD IN PRIMARY ONE
SWAY
SWAY - ELC PERSPECTIVE
TEACHER OPPORTUNITIES TO MEET AND ENGAGE WITH THE PARENTS
TRANSITION INVOLVING PARENTS DURING COVID-19
TRANSITION OPPORTUNITIES FOR CHILDREN - TRANSITION DAYS

TRANSITION OPPORTUNITIES FOR PARENTS - PRIMARY SCHOOL
TRANSITION THOUGHTS ELC
USE OF POLICIES ON GUIDANCE TO COMMUNICATE WITH PARENTS
USE OF POLICIES ON TRANSITION GUIDANCE
WHO IS TAKING THE LEAD WITH TRANSITION TO SCHOOL
WORKING IN PARTNERSHIP WITH THE PARENTS

Appendix 21 – Themes

Phase 3 Themes

Aims One to Three

Active Parental Engagement at School

Active Parental Engagement in Transition

Barriers

Communication

Covid-19

Forming Relationships

New School

Polices

Professional Concerns with Transition

Supporting and Knowing Own Child

Transition Events with Children

Two-Way Communication

Aim Four

Participation

Participation – Steering Group

Participatory Approach

Power

Phases 4 Themes

Aims One to Three

Active Parental Engagement in Transition

Barriers

Communication

Forming Relationships

Participation

Policies

Professional Concerns with Transition

Supporting and Knowing Own Child

Aim Four

Participation – Steering Group

Participatory Approach

Phase 5 Themes

Aim One

Digital Communication – Nursery App and School App; Emails; School Website

Traditional Communication – Letters; Face-to-face

Additional ‘informal’ Methods of Communication

Communication with Parents at Local Authority Level

Aim Two

Getting to Know Blue Primary School

Establishing a Relationship with School Staff

Aim Three

Barriers – Timing of Transition Talk; Advance Notification of Events; Different Care Arrangements

Possible Solutions

Aim Four

Reflections on the participatory research approach – parents and professional

Other – Policy Awareness

Appendix 22 – Steering Group Meeting Three Task (Collated Results)

Select four posters, look at the data and decide what you think should be stopped, keep on doing, develop further or introduce

First do it individually then join up with someone else. If some of the posters are the same discuss and come up with a list together – 4 things

Come together and discuss as a full group and decide with the support of Head of ELC and DHT think about what could be stopped, keep doing, develop further or introduce.

What do you think might be possible in the short term and long term?

Record on paper – these are things that both the ELC and school will take and consider for their settings and help inform next steps for both settings.

Questions:

Slide 1

***What communication tools does the ELC use with you? Any issues?**

***Do you feel communication between ELC and home is 2-way?**

Using the data decide:

What to stop doing?

ELC Head - Regular SWAYS – 2 per year; nursery photos only

What to keep doing?

Parent 2 – I like the school app, but have a few issues, out of nurseries control

Transition Coordinator – keep printing timetables and display on the Nursery App and playroom doors.

ELC Head – parents forum, introductory SWAY – end of year SWAY; app

What to develop?

Parent 2 – more information, sometimes I have to check with the nursery with the way its worded.

Transition Coordinator – more information on the app regarding daily activities or upcoming actions; section on app for transition

ELC Head – take photos out all together

What to introduce?

Parent 2 – an email link/box; 2-way chat to ask questions

Transition Coordinator – monthly transition information leaflets with the school

ELC Head – parents forum – more evenings?

Questions:

Slide 2

What digital communication tools does the ELC use with you to engage you in life of nursery? Suitable?

Do you feel that the purpose of the communication affects the tool that should be used?

Using the data decide:

What to stop doing?

ELC Head – limit SWAYS – 2 per year

What to keep doing?

ELC Head - App

Researcher – SWAY; face-to-face; app

What to develop?

ELC Head – awareness of Twitter; glow tile – more information

Researcher – app – what it can do – put more stuff on it

What to introduce?

Questions:

Slide 3

Do you feel the ELC communicates regularly enough? Why? Why Not? Timing suitable?

Using the data decide:

What to stop doing?

What to keep doing?

Parent 1 – app has been useful, allows you to check back from previous notices easily; parent engagement activities positive.

ELC Head – home activities, app, journals.

What to develop?

Parent 1 - minutes from forum to be circulated as good updates included for all parents; range of timings for forums or opportunities to attend virtually

ELC Head – more face to face; communication – re. timetable for transition visits if possible.

What to introduce?

Parent 1 – consistency of SWAY timings

Questions:

Slide 4

What communication have you had with the primary school?

What communication tools did they use?

Do you feel communication between the primary school and home is 2-way?

Using the data decide:

What to stop doing?

What to keep doing?

What to develop?

What to introduce?

Questions:

Slide 5

Parental Involvement in Transition

What information would you like to see on it?

Have you had the opportunity to visit your child's primary school?

Using the data decide:

What to stop doing?

DHT – think about website

What to keep doing?

DHT – two-day event and pack

Transition Coordinator – keep informing parents through app and emails about upcoming

Researcher – linking in with the primary school; induction days

What to develop?

DHT – more information about uniform as part of information sent out

Transition Coordinator – more parent involvement; invite all schools in learning community to a meeting

Researcher – keeping parents involved of what is happening – monthly timetable; visiting the school at a different time – may be earlier in the term

What to introduce?

DHT – information event in November

Transition Coordinator – to introduce a parent meeting regarding transition prior to the transition starting; poss. walk round school.

Questions:

Slide 6

What communication have you had with your child's primary school so far about the transition process?

What has been most effective in your view?

Using the data decide:

What to stop doing?

What to keep doing?

Parent 1 – welcome pack given to each child on Induction Day; beneficial to have activities to go through with your child over summer; personalisation of packs was positive.

Researcher – personal invites

What to develop?

Parent 1 – more information about the transition process will progress at an early stage – main things to expect and how you can support your child; opportunities for parents to have a quick tour around the school in person, or a virtual tour.

Researcher – PowerPoint available on website; SWAY reminders

What to introduce?

Questions:

Slide 7

What activities or communication not already discussed would you like to be involved in to support your child during their transition to primary school?

What communication methods would you like used before your child goes to school?

Are there any specific communication tools that you would like the primary school to use with you when involving you in your child's transition to primary school?

Using the data decide:

What to stop doing?

What to keep doing?

DHT - reminder about SWAY and Virtual Tour

Parent 2 – the app, the school seems very open for communicating which is great.

What to develop?

DHT – think about timing of events for working parents

Parent 2 – let parents know they can come in and have a chat, so we don't feel like we are pestering. I only know due to these steering meetings.

Transition Coordinator – to develop more parent information days in the evening for working parents

What to introduce?

Transition Coordinator – to plan and implement more parent involvement prior to transition activities starting

Questions:

Slide 8 (nursery)

Have the Covid-19 mitigations affected the communication tools you use to communicate with parents/carers?

What communication tools did you use to support the transition during Covid-19? Do you still use them?

What digital communication tools does your setting currently use to communicate with parents/carers about the life of the setting?

Do you feel that the purpose of the communication affects the tool used?

Any contact from parents/carers regarding problems/concerns with ICT?

Using the data decide:

What to stop doing?

What to keep doing?

What to develop?

What to introduce?

Questions:

Slide 9 (school)

Have the Covid-19 mitigations affected the communication tools you use to communicate with parents/carers? What communication tools did you use to support the transition during Covid-19? Do you still use them? What digital communication tools does your setting currently use to communicate with parents/carers about the life of the setting? Do you feel that the purpose of the communication affects the tool used? Any contact from parents/carers regarding problems/concerns with ICT?

Using the data decide:

What to stop doing?

What to keep doing?

What to develop?

What to introduce?

Questions:

Slide 10

Do you engage in learning opportunities with the parents/carers regarding transition to primary school? Are they general or specific?

What parental engagement opportunities have you implemented as part of the transition process?

What parental engagement opportunities would you like to do with parents/carers that you do not already do?

Using the data decide:

What to stop doing?

What to keep doing?

DHT – all comments

Parent 2 – pack for kids, especially the activity pack, lunch, PowerPoint

Parent 1 – induction days – lots of information and good to have a copy of the PowerPoint included in the pack to refresh after the event; including lunch to have an understanding of how it works to discuss with child.

What to develop?

DHT – opportunities for parents to take part in activities during induction day

Parent 2 – in the activity pack it would be nice to see info on other staff (head teacher) so my child 'knows' the people he can approach and who can help him if he needs.

Parent 1 – opportunities for parents to collaborate more in the process, to provide any relevant info for their child or engage in activities with them (some of this is met by booklet to be filled in for returning to school)

What to introduce?

DHT – walk round for parents before transition starts; monthly newsletters for parents

Parent 2 – maybe a walk round the school with our child; interview with my child's new teacher 1 to1 to share additional information that I see at home.

Parent 1 – opportunities for parents to contribute to the process and information about their child.

Appendix 23 – What to Take Forward

The decisions made by the steering group to take forward as part of their transition programme in light of the data collected and discussed were:

Rainbow ELC

- Meeting with parents not just those going to primary school involved in case study before the transition starts in January
- Meeting the local learning community to decide what each primary school that the children will be going to needs for their transition.
- Promoting Twitter as a communication tool
- Raise awareness of Nursery App as a communication tool and use this to promote Twitter
- More face-to-face opportunities between parents and ELC

Blue Primary School

- Walk round prior to registration at school (new)
- Information/transition evening in November (new)
- Monthly newsletter – transition from January including timetable and note from School DHT
- Learning activity each month
- Update website with information parents would like
- Twitter (let new parents know about it)
- Information about how to join the primary school Parent Council Facebook
- School App (let new parents know about it – know they can register and use before their child starts the primary school)
- Reinforce the SWAY, booklet etc. sent out by the email to parents once registered for the primary school.
- Reminder of this information during the year in transition newsletter
- Information about uniforms more prominent on website and on the first email about going to the primary school.

Appendix 24 – Data Timeline

Date	Activity	Present	Purpose	Outcome
11/10/22	My line manager confirmed that as I am wishing to use not only Rainbow ELC where I am working, permission is required from the authority and permission from Blue Primary School as well.	Completed application from sent to be countersigned by lead supervisor and forwarded to my line manager to submit on my behalf.	As more than one establishment involved needed permission from local authority.	Application form required to be completed detailing research.
12/10/22	Letter sent to Head of ELC seeking permission to undertake research which outlined research.		To explain research and what support and participation required from ELC.	
12/10/22	Application to undertake research within local authority.	Email sent to Head of Education within the local authority after supervisor had checked and signed form.	To seek permission to contact the primary school wishing to use in research.	Extra information was required from Head of Education in term of research being undertaken – issue surrounding the purpose of

				the steering group.
14/10/22	Extra information was supplied and direct permission via email from Head of Establishment (ELC) and HT to confirm happy research to be undertaken.	Researcher supplied information, Head of ELC sent email confirming happy for research to be undertaken. Line manager also confirmed again via online meeting with Head of Education happy with research to be undertaken.	To answer questions posed – more information was needed regarding the participatory approach to the research as the Head of Education was unsure about what it involved and how what I was doing was actually research. Permission needed in writing from Head of Establishment (ELC).	Permission was granted that afternoon – via email sent to line manager.
05/12/22	Ethics Application Form submitted to UWS.		Ethical Approval Required.	Permission Granted with amendments.
20/12/22	ELC improvement plan and quality and standards report.	Head of ELC emailed	To see where the research being	Links with primary schools and establishing

			undertaken links in.	professional contacts; Transition with feeder schools.; how good is our communication.
10/01/23	List of pre-school children and SIMD numbers. Discussion with Head of ELC regarding parents who could be involved.		To allow researcher to see the SIMD background for the setting and who may take part in research.	Gives information as part of the context.
20/01/23	Sway - Welcome to Blue Primary School	DHT – Sway	To see some of the information that has been sent out to parents once they have enrolled their child.	Communication for parents from primary school.
21/03/23	Business Cards	DHT	Emailed over following first steering group in case any parents needed them.	Links into ethics form – in case parents are upset – contact details for DHT at the primary school.

17/04/23	STEM Topic	DHT emailed	STEM topic being worked on with the ELC.	Topic for Transition – STEM.
10/05/23	Primary School SIMD data	Basic SIMD/ free meal breakdown.	This gives an overview for the context of the catchment for the school.	Gives information as part of the context.
25/05/23	Primary school improvement plan and quality and standards report.	Infographic and SIP 22-23; Quality and standard report School Handbook.	To see whether research links into their improvement plan etc.	No direct link is evident.
25/05/23	Copies of transition letters sent out to parents.	DHT emailed	In order to see what information had actually been sent to parents.	To allow researcher to look at what parents had actually been sent out and how this tied into what parents had said.
05/06/23	Video of the transition that children have taken part in.	DHT email	Showing parents the transition that their child has been through.	To consider how this links to the parent comments about transition.
06/06/23	Email of what the families will	DHT emailed	To showcase exactly what	Great to see and ascertain

	receive as part of first transition day.		the children and parents will receive – this had been shown to me at meeting with DHT.	whether any of this is talked about by parents being interviewed after the event on 6 th June.
16/06/23	P1 presentation	HT PowerPoint information for parents at first induction day on 6 th June.	See what the HT spoke to parents about.	See if the information either addresses or supports what parents/Future Primary One teachers said.
16/06/23	Transition Feedback	DHT and information from parents google form completed.	See what parents have said about the transition talk.	Use to possibly support data collected by researcher.
Steering Group Timeline				
End of January 2023	Speaking to Head of ELC regarding possible parents/carers for the steering group.	Head of ELC and Researcher (face-to-face)	8 parents were consequently approached in person with three agreeing to take part in these meetings – date at that	Three participant information sheets (PIS) and consent forms giving more detailed information and returned.

			time would be a Friday to support childcare - their children needed to attend on that day of the week.	(These were returned but due to supporting another nursery the first meeting was delayed until March).
January 2023	Speaking to Transition Coordinator about taking part in research.	Transition Coordinator in ELC and researcher (face-to-face)	Discussion informally about the group and whether she would like to take part.	She agreed.
20/01/23	Speaking with the Depute HT of the primary school about taking part in the steering group.	Depute HT and researcher (face-to-face)	Discussion informally about the group and whether she would like to take part.	She agreed and was very interested in being part and looking at how things could be improved in the primary school regarding transition between the ELC and them.
End of Feb 23	Felt another parent would be good on steering group.	Advice sought from Transition Coordinator and Head of ELC	Parent approached by Transition Coordinator (I was supporting	Agreed and PIS and consent form completed and returned.

			another nursery).	
17/03/23	First Steering group meeting – 10am	Researcher, Head of ELC, Transition Coordinator and 3 parents (SP1, SP2, SP3) (face-to-face) DHT from primary school (MS teams – for health reasons) One parent unable to attend at last minute - child ill.	Discussion about group and their involvement. Discussing and finalising questions to be asked to parents/carers of children attending the primary school and ELC staff and future Primary One teachers focus groups.	Focus Group on a Friday was preferred option and number of questions were slimmed down. Five completed reflective notes from participants returned.
02/06/23	Second steering group meeting – 10am	Researcher, Head of ELC, Transition Coordinator and 2 parents (SP1 and SP2) (face-to-face); apologies from DHT and 1 parent; 1 parent didn't respond to the invite.	Update on research and discussing what they could see from the data.	Meeting was delayed by a week due to Head of ELC being unable to attend – message sent out on App on 30 th May to parents involved that it would be same time but on 09/06/23.

05/06/23	Shared data collected with DHT as DHT could not make the re-scheduled second steering group meeting.	Researcher and DHT in their office at the primary school 2pm.	To discuss the data collected so far.	DHT found it hard to look at data objectively as lots of what parents were saying had actually been covered. Started to consider implications for practice.
09/06/23	Rescheduled second steering group meeting took place.	Same participants as 02/06/23	Changed slightly to group questions together on speech bubbles to highlight the responses. Give opportunity to look at the data collected so far.	Informative – some data had been looked at by participants, but some gave responses to the data in terms of their opinion. Five reflective notes from participants interviewed been returned.
26/06/23	Third Steering Group Meeting – date changed to a Monday so DHT could attend in	2 x parents (SP1 and (SP2); DHT, Head of ELC, Transition Coordinator and researcher	Looking at data collected from final individual interviews and discussing	Lots of great discussion and looking at what both the ELC and primary school wish to take forward.

	person 9.30am.		implications for practice. Individual comments on 3 slides – what to stop doing, keep doing, develop or introduce.	Information will be used as part of implications for practice and looking at power from a parent’s perspective – has what they have said had an impact on the changes being suggested. No reflective notes given out - general discussion about participation in group.
27/06/23	Email from Depute with changes going to be implemented for transition next term.	Depute email to researcher, Head of ELC and Transition Coordinator	Show changes already being put in place.	Support implication for practice.
Parent Focus Group/Individual Interviews				
27/03/23	First letters send home to all	Individually named envelopes to	To find out the number of participants	Five agreed to online and one afternoon.

	parents/carers about the research – included PIS and consent forms. Focus group would be on a Friday – morning, afternoon or online in evening.	parents/carers of children going to the primary school – introductory letter, PIS and consent forms.	who could take part in the research.	
09/05/23	Second letter sent to parents/carers to try and seek more parental involvement. Only a letter went out explaining that it would be individual interviews and to let me know when they would be available.	Individually named to those not previously returned forms. Still looking at focus group but opened up to a Monday, Tuesday or Friday.		Five more agreed – Monday AM - one; PM - three; online – two. Friday AM - one; PM - two; online - three (most gave multiple times).
12/05/23 (last date for replies)	Letter sent out indicating 19/05/23 meeting but needed to see if Zoom or MS	Six parents who had indicated they were happy to be involved online invites sent out.	To see which platform would be most suited – unsure if all parents had	Transition Coordinator had forgotten to hand out the letters (I had not been in the

	Teams would be easier.		access to MS Teams.	nursery that week to remind her to be given out) so decided to do Zoom.
12/05/23	Letter indicating the meeting would take place on the Friday 19 th via Zoom.	Letter to five people interested (one other parent had lots on so I decided not to involve them at present).	I took decision to go with Zoom as it was the easiest option.	One written reply confirming and one verbal reply confirming. One letter had not been given out as child was on holiday that week. One parent indicated that they could not do Friday but could do a Monday or Tuesday evening online instead. I needed email addresses to send out the link.
19/05/23	Zoom Scheduled	Researcher – zero of the parents came on – two had		Parent who had written confirming indicated later

		actually confirmed that they would be able to attend.		on via email child was unwell. Spoke to other parents a week later – they were going on holiday next day and had had things to do. Both happy to still be interviewed.
14/05/23	Letters sent out to parents who could meet in person for a focus group.	Researcher handed out some of the letters and left others for staff in ELC to give out.		Two replied they could and one now couldn't attend.
22/05/23	Focus Group arranged for parents who had returned and said they could take part in person on the Monday afternoon at 2pm. (I had verbally invited a parent who had been unable to	As the three parents had children who were morning sessions, I took the decision to do individual interviews in the morning as one parent had indicated on the Monday that they could not make the focus	To ascertain parental views regarding communication and parental engagement.	Changed to individual interviews.

	make the online meeting on the 19/05/23).	group in the afternoon, resulting in a focus group of two – hence deciding to undertake individual interviews.		
22/05/23	Individual Interview – Parent 1 (face-to-face).	Researcher and Parent 1 ELC Management Room 9.30am.	To ascertain parental views regarding communication and parental engagement.	Lots of data from interview to be compared with others.
22/05/23	Individual Interview – Parent 2 (face-to-face).	Researcher and Parent 2 ELC Management Room 10.30am.	To ascertain parental views regarding communication and parental engagement.	Lots of data from interview to be compared with others.
22/05/23	Individual Interview – Parent 3 (face-to-face).	Researcher and Parent 3 and younger child ELC Management Room 12noon.	To ascertain parental views regarding communication and parental engagement.	Lots of data from interview to be compared with others.
22/05/23	Final letter went out to parents/carers who had indicated they were			One reply received from parent who couldn't make the online

	interested in taking part in research – indicating that it was now individual interviews and will be continuing into June for interviews to take place.			focus on 19/05/23.
24/05/23	Individual Interview with Parent 4. The parent had been interested in taking part in research but was only free on a Wednesday. Initially a Zoom meeting but this changed to face-to-face as parent had never used Zoom.	Researcher and Parent 4 ELC Bistro – ELC 4pm.	To ascertain parental views regarding communication and parental engagement.	Data collected that could be compared to other collected from parents.

26/05/23	Individual Interview with Parent 5 – online via Zoom.	Researcher and Parent 5 – Online 6pm.	To ascertain parental views regarding communication and parental engagement.	Data collected that could be compared to other collected from parents.
31/05/23	Individual Interview with Parent 6 – online via MS Teams (rescheduled from 19/05/23 online focus group).	Researcher and Parent 6 – Online 6pm.	To ascertain parental views regarding communication and parental engagement.	Data collected that could be compared to other collected from parents.
07/06/23	Individual Interview with Parent 7 – online via MS Teams (parent on holiday and could not make focus group on 19/05/23).	Researcher and Parent 7 – Online 7pm.	To ascertain parental views regarding communication and parental engagement.	Data collected that could be compared to other collected from parents.
09/06/23	Individual Interview with Parent 8 – face-to-face (parent had missed the focus group on 19/05/23 and	Researcher and Parent 8 – ELC Visiting services Room 11.30am.	To ascertain parental views regarding communication and parental engagement.	Data collected that could be compared to other collected from parents.

	spoke to them about when free).			
19/06/23	Individual Interview with Parent 9 - online via MS Teams (one of the original parents but couldn't get correct email address).	Researcher and Parent 9 – Online 6.30pm.	To ascertain parental views regarding communication and parental engagement.	Data collected that could be compared to other collected from parents.
Education Staff Focus Groups				
05/05/23 (final date for replies)	Letter to invite the new Primary One teachers with PIS and consent form – given out via the DHT.	Individual invites to take part in the research as a focus group – three teachers.	To ascertain the views of the Primary One teachers for August 2023 regarding communication and parental engagement.	All three agreed to participate.
12/05/23	Focus Group with the Primary One teachers – face-to-face.	Researcher and the three primary one teachers for August 2023. Blue Primary School – multipurpose room – during assembly 11am.	To ascertain the views of the Primary One teachers for August 2023 regarding communication and parental engagement. Questions	Lots of data collected from the questions asked.

		This time had been agreed with DHT as she would need to arrange cover for the classes.	used were ones agreed at steering group first meeting.	
12/05/23 and 15/05/23	Focus Group with staff from the ELC – staff approached face-to-face	Staff were approached to ascertain who would be interested – criteria – staff who had been involved in previous transition/current transition at the ELC and were available depending on their shift pattern. PIS and Consent forms given out.	To ascertain the views of the ELC staff regarding communication and parental engagement.	Four agreed to take part on the date available.
18/05/23	Focus Group with ELC staff – face-to-face	2 x EYP, 1 PACS, 1 TL and Researcher. Management Meeting Room – 4pm.	To ascertain the views of the ELC staff regarding communication and parental engagement.	Lots of data collected that could be used to compare their thoughts with other participants
Throughout data	Reflective notes and	Following all steering group	To ascertain my reflective	Data collected will be used to

collection phase	accompanying notes written by myself.	meetings and individual interviews.	views and thoughts at these moments in time.	support and inform within thesis.
------------------	---------------------------------------	-------------------------------------	--	-----------------------------------

Appendix 25 – Steering Group Data Collection

Steering Group Meetings and Date	Data Source - Reflective Note (RN) or Other (stated)
First Meeting – 17/03/2023	Researcher (RN)
	Head of ELC (RN)
	Transition Coordinator (RN)
	Steering Parent 1 (RN)
	Steering Parent 3 (RN)
	DHT (email)
	Minutes of meeting
Meeting 2 – 09/06/2023	Head of ELC (RN)
	Transition Coordinator (RN)
	Steering Parent 1 (RN)
	Steering Parent 2 (RN)
	Researcher (RN)
	Minutes of meeting
Meeting 3 – 26/06/2023	Researcher (RN)
	All other participants – verbal feedback during meeting (meeting notes)
	Minutes of meeting